

**Early Cell Fate Specification in the amphipod crustacean,
*Parhyale hawaiiensis***

by

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Abstract

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When and how cells commit to different fates is critical to an embryo. The mechanisms underlying cell fate specification fall into two categories: cell-autonomous and cell-nonautonomous specification. Historically, early specification events leading to the three germ layers were thought to be primarily cell autonomous in embryos with invariant cell lineages. However, it is now clear that both mechanisms are employed during the specification of all types of embryos.

Parhyale hawaiiensis, an amphipod crustacean, displays a stereotypical cleavage pattern with an invariant cell lineage during early embryogenesis. Fate mapping of the eight-cell stage embryo demonstrates that each blastomere is fated to give rise to only one of the three germ layers or in the case of one of the blastomeres (*g*), the germline. However, it is not known if these cells are committed at this stage; therefore I set out to investigate how tightly early cell

lineage and cell fates are coupled in this species. Using cell ablations, a classic approach for determining the developmental potential of early blastomeres, I show that much regulation occurs within the three germ layers following ablation indicating that the fate of early blastomeres may not yet be committed at the eight-cell stage. Furthermore, these findings demonstrate the presence of mesoderm and ectoderm equivalence groups in *Parhyale*.

In addition, using molecular approaches, I cloned the *Parhyale* orthologs of genes with known roles in cell fate specification or germline development. Characterization of *vasa* suggests a conserved role for this gene in germ cell development, while the novel localization of β -*catenin* in what may be analogous to the germ plasm, which becomes restricted specifically to the germline, indicates a possible new role for β -*catenin*. In *Parhyale*, the germ cells are specified early in development by preformation (segregation of germline determinants). Ablation of the *g* blastomere, which exclusively gives rise to the germ cells, or its progeny, later in development, results in a loss of embryonic germ cells. However, these *g*-ablated animals are fertile and produce normal offspring demonstrating that replacement germ cells must be induced in post-embryonic stages. This is the first report of an animal that preferentially specifies its germline early in development, yet if forced, can also undergo germ cell induction suggesting that both cell-autonomous and nonautonomous germline specification mechanisms exist in *Parhyale*.

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Chapter I: Introduction

MECHANISMS OF CELL FATE SPECIFICATION

Many multicellular organisms begin life as a single totipotent cell that undergoes subsequent divisions and growth to give rise to an animal with three distinct axes—dorsoventral, anterioposterior, and left/right—and complex organs or structures that can be composed of different cell and tissue types. How cells are specified to give rise to this diversity and complexity is a fundamental question driving the field of developmental biology. In this chapter, I review key mechanisms of cell fate specification with particular attention to autonomous and nonautonomous specification during early embryogenesis. I then discuss the specification of a specialized cell type, the germ cell.

When and how cells commit to different cell fates is of critical importance to the embryo. Cell fate commitment can be defined as the processes that direct the specification and then determination of a cell prior to terminal differentiation (Harrison, 1933; Slack, 1991). The definition for specification has changed over time and varies depending on the criteria involved in assessing the state of a cell by experimental manipulation or by molecular characteristics (Davidson, 1991; Slack, 1991). For example, the classic criterion for specification is the isolation test. If cells are specified at a particular time, then they will still develop to give rise to their normal fate following isolation. More recently, with advances in molecular biology, many

researchers now use the expression of cell- or tissue-specific molecular markers to indicate specification. In either case, because a cell is “specified” that does not mean it cannot change its fate given different conditions. In contrast, a “determined” cell is irreversibly committed to a particular fate and transplantation or grafting of this cell to another region within an embryo cannot change its fate (Wolpert, 2007). In this dissertation, I consider specification any process that results in the generation of distinct cell types and determination the irreversible loss of developmental potential, i.e., commitment of a cell.

According to the textbook, *Developmental Biology*, specification can be divided into three modes: nonautonomous (conditional), autonomous, and syncytial (Davidson, 1991; Gilbert, 1997). Syncytial specification specifically characterizes specification in insects that initially develop in a syncytium, where cell division is incomplete, and therefore will not be discussed further here.

Nonautonomous Specification

Cell nonautonomous specification, or conditional specification, requires inductive signals via cell–cell communication or the action of morphogen gradients to specify cell fates. Upon receiving the signal(s), the responsive cell can initiate a particular specification program, which itself can be cell-autonomous or nonautonomous (Figure 1.1). This type of specification plays a large role in embryos that do not have an early fate map and whose cells are initially totipotent and then specified later in development, during blastula to gastrula stages, such as is found in some vertebrates. Historically, cell

nonautonomous specification has been associated with the term “regulative” development, whereby the remaining cells can “regulate” development by compensating for the removal of an early blastomere. Therefore, in these embryos, the potential of a cell is greater than what it was fated to be.

However, as I discuss below, no embryo displays strict regulative development throughout embryogenesis, as all embryos employ both nonautonomous and autonomous mechanisms for specifying cell fate (Lawrence and Levine, 2006).

Classic embryological tests for induction or nonautonomy include blastomere isolation and recombination studies and ablation studies (Slack, 1991). Isolation and recombination studies demonstrate whether a cell or group of cells is required to induce the predicted fate of another cell; they also test whether a cell can induce different fates in other cells. Ablations show whether a particular cell (or cells) acts as a signaling center. If so, its ablation would not only affect its own lineage, but that of others. At the molecular level, nonautonomous specification is primarily achieved by the action of signaling pathways that act on neighboring cells or at a distance (Horvitz and Herskowitz, 1992; Wolpert, 2007). For example, following a cell division, intercellular signaling between the sister cells or from other cells can induce different fates in initially equipotent sister cells (Figure 1.1) (Horvitz and Herskowitz, 1992). These equipotent cells are said to form an equivalence group, as the developmental potential of each cell is the same (Kimble, 1981). For example, in the nematode *Caenorhabditis elegans*, the anterior (ABa) and posterior (ABp) daughter cells of the AB blastomere have different fates based

on the fate map; however, when their positions are physically switched, the fates are reversed (Priess and Thomson, 1987). These results show that these two cells have the same potential; i.e., are equivalent, but that due to their position and a signal from another blastomere, in this case P2, they acquire different fates (Mango et al., 1994). Interestingly, the early blastomeres in *C.elegans* were initially thought to be specified primarily by cell-autonomous mechanisms.

Autonomous specification

Cell-autonomous specification means that a cell can follow its developmental program without input or instructions from other cells. This mode of specification is characterized by the segregation of cytoplasmic determinants, usually maternally provided RNAs or proteins that will then direct the specification program of that cell or cell lineage (Moody, 1999). Typically, embryos that display an early restriction in cell potential; i.e., those that are specified or determined early in development, are thought to be largely specified by maternal cytoplasmic determinants that have been parceled out within the egg or early zygote, such as that observed in nematodes, molluscs and ascidians (sea squirts) (Moody, 1999; Slack, 1991). Historically, this type of specification has been associated with the term “mosaic” development, whereby a cell’s fate is determined very early in development such that it can only develop as its fate map dictates, even in isolation, and upon ablation, it cannot be replaced by the remaining cells within the developing embryo. Therefore, these early embryos were thought to be composed of different

territories that were established very early by a cell-autonomous mechanism. However, it is not necessarily the case that the presence of cytoplasmic determinants equals strict cell autonomy, or that embryos that do not restrict cell fates until later in development do not also have cytoplasmic determinants that are important for proper patterning (Angerer and Angerer, 2000; Davidson et al., 1998; Schnabel, 1995; Yost et al., 1996). Mechanisms of segregating cytoplasmic determinants include, but are not limited to, intrinsically determined asymmetric cell division, cortical reorganization, specialized cytoplasm, and the use of specialized subcellular structures for RNA segregation (Astrow et al., 1987; Horvitz and Herskowitz, 1992; Kingsley et al., 2007; Lyczak et al., 2002). Moreover, these mechanisms are not mutually exclusive of one another and are often used in combination.

Asymmetric cell divisions generate sister cells with different fates (Horvitz and Herskowitz, 1992). Cell division can lead to the asymmetric inheritance of cytoplasmic determinants already differentially localized in the initial cell by other mechanisms, thus establishing a difference in the composition of the cell in the different halves, or it can lead to an asymmetric division plane that results in two daughter cells of unequal size that have different developmental potentials and will generate different fates (Figure 1.1). Interestingly, the mechanisms underlying the process of division may not be conserved (Ren and Weisblat, 2006). For example, in *C. elegans* and in the leech *Helobdella robusta*, the first division is unequal. In *C. elegans*, the sperm entry point initiates a cascade that leads to the differential localization of

specific cortical proteins, such as the partitioning defective (PAR) proteins, to the cortex of anterior or posterior regions at the one-cell stage (reviewed in Lyczak et al., 2002). These proteins are then involved in polarizing the mitotic spindle during the first unequal cleavage to give rise to the AB and P1 blastomeres (Grill et al., 2001; Labbe et al., 2004; Rose and Kemphues, 1998). In *H. robusta*, the first unequal division leads to the generation of the AB and CD blastomeres. The CD blastomere contains teloplasm, a specialized yolk-free cytoplasm, required in the D quadrant for subsequent specification events (Astrow et al., 1987; Pilon and Weisblat, 1997). In this animal, the PAR proteins are not localized at the one-cell stage and thus are not directing the unequal first cleavage, although they may play a role in later cleavages (Ren, 2005). Rather, it appears that the unequal division that generates the AB and CD blastomeres is driven more by the dynamics of the centrosome and spindle aster resulting in the asymmetric position of the spindle (Ren and Weisblat, 2006). In this example, a similar outcome—unequal first cleavage—is mediated by different underlying mechanisms.

In ascidians, a subcellular structure made of an electron-dense matrix called the centrosome attracting body (CAB) is dually responsible for the asymmetric cleavage planes during division and the successive anchoring and segregation of “postplasmic RNAs,” starting at the eight-cell stage specifically in the B4.1 blastomere, and then into the smaller posterior daughter cells in the next three divisions (Hibino et al., 1998; Iseto and Nishida, 1999; Nishikata et

al., 1999; Sasakura et al., 2000). In this case, the cells that inherit these RNAs are fated to become the primordial germ cells.

More recently, a novel mechanism that may be involved in the autonomous specification of cell fates has been described in the lophotrochozoan mollusc, *Ilyanassa obsoleta*. This mechanism is related to the general concept of cytoplasmic determinant segregation; however, in this case, the segregation of RNAs to cells with similar developmental fates is mediated in a centrosome-dependent manner (Lambert and Nagy, 2002). In this mechanism, after division, RNAs bind specific centrosomes that then, during prophase, move to a portion of cortex that will be inherited by only one daughter cell at the next division (Figure 1.1). It is estimated that 3%-4% of RNAs in *Ilyanassa* are localized via this method and that a great many of them may encode proteins with regulatory functions (Kingsley et al., 2007). The authors suggest that the prevalence of this mechanism for segregating RNAs may be correlated with constraints on cleavage patterns and cell fate in this mollusc and perhaps in spiralian in general (Kingsley et al., 2007). To date, this mechanism for RNA segregation has not been described in other systems. Therefore, it will be interesting to see if this phenomenon occurs outside of this mollusc and, if so, how widespread it is.

Evolution of cell fate mechanisms in closely related species

Even though the relative contribution of specification mechanisms may vary greatly between species, knowing the mechanism of specification in closely related species can lead to great insight into the evolution of those mechanisms

and the possible bias that could lead to phenotypic changes. Classic examples can be found in molluscs and nematodes (reviewed in Felix and Barriere, 2005). For example, in molluscs and spiralian, in general, specification of the D quadrant, a precursor of the organizer and mesoderm, is achieved either by induction from micromeres or by asymmetric divisions of cytoplasmic determinants (Freeman and Lundelius, 1992; Henry, 2002; Martindale, 1986; van den Biggelaar and Guerrier, 1979). However, many of the downstream specification events that require the proper specification of the D quadrant are highly conserved, even at the molecular level (reviewed in Lambert, 2007). In this case, the flexibility or evolvability of the D quadrant specification event does not appear to affect subsequent cellular interactions or eventual morphologies. This example highlights the fact that mechanisms during early development need not be the same to ultimately arrive at the same conserved state. Furthermore, it underscores the importance of comparative studies at the molecular level between related species.

Development is dynamic and progressive, and cell states are changing continually; the relative role of cell autonomous or nonautonomous specification can only be defined at discrete times during the path to differentiation. Furthermore, knowledge about the specification mechanisms in closely related species add data valuable for understanding the evolution of pattern formation.

ROLE OF CELL LINEAGE IN CELL FATE SPECIFICATION

In the past, and to a lesser degree in the present, studies of cell lineage were so intimately tied to the idea of mosaic or regulative development that the mechanisms also became synonymous with those concepts (Lawrence and Levine, 2006; Slack, 1991). However, the study of cell lineage and its role in cell fate specification has evolved over the last century. Although, the terms mosaic and regulative development have become archaic as classifications for any one embryo, they do provide a historical context in which to understand the more relevant concepts of cell-autonomous or nonautonomous specification. Because both modes of specification are used at some point in the development of a given embryo, cells acquire different fates using both cell-autonomous or cell nonautonomous mechanisms to varying degrees. Of course, that is not to imply that cell lineage is not important. Knowing a cell's lineage is one of the first steps towards understanding the underlying patterning mechanisms that govern that cell's fate. For this reason, embryos with invariant lineages provide some of the best examples in which to study the molecular basis of cell-autonomy or cell signaling in cell fate specification (Nishida, 2005; Schnabel, 1995). Examples of embryos with invariant early lineages can be found in many metazoan phyla (Moody, 1999; Slack, 1991).

C. elegans is a classic example of an embryo with an essentially invariant lineage in which cell lineage and the cytoplasmic distribution of determinants play a major role in specifying cell fates (Goldstein et al., 1998; Labouesse and Mango, 1999; Lyczak et al., 2002; Schnabel, 1997; Sulston and White, 1980).

However, more recently, it has become clear that, in *C.elegans*, cell–cell communication and induction are also crucial components of establishing early cell fates (Goldstein, 1992; Goldstein, 1995; Priess and Thomson, 1987; Schnabel, 1995). In this case, a great deal of information is available that describes the genetic basis of these interactions. Using this information, a two-phase model for embryonic patterning has been proposed that integrates a lineage-dependent mechanism with an organ/tissue identity–specification mechanism (Labouesse and Mango, 1999). Lineage-driven anterior–posterior fate specification and the activity of so-called “blastomere identity” genes are first employed to establish an “address” for a polyclonal group of cells to specific regions or fields within the embryo. Once this field has been established, the action of organ/tissue specific genes then direct the patterning of cells within those fields that are, at this point, independent of cell lineage. In this specification model, cell lineage is tightly coupled to cell fate, but additional intercellular patterning mechanisms also account for how cells reach their ultimate fate.

Among the chordates, ascidians have emerged as a new and powerful developmental system for studying cell fate mechanisms. Ascidians also have an invariant lineage in which cell fates, which are determined prior to gastrulation, are tightly coupled to cell lineage (Conklin, 1905; Nishida, 1987; Nishida, 1992). In the past, ascidians were thought to be primarily patterned by the segregation of maternal determinants; i.e., cell-autonomously (Nishida, 1992; Reverberi and Minganti, 1946). This is in contrast to another chordate,

Xenopus, in which cell lineage can be uncoupled from cell fate, and, therefore, patterned by induction. Interestingly, comparison of the fate maps of ascidians and *Xenopus* show a high degree of similarity in terms of the distribution of tissue territories, suggesting a common chordate fate map (Kourakis and Smith, 2005). Despite differences in the mechanisms establishing many of those fates, new findings have uncovered some molecular similarities and many inductive interactions that are important for the normal expression of cell fate in ascidians. Therefore, views regarding how ascidians develop are changing as more and more inductive events are found to be essential. But, invariant cell lineages can only tell one so much. Experimental manipulations and molecular analyses are required to get a more accurate picture of the mechanisms involved in cell fate specification.

GERMLINE SPECIFICATION: EPIGENESIS AND PREFORMATION

Primordial germ cells (PGC) are the precursors to the gametes—eggs and sperm. Their highly specialized and critical role in development has received much attention due to their immortal nature and ability to propagate the next generation. How and when these cells segregate from the prospective somatic lineages during embryogenesis is a major question in the field.

Germ cells can be distinguished from somatic cells by several different criteria using histological and, more recently, molecular markers (reviewed in Extavour and Akam, 2003). For example, the nuclei of germ cells tend to be larger and more rounded and the cytoplasm frequently has electron-dense

bodies. Germline-specific markers are used commonly in research today, and several of the genes expressed in germ cells are conserved among animals across the phyla. One such marker, *Vasa*, a member of the DEAD family of RNA helicases, is used frequently to identify germ cells, due to its high conservation in germline development in all metazoans studied to date. In some systems, newly specified germ cells are transcriptionally quiescent compared to the surrounding somatic cells, and therefore can be further identified by the lack of active RNA polymerase (reviewed in Strome and Lehmann, 2007). These characteristics, combined with lineage studies, allows for the accurate identification and tracking of germ cells during development.

Germline specification generally falls under two main mechanisms: epigenesis and preformation (Figure 1.2). Epigenetic specification requires a nonautonomous inductive event occurring later in development, in which surrounding cells direct the specification of the primordial germ cells from a subset of cells (the remaining cells go on to make somatic derivatives). Preformation is characterized by the early specification of germ cells via the segregation of germline determinants, generally in a specialized cytoplasm—the germ plasm—that cell-autonomously promotes germ cell fate. Clearly, specification of germ cells is similar to specification of other cells, being either cell-autonomous (preformation) or nonautonomous (epigenesis). I have chosen to use the older terms—epigenesis and preformation—following the nomenclature of Nieuwkoop and Sutasurya (1981), which continues to be used in recent literature (Extavour and Akam, 2003).

Epigenesis

The best-studied examples of epigenetic germline specification are found in vertebrates, especially in mammals and urodele amphibians. In the mouse, markers for definitive germ cells, such as alkaline phosphatase, are not present until E7 (Chiquoine, 1954). Lineage analysis suggests that germ cells arise around E6.5 from the proximal epiblast (Lawson and Hage, 1994). Therefore, germ cells are not present at the earliest stages of development. However, the strongest evidence for the induction of germ cells arises from transplantation studies in which cells from an area that normally does not give rise to PGCs can be induced to make PGCs if transplanted to the proximal epiblast (Tam and Zhou, 1996). Some of the molecular mechanisms that control this specification event have been described (Figure 1.2). BMP proteins, members of the TGF- β superfamily of signaling molecules, are required in the extraembryonic ectoderm and visceral endoderm to promote cells in the epiblast towards a germ-cell fate. Expression of other genes, such as *fragilis*, *stella*, and *Blimp1*, then directs the differentiation of these cells into PGCs (reviewed in Hayashi et al., 2007; McLaren, 2003).

Another vertebrate that uses epigenetic specification is the axolotl *Ambystoma mexicanum* (Johnson et al., 2003). Based on ultrastructural and molecular evidence, this axolotl does not have germ plasm (Johnson et al., 2001; Nieuwkoop and Sutasurya, 1979), but rather induces PGCs from the lateral plate mesoderm, in part, from inductive signals emanating from the ventral vegetal blastomeres (presumptive endoderm) (Boterenbrood and

Nieuwkoop, 1973; Humphrey, 1929; Ikenishi and Nieuwkoop, 1978; Sutasurya and Nieuwkoop, 1974). It is unclear how conserved the epigenetic program may be between mammals and axolotls at the molecular level. Recent findings suggest that BMPs may be involved in promoting PGC fate in axolotls and that germline markers shared between these two groups, such as *Oct-4* and *dazzle*, share greater sequence homology to each other than to orthologs in another amphibian, *Xenopus laevis* (Johnson et al., 2003). The researchers suggest that these findings may reflect constraints on gene evolution due to the regulative mechanism of PGC specification in axolotls and mice (Johnson et al., 2003). Based on these findings and evidence in other vertebrate groups, epigenetic mechanisms dominate and are likely the ancestral mode of specification in vertebrates (reviewed in Extavour and Akam, 2003).

Preformation

Germ cell specification by preformation has been extensively examined in several developmental systems such as in *C.elegans*, *Drosophila*, and *Xenopus* (Figure 1.2) (reviewed in Mahowald, 2001; Saffman and Lasko, 1999; Seydoux and Schedl, 2001). In each of these cases, the germline is segregated from the presumptive somatic lineages early in development, prior to gastrulation. In organisms that undergo early specification of the germline, presumptive germ cells are cytologically distinct from the somatic lineages due to their large nuclei and the presence of the germ plasm—a specialized cytoplasmic region composed of mitochondria, electron-dense granules, proteins, and RNAs—that direct the specification and differentiation of PGCs

(Kloc et al., 2001; Mahowald, 2001; Wolf et al., 1983). Many of these proteins and RNAs have been characterized in these groups, and several of them are highly conserved between groups. However, rather than focus on the molecular mechanisms of germ cell specification between different groups, I instead describe the initial formation of germ cells to highlight the commonality of germ plasm inheritance into the prospective PGCs at early stages of development.

In *C.elegans*, the germ, or P, granules, are initially distributed throughout the egg. Several mechanisms work to asymmetrically segregate the P granules to the cells that become the PGCs. First, fertilization results in dramatic cytoplasmic and cortical rearrangements that not only establishes the anterior–posterior axis, but also results in the posterior segregation of the P granules. Subsequent asymmetric cell divisions in the P blastomere lineage further segregate the P granules, while degradation in the somatic lineages removes any remaining P granules. Finally, the process is complete with symmetric division of the P4 blastomere to make Z2 and Z3, the founder PGCs. These cells will not divide and will remain transcriptionally quiescent until after hatching (reviewed in Strome and Lehmann, 2007).

In *Drosophila*, the localization of germline determinants and pole plasm to the posterior pole is initiated, prior to fertilization, during oogenesis by a series of protein interactions that anchor determinants to the posterior pole. Early embryogenesis in *Drosophila* is characterized by nuclear divisions without corresponding cell divisions thus giving rise to a syncytial blastoderm.

Following cellularization, the cells that inherit the posterior pole plasm, the pole cells, become the PGCs (reviewed in Saffman and Lasko, 1999).

In *Xenopus*, germ plasm material is localized to the vegetal pole of the egg in a structure called the mitochondrial cloud, which then fragments into hundreds of smaller islands (reviewed in Saffman and Lasko, 1999). After fertilization, these islands aggregate into four clusters that are then inherited by the four most vegetal blastomeres at the 32-cell stage. Following subsequent asymmetric divisions, only a few of the cells ultimately inherit the germ plasm thus becoming the PGCs (reviewed in (Kloc et al., 2001; Saffman and Lasko, 1999)). Together, these examples emphasize the importance of the germ plasm despite differences in the mechanisms leading to its segregation.

Evolution of germline specification in arthropods

Although germ cells are undeniably one of the most important cell types in development, the variation of developmental mechanisms resulting in their specification is striking. This suggests the convergent evolution of preformation or epigenesis in many different phyla. For most arthropods, there is no evidence of early segregation of germ cells, although exceptions have been described in some insects, crustaceans, and spiders (reviewed in Extavour and Akam, 2003). Although, the evidence implies that epigenesis is more common within the arthropod lineage, it is unclear which mechanism is ancestral. In-depth comparisons of more nonmodel organisms within and basal to the arthropods will be required to determine which mechanism is

ancestral, as well as the evolutionary history of germline specification in related groups.

PARHYALE HAWAIENSIS—A MODEL CRUSTACEAN SYSTEM

Arthropods represent one of the most diverse groups of organisms found on the planet. However, much of what is known about arthropod development has been gleaned primarily from research in the fruit fly *Drosophila melanogaster*. With the reincarnation of “evo-devo” as a discipline unto itself and recent technological advances in genomics, more nonmodel systems are being developed to appropriately fill key gaps within the metazoans. One such arthropod, *Parhyale hawaiiensis* (Crustacea, Malacostraca, Peracarida), is emerging as a useful arthropod and crustacean developmental system in which to address interesting questions at the interface of evolution and development.

In order to understand evolutionary histories, a phylogenetic framework is first necessary. Recent metazoan phylogenies, although still contentious, place bilaterians into one of three main superclades: the Deuterstomes, the Ecdysozoa, and the Lophotrochozoa (Aguinaldo et al., 1997; Ruiz-Trillo et al., 1999). The ecdysozoan clade includes the nematodes, priapulids, onychophorans, tardigrades, and arthropods, among others (Figure 1.3A). Arthropods comprise the myriapods, chelicerates, crustaceans, and hexapods (insects). It is widely accepted that the hexapods and crustaceans form a Pancrustacean clade, although the mono- or paraphyly within each group is debated (Nardi et al., 2003; Schram, 2004).

Crustaceans are a highly diverse and speciose group of arthropods that can be divided into two major groups, the nonmalacostracans and the malacostracans—with most of the phenotypic diversity seen within the malacostracans (Brusca and Brusca, 2003). Malacostracan crustaceans, which include the more commonly recognized and commercially important shrimps, crabs, lobsters, and krill, are united by the conserved characteristic of having five head segments, eight thoracic segments, and six or seven abdominal segments (Brusca and Brusca, 2003).

Amphipods are malacostracan crustaceans more commonly known as beach scuds or beach hoppers as they are found on beaches all over the world. However, amphipods can also be found in fresh water or on land. In the Patel lab, we study various aspects of development and evolution in the amphipod, *Parhyale hawaiiensis* (Figure 1.3B). *Parhyale* is widely distributed throughout the tropics, primarily in mangrove forests (Barnard, 1965; Myers, 1985; Shoemaker, 1956). However, a considerable advantage of working with *Parhyale* is the ease with which it can be reared in the laboratory. The Patel lab *Parhyale* culture, originally seeded from animals found in the filtration system at the Shedd Aquarium in Chicago, are raised at 26° C in shallow plastic tubs with artificial seawater, and they subsist primarily on kelp and carrots. Males grasp females in the mating behavior of amplexus until the female molts and can be fertilized. Following fertilization, females lay the embryos externally in a ventrally located brood pouch. Mating pairs and/or gravid females are easy to identify and collect; thus, obtaining embryos at various

stages is a simple task. The approximate generation time is eight weeks and adults reproduce year round, so that embryos are always easily accessible.

Embryogenesis in *Parhyale hawaiensis*

Browne et al. (2006) recently described a developmental staging series for *Parhyale*. I have summarized embryogenesis in Figure 1.4, highlighting the key stages that are most important in this dissertation. Briefly, embryogenesis takes approximately 220 hours (10 days) at 26°C, resulting in a direct-developing hatchling. The early cleavages are holoblastic or total, as well as radial. The first cell division is slightly asymmetric, followed by two more visibly asymmetric divisions (Figure 1.4A–C). At Stage 4 (S4), the embryo is composed of four larger cells, the macromeres, and four smaller cells, the micromeres (Figure 1.4D). After this point, divisions become highly asynchronous and cell divisions become superficial, as the yolk is pushed towards the center of the embryo (Figure 1.4E). At S8, gastrulation begins with the condensation of Mav and g blastomeres into a “rosette” and the condensation and proliferation of the ectodermal cells at the anterior ventral pole into a germdisc, followed by ingression of the segmental mesoderm and endoderm clones (Figure 1.4F). By S10, the cells of the germdisc organize into a clearly visible germband with ordered rows, called parasegment precursor rows (PSPR), that will subsequently undergo two rounds of anterior–posterior divisions to give rise to the parasegment, the precursor to morphological segments. These divisions result in the elongation and elaboration of the germband (Figure 1.4G–I). As the germband elongates (S10–S19), appendage

formation begins, anteriorly, with the condensation of the antennal and gnathal appendages and progresses posteriorly until all appendages have formed (Figure 1.4J and K). Organogenesis of the major systems completes embryogenesis resulting in a hatchling that resembles a little adult (Figure 1.4L).

Parhyale fate map at the eight-cell stage (S4)

In *Parhyale*, the first three divisions are holoblastic yet asymmetric and highly stereotyped. The first cleavage plane spreads from the site of the polar bodies, thus indicating the animal–vegetal axis where, in other organisms, the polar bodies also mark the animal pole. The second division is perpendicular to the first, resulting in four cells of unequal size and arrangement. At this stage, the anterior–posterior axis is evident. The third division is highly asymmetric resulting in four micromeres at the vegetal pole. Using the stereotyped cleavages as a guide, Gerberding et al. (2002) generated a fate map of the eight-cell stage demonstrating that each blastomere at the eight-cell stage is normally fated to give rise to only one germ layer, or in the case of one of the blastomeres, the germline (Figure 1.5A). The germ layer fates are segregated such that three of the macromeres, El, Er, and Ep, generate all the ectoderm of the animal in a spatially restricted manner, while the fourth macromere, Mav, gives rise to the visceral mesoderm and some anterior somatic mesoderm. The four micromeres are fated to give rise to the germline (g), endoderm (en), and segmental mesoderm on the left and right sides (ml and mr). Therefore, not only has the anterior–posterior axis been established by

the eight-cell stage and left–right differences are apparent, but the germ layers have also been segregated.

The g blastomere and germline development in *Parhyale*

The progeny of the g blastomere divides several times to give rise to between 12 and 16 cells during embryogenesis (Extavour, 2005) and personal observations). At early germband stages, the g lineage is located in a single cluster beneath the ectoderm near the presumptive mandibular segment (Figure 1.5B). Around S15 (80 hrs of development), the cluster segregates into two bilateral clusters that then migrate along the visceral mesoderm towards the dorsal side of the embryo where the somatic gonad is eventually located—near the fourth thoracic segment (Figure 1.5C, D). At juvenile stages, these cells assume a linear arrangement, likely along the length of the maturing somatic gonad (Figure 1.5E). Although oogenesis has been studied in the amphipod *Orchestia gammarellus* at the ultrastructural level (Zerbib, 1980) the development of the PGCs from hatching to sexual maturity, in crustaceans, has not been investigated in great detail using modern techniques.

Blastomere isolations in *Parhyale*

In addition to fate mapping, blastomere isolations have been done in *Parhyale*, specifically addressing the autonomous specification of germ-cell fate from the g blastomere. Extavour (2005) separated blastomeres at the two-, four-, and eight-cell stages and then assayed for the presence of the highly conserved germline marker, Vasa, in the isolated aggregates. She found that

only the g blastomere gives rise to Vasa-positive cells and that no other cells from the eight-cell stage can, suggesting that the germline is cell-autonomously specified by the eight-cell stage. Furthermore, her findings suggest that a germline determinant segregates asymmetrically at the second cell division and then becomes restricted to the g blastomere. As for the other lineages, the lack of distinguishing characteristics and molecular markers of early cell fate make it currently impossible to assess the state of specification of these cells following isolation. However, based on these experiments, another conclusion can be drawn. Isolation of blastomeres at the two-, four- and eight-cell stages does not recover entire embryos, demonstrating that developmental potential is already restricted at the two-cell stage and that the earliest blastomeres are not multipotent, which is a hallmark of mosaic development. Based on the fate map and blastomere isolations, the evidence suggests that, in *Parhyale*, the early blastomeres may be committed very early in development.

In this dissertation, I use both classic experimental embryology and modern molecular biology in an attempt to move beyond the fate map and to describe in greater detail the possible mechanisms involved in establishing cell fates in *Parhyale*. The overarching questions throughout this dissertation are: what are the developmental potentials of early blastomeres, when are cells committed during development, and what are the mechanisms involved in establishing early cell fates or asymmetries in *Parhyale*? Specifically, I address the following questions:

1. How does ablation of ectodermal lineages at three different time points affect cell fate and development in *Parhyale*?
2. Are β -catenin gene products localized in the early embryo suggestive of a role in establishing either early cell asymmetries or cell fates?
3. Is there a conserved pattern of localization of *vasa* transcripts in the primordial germ cells (PGC) in *Parhyale*?
4. What is the effect of ablation of the germline cell(s) on the subsequent development and reproductive ability of *Parhyale*?

To answer the first question, I used photoablation to kill individual cells and cell labeling to follow the lineages of other cells to determine if and how different lineages respond to cell ablation. In Chapter II, I describe experiments that demonstrate that ectoderm and mesoderm ablations can be compensated for in a temporally and spatially restricted manner. In Chapter III, I address the second and third questions. I describe the cloning and localization of the *Parhyale* orthologs of *vasa* and β -catenin during development. *vasa* transcripts are localized widely during the earliest cleavages, but then become restricted specifically to the PGCs suggesting a conserved role in marking the germline. β -catenin transcripts are asymmetrically localized at the one-cell stage and become restricted specifically in the g blastomere, which gives rise to the germ cells. β -catenin may be a germline determinant that is localized to what may be the germ plasm, a specialized cytoplasm involved in the early specification of germ cells. Finally,

in Chapter IV, I address the fourth question by ablating the germline and examining subsequent development of the animal. Germline-ablated embryos have a complete loss of PGCs during embryogenesis; however, they are fertile as adults, suggesting they have an inductive mechanism for germline specification in the event of germline loss during embryogenesis. These findings not only demonstrate the remarkable regulative capacity of *Parhyale hawaiiensis*, but also contribute to a greater understanding of the process of cell fate specification and germline specification in a non-insect arthropod.

Figure 1.1 Mechanisms of cell fate specification

Schematic diagramming the two main modes of specification: cell-nonautonomous and cell-autonomous. Nonautonomous specification is characterized by inductive signals from other cells. Autonomous specification can be achieved by several different mechanisms. Shown are asymmetric inheritance of cytoplasmic determinants, asymmetric cell division, and segregation of centrosomally-localized RNAs.

Nonautonomous specification

Autonomous specification

Figure 1.2 Modes of germline specification: Epigenesis and Preformation

Schematic showing specification of PGC fate in several model developmental systems. In the top diagram, epigenetic specification in the mouse is shown (adapted from Hayashi et al., 2007). Cells (green) receive signals from surrounding tissues making them competent to further induce PGC fate through activation of other genes, such as *fragilis* (dark orange), *stella* (blue) and *Blimp1* (light orange) in a subset of proximal epiblast cells. In the bottom diagram, preformation and the inheritance of P-granules in *C.elegans*, pole plasm in *Drosophila* and germ plasm in *Xenopus* are shown. In each case, the germ plasm or its equivalent is depicted in red. (Adapted from Saffman and Lasko, 1999; Strome and Lehmann, 2007)

Epigenesis

Preformation

Figure 1.3 *Parhyale hawaiiensis*, an amphipod crustacean

(A) Phylogeny of amphipods within the context of Crustacea (purple), Arthropoda (orange), and Ecdysozoa (blue). Adapted from the Tree of Life Web Project: <http://www.tolweb.org/>. This tree is a compilation of data from many resources listed on the webpage. Many of the relationships are not resolved between phyla. Indeed, evidence suggests that the Crustacea is paraphyletic (gray bar) (Schram, 2004) and that the Hexapods may also be paraphyletic (Nardi et al., 2003). (*) indicates phyla where holoblastic or total cleavages are observed. (B) Adult male and female *Parhyale*. The male, picture on top, has segments labeled. The head (C1 +T1) is considered the seven most anterior segments. C1, the cephalon, includes a preantennal segment, antennae 1 and 2, mandible, maxillae 1 and 2. T1 is the first thoracic segment. The trunk is composed of the remaining seven thoracic segments (T2–T8) and six abdominal segments (A1–A6). Photograph in (B) from (Browne et al., 2005).

A

B

Figure 1.4 Stages of *Parhyale hawaiiensis* embryogenesis

(A–F) Live darkfield images (G–L) Fixed embryos stained for DAPI, a nuclear marker. (A) S1: one-cell embryo. (B) S2: two-cell embryo. (C) S3: four-cell embryo. (D) S4: eight-cell embryo. (E) S6: soccerball stage. The divisions become asynchronous and superficial. (F) S8: gastrulation. The cells have begun to migrate to the anterior ventral side (to the left) to make the germdisc. (G, H) S11 and S14, respectively: germband elongation. Ventral views. The posterior cells organize and divide into parasegments at these stages. (I, J, K) S19, S20, and S23, respectively. Lateral views; anterior to the left. Appendage formation. (L) S28: hatchling. Amphipods undergo direct development resulting in an animal that looks similar to the adult. Photographs from (Browne et al., 2005).

Figure 1.5 Fate map of the eight-cell stage and germline development

(A) Schematic showing the fate, at germband stages, of individual blastomeres derived from the eight-cell stage (adapted from Price, 2005). Three of the large macromeres, Er, El and Ep, (blue) give rise to the ectoderm on the right, left and posterior regions, respectively. Mav (orange) gives rise to visceral and anterior mesoderm. The micromeres, ml and mr (red) give rise to the segmental mesoderm on the left and right sides, respectively. en (green) gives rise to endoderm and g (yellow) gives rise to the germ cells. (B–E) Embryos injected with lineage tracer in the g blastomere at the eight-cell stage and then followed to the indicated stage. (B) Dorsal view of S13 embryo (72hrs) stained for the lineage tracer, DsRed (red) and DAPI (blue). The germ cells (red) are a single cluster overlying the region of maxillae 1 and 2. (C) Live, ventral view of S19 (96hrs) embryo. The lateral migration of one of the two bilateral cluster of germ cells (red) is shown. (D) Live, lateral view of S23 (144hrs) embryo. The germ cells (red) are migrating dorsally towards the site of the gonads. (E) Two-week old hatchling. Germ cells (red) are visible in two strands along the dorsal side.

Chapter II: Regulation of Germ Layer Specification in *Parhyale hawaiiensis*

SUMMARY

Parhyale hawaiiensis, an amphipod crustacean, displays a stereotypical cleavage pattern with an invariant cell lineage during early embryogenesis. The earliest cell divisions are holoblastic and asymmetrical, resulting in an embryo that consists of four macromeres and four micromeres by the eight-cell stage. Lineage studies performed at this stage demonstrate that each blastomere is fated to give rise to only one of the three germ layers or in the case of one of the blastomeres, the germline. However, it is not known if these cells are specified or determined at this early stage, and we set out to investigate how tightly the early cell lineage and cell fates are coupled in this species. Cell ablations are a classic method for addressing how lineage is coupled to cell fate, and utilizing this approach, we found that regulation can occur between lineage-restricted equivalency groups that give rise to the mesoderm and ectoderm germ layers. Our results show that loss of a mesoderm-producing or an ectoderm-producing blastomere at the eight-cell stage or its progeny at gastrulation can result in a normal embryo, but ablation at germband stages results in the permanent loss of that tissue. Commitment of blastomeres to an ectoderm or mesoderm fate appears irreversibly established at the eight-cell stage, yet, within germ layers,

fates are not determined until after gastrulation. *Parhyale* represents a clear case where cell fate and cell lineage can be uncoupled during early cleavages.

INTRODUCTION

Bilaterian embryos are comprised of three germ layers—the ectoderm, the mesoderm, and the endoderm—that are subsequently subdivided into different tissue and cell types from those initial germ layers. However, all three germ layers are initially derived from a single totipotent progenitor cell, the fertilized egg. The three germ layers arise when the fertilized egg divides to produce the embryonic cells that become committed through the refinement of a hierarchy of specification events. The commitment of germ layers is of critical importance to the proper development of the embryo as it is one of the earliest decisions embryos make within the developmental hierarchy towards terminal cellular differentiation (Slack, 1991).

Embryos with stereotypical early cleavage patterns provide the best examples in which to study the fate and commitment of cells because individual blastomeres can be labeled and followed on a cell-by-cell basis. Several different groups, such as molluscs, ascidians, and nematodes, have stereotypical early cleavages that have been fate mapped (Dictus and Damen, 1997; Nishida, 1987; Sulston et al., 1983). Although fate maps can describe with great precision the normal fate of a cell, it does not imply that the fates are committed at that point in development (reviewed in Wolpert, 2007).

A classic approach to determining if or when cells are committed to certain cell fates is to ablate those cells and determine if the resulting embryo is deficient for structures that would have arisen from the ablated cells. If the resulting embryo did have a loss of the ablated lineage, it would suggest that the fate of that particular blastomere was fixed or committed at that stage. In addition, it would suggest that other lineages might also be committed, as they did not compensate for the ablated cell. On the other hand, if the resulting embryo was not deficient for the ablated lineage, then it would suggest that some other lineage(s) were able to compensate for the loss of the ablated cell, and thus, that their fates not irreversibly committed at this point in time. Another possible outcome is that, not only, is the ablated lineage absent, but other lineage(s) may also be affected. Therefore, cell ablations may uncover the presence of inductive interactions originating from the ablated cell. Furthermore, ablations applied at different times in development can reveal key intervals during the progressive specification and determination of germ layers and their derivatives.

A major question is to what extent is cell lineage linked to the developmental potential of a given blastomere. In some developmental systems, such as the nematode, *Caenorhabditis elegans*, cell lineage is intimately linked to cell fate (Sulston et al., 1983). Studies show that commitment of germ layers occurs shortly after blastomeres form and that cells are not compensated for following ablation (Sulston et al., 1983). Yet in other systems, such as the sea urchin, cell lineage can be largely uncoupled from cell

fate and it is the location of cells within the embryo that determines the ultimate fate of that cell. An exception in sea urchins is the micromere lineage, which is committed to a skeletogenic fate shortly after forming (reviewed in Davidson et al., 1998). Therefore, even within a single embryo, different lineages can have varying developmental potentials. Historically, blastomere specification in *C. elegans* was thought to be achieved primarily cell-autonomously by segregation of cytoplasmic determinants, while the specification in sea urchins would have largely been achieved nonautonomously by cell–cell interactions and induction (reviewed in Wolpert, 2007). However, such distinctions cannot be made on the level of the whole embryo. It is now known that most, if not all, embryos studied to date employ both mechanisms during the refinement of cell fates.

Little is known about the mechanism of blastomere fate specification in crustaceans. Previous blastomere isolation and ablation studies in malacostracan crustaceans suggest that the endoderm, mesoderm and germ cells are specified by a cell-autonomous mechanism likely involving the segregation of cytoplasmic determinants (reviewed in Davidson, 1991; Green, 1971). More recently, detailed cell lineage data have been obtained for several malacostracan crustaceans that display holoblastic cleavage: the tiger shrimp *Sicyonia ingentis* and two amphipods *Parhyale* and *Orchestia cavimana* (Gerberding et al., 2002; Hertlzer and Clark, 1992; Wolff and Scholtz, 2002). These studies show that fate maps from early cleavage stages link cell lineage to particular tissue types. Isolation and recombination studies in *S. ingentis*

suggest that the mesendoderm lineage is autonomously specified and determined by the four-cell stage as determined by characteristics such as cell size and cleavage pattern (Hertzler et al., 1994). Modern experimental evidence to convincingly support these claims have been lacking; thus, the molecular underpinnings of any of these events are unknown.

Parhyale hawaiiensis embryos have complete yet unequal early cleavages. The first cleavage plane starts from the site of the polar bodies and is slightly asymmetric. At the second division, the anteroposterior axis is evident by formation of three larger cells and one smaller cell. The third division is very asymmetric resulting in four macromeres and four micromeres. Previous cell lineage studies of this amphipod have shown that cells at the eight-cell stage give rise to highly stereotyped lineages (Gerberding et al., 2002; Figure 1.1). The three largest macromeres, El, Er, and Ep, generate all the ectoderm of the embryo in a clonally restricted pattern, while the fourth macromere, Mav, gives rise to the anterior somatic mesoderm and the visceral mesoderm of the gut. The micromeres, ml and mr, comprise the segmental mesoderm on the left and right sides, respectively, via the formation and division of mesoteloblasts and their progeny, the mesoblasts. The last two micromeres, en and g, give rise to the endoderm and germline, respectively. The specification and regulation of the germline will be discussed in greater detail in Chapters III and IV. Based on the stereotypical cleavage pattern, very early segregation of germ layer fates, and an essentially invariant fate map of the eight-cell stage

embryo, *Parhyale* is a perfect candidate for addressing questions of germ layer commitment, as well as, what role segregation of determinants or cell–cell interactions play in determining germ layer fates (Gerberding et al., 2002).

Although the early restriction in cell fates in *Parhyale* is highly suggestive of a cell lineage-based mechanism that likely involves the asymmetric localization of cytoplasmic determinants in establishing those cell fates, it is currently unknown to what extent localized maternal factors may be influencing cell fates. Blastomere isolations, with regards to germline specification, have been done in *Parhyale* (Extavour, 2005). Based on isolations at the two, four, and eight cell stages, a germline specific determinant appears to be asymmetrically localized as early as the two-cell stage to cell autonomously specify the germline. Unfortunately, in this case, due to the lack of molecular markers for early germ layer-specific cell types, isolation studies cannot address the specification state of the other blastomeres. Therefore, from a technical perspective, ablations provide a suitable alternative to address questions of cell fate commitment in *Parhyale*.

Previous work performed by Price (2005) demonstrates that ablation of any of the mesoderm blastomeres (ml, mr or Mav) at the eight-cell stage can result in a viable hatchling with no obvious deficits in mesodermal tissue. This demonstrates that other lineages can compensate for the loss of the mesoderm blastomere. Ablations combined with cell labeling of other lineages demonstrate that the ablation of ml or mr (segmental mesoderm) at the eight-

cell stage is compensated for by the progeny of Mav (visceral mesoderm and anterior somatic mesoderm) (Figure 2.1-1). In the reciprocal experiment, the progeny of ml and mr compensate for the ablation of Mav, on the left and right sides respectively. However, when Price ablates the progeny of ml and/or mr just after mesoteloblast formation at 56hrs post fertilization (S10), she finds that the mesoteloblasts do not get replaced, suggesting that, at this point in development, the capacity to compensate is no longer present within the Mav lineage (Figure 2.1-2). Her findings suggest that the three mesoderm-producing blastomeres, while committed at the eight-cell stage to a mesodermal fate, may not yet be committed to their predicted fate. Therefore these blastomeres form a mesoderm equivalence group that has the developmental potential to compensate for each other in the event of ablation.

At the same time Price was investigating the mesoderm, I began my investigation of the ectoderm, endoderm, and germline. In collaboration with Price and Roberta Hannibal, a graduate student in the Patel lab, we make the preliminary observations described below.

Ablation of any blastomere at the eight-cell stage can result in a viable hatchling

Based on the fate map by Gerberding et al., (2002), the cell lineage of *Parhyale hawaiiensis* embryos at the eight-cell stage is highly stereotypical (see Figure 1.5). First, we addressed whether the fates of these cells are also committed at this stage. If these cells are committed at the eight-cell stage,

then ablation of that cell would result in a complete loss of that lineage. On the other hand, if at least some of the remaining cells are uncommitted, then they would be able to compensate for this loss and the resulting embryos will still develop the ablated lineage. In order to test this hypothesis, cells were photoablated at the eight-cell stage (Shankland, 1984). Embryos were observed, by microscopy, immediately following injection and for several days after photoablation to confirm that the targeted cell was ablated. When cells were ablated, cell division ceased and cellular debris was either incorporated into the yolk where it could be seen as a green fluorescent bolus under FITC illumination for days after, or the debris was shunted to the outside of the embryo where it remained as granular debris between the eggshell and embryo.

We find that photoablation of any one blastomere at the eight-cell stage can result in a fully formed and viable animal. Photoablated animals survive at varying frequency depending on the cell ablated. Micromere ablated embryos are able to survive to hatching more frequently than macromere injected animals. Macromere ablated embryos survived to hatching approximately 10%–20% of the time, while micromere ablated embryos survived greater than 80% of the time (data not shown). These results indicate that cells at the eight-cell stage are not irreversibly committed to a single lineage because they can compensate for the loss of other cells.

The observation that the majority of macromere-lineage ablated embryos do not survive to hatching suggests that although ablated embryos can initiate a compensatory response, there are other factors that play a role in

determining the viability of an ablated embryo to hatching. Difference in survivorship between macromere and micromere ablations may imply that the embryonic architecture of the ablated embryo is compromised by the large amount of debris generated by the ablated cell.

Blastomeres at the eight-cell stage are committed to an ectodermal or mesodermal fate

To determine which lineages are able to compensate for the ablation of specific blastomeres, we performed experiments to uncover patterns of compensation from the remaining lineages during development of mesoderm- and ectoderm-ablated embryos. At the third cleavage, the ml and mr micromeres derive from an asymmetric division in which their sibling macromeres become ectodermal precursors (El and Er, respectively) (Gerberding et al., 2002). Therefore, Price first sought to determine whether this relationship was retained such that E lineages compensate for the loss of sibling m lineages. To do this, she injected RNA encoding nuclear localized DsRed into one blastomere to act as a lineage tracer and injected FITC into another blastomere to act as a substrate for photo-oxidation. Photoablation caused death of the FITC injected cell while DsRed localization allowed her to trace the origin of any compensating cells.

She found that labeled El or Er lineages never gave rise to mesodermal derivatives when the corresponding mesoderm micromere was ablated (data not shown). Therefore, none of the E macromere lineages compensate for ablated m micromere lineages. When Hannibal or I ablated an E macromere

and labeled the adjacent m micromere, we never observed the labeled mesodermal lineage giving rise to ectodermal cells. These results suggest that the E and m blastomeres are already irreversibly committed to an ectodermal or mesodermal fate, respectively, at the eight-cell stage.

In this chapter, I investigate the regulation of the ectodermal lineages following ablation at the following stages: eight-cell stage, gastrulation, and germband elongation. I show that ablations at the eight-cell stage and gastrulation can result in a viable embryo, and that in these experiments, the remaining ectoderm lineages compensate for the ablated lineage in a lineage-restricted manner. My results show that the E blastomeres, El, Er and Ep, also form an equivalence group. In addition, I expand upon the previous observations of Price (2005) regarding mesoderm commitment. I confirmed that ablation of all three mesoderm-producing cells at the eight cell stage results in no compensation for the mesoderm. Then I ablated each of the mesodermal lineages at gastrulation and demonstrate that the remaining mesoderm lineages can still compensate for the ablated lineage. Taken together, our results demonstrate that the developmental potential of the blastomeres from the eight-cell embryo in *Parhyale* is greater than that predicted by the fate map and that there is a stereotypical pattern of regulation of germ layer fates following ablation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Parhyale hawaiensis cultures

Mating pairs and gravid females were collected from the Patel lab breeding cultures. Females were anesthetized in a clove oil solution for 10 minutes (10ul oil in 50ml filtered seawater) prior to the removal of embryos from the brood pouch using forceps. Embryos were grown in artificial seawater. Stages were determined according to Browne et al., (2005).

Injection, Photoablation and lineage tracking

Microinjections were performed on a Zeiss Axiovert 10 or S100 equipped with a 16x objective. A Narishige IM300 microinjector was used to deliver reagents through glass capillary needles with beveled tips (TW100F, World Precision Instruments). Targeted blastomeres were injected with 100 picoliters of 25-50 mg/ml of fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC) linked to dextran (250,000MW) (Sigma) and then ablated by photo-oxidation (Shankland, 1984). For ablations at the eight-cell stage, embryos were exposed to the fluorescein excitation wavelength ($\lambda = 490\text{nm}$) for twenty minutes under a Zeiss Stemi SV11 Apo dissecting scope. For ablations at gastrulation (S8) and germband stages (S10-14), embryos were similarly exposed except using a Zeiss Axiophot (Zeiss Plan-NeoFLUAR 10x/0.3 objective). Ablated cells ceased division and were either excluded from the developing embryo entirely, or broken down and reabsorbed by the gut.

To trace other lineages, targeted blastomeres were injected with approximately 100 picoliters of 10 to 50 mg/ml Tetramethylrhodamine isothiocyanate-Dextran (TRITC) (Sigma) or 100 picoliters of 0.7-1 µg/ml of the RNA encoding the nuclear localized red fluorescent protein, DsRed (Price and Patel, 2007). The Ambion SP6 mMessageMachine kit was used to synthesize the capped mRNA for injection. Embryos with injection trauma were discarded.

Immunohistochemistry

Embryos were fixed for 15-20 minutes at room temperature in one of two fixatives: 3.7% formaldehyde in 90% filtered seawater or in 3.7% formaldehyde in PEM (0.1M PIPES; 1mM MgSO₄; 2mM EGTA; pH 7.0). While in fixative, eggshells were removed with sharpened tungsten needles. Embryos were then washed in 1x PT (1x PBS, pH 7.4; 0.1% Triton X-100) several times and then either dehydrated through a methanol series and stored at -20° until further use or immediately processed through the procedure as described by Patel (1989). The polyclonal rabbit-anti-DsRed antibody (Clontech) was used at a final concentration of 1:500 to 1:1000. Primary antibodies were incubated overnight at 4°C. HRP conjugated goat-anti-rabbit secondary (Jackson ImmunoResearch) was used at 1:300 to 1:600. Secondary antibodies were incubated for 2 hours at room temperature or overnight at 4°C. Following washes in 1x PT, embryos were reacted in DAB + 0.8% NiCl and 20 µl of 0.3% H₂O₂ for 10 to 20 minutes. Following several 1x PT washes, embryos were

counterstained in 1 µg/ml DAPI in 1x PBS, first cleared in 50% glycerol and then 70% glycerol prior to mounting and photography.

Timelapse and Microscopy

Static images were captured on a Zeiss Axiophot microscope (Plan NEOFLUAR objectives: 5x, 0.15; 10x, 0.3; 20x, 0.5; 40x, 0.85; 100x, 1.3) using either the SPOT INSIGHT QE (model 4.2) or SPOT FLEX 64Mp shifting pixel (model 15.2) cameras (Diagnostic Instruments). Confocal stacks were obtained on a Leica DMRXE microscope with Leica TCS software (PL FLUORTAR: 10x, 0.3; 16x, 0.5; 40x, 1.0; PL APO: 63x, 1.32; 100x, 1.4). Images were assembled using either Adobe Photoshop CS2 v9.0™ or Volocity™ v3.7-4.1 softwares (Improvision).

RESULTS

Ablation of the ectoderm blastomeres, El, Er, or Ep at the eight-cell stage are compensated for by the remaining ectodermal lineages

Based on the pattern of mesoderm compensation initially described by Price (2005), I suspected that the ectoderm would also form an equivalency group, and set out to test this hypothesis first. The ectoderm in *Parhyale* is generated from three specific macromeres at the eight-cell stage: El, Er, and Ep (Figure 2.2). Each ectodermal macromere gives rise to a spatially restricted clone of cells in the left, right, and posterior regions of the embryo, respectively (Gerberding et al., 2002; Figure1.5).

To determine if the remaining ectodermal lineages compensate for the loss of an ectoderm blastomere, I ablated one E blastomere by injecting FITC-dextran and photoablating, as described above, and then injected a different E blastomere with the lineage tracer, nuclear localized DsRed, to follow the subsequent development of the remaining lineages. My experiments show that the progeny of the remaining ectodermal blastomeres can compensate for the ablation of any ectoderm blastomere at the eight-cell stage. Based on the lineage studies of Gerberding et al., (2002), cells of the ectoderm mix in a predictable pattern in the head and gnathal versus trunk regions suggesting that the pattern of compensation among these lineages might also be predictable. Indeed, this is what I observed.

Normally, the El blastomere gives rise to the majority of the ectoderm on the left side of the germband (Figure 2.2A, A'). Labeling of El and ablation of Er lineages at the eight-cell stage resulted in labeled cells in the right anterior half of the developing germband (n = 7) (Figure 2.2B, B'). The reciprocal experiment, ablating El and labeling Er, resulted in the right ectoderm lineage compensating for the loss of El in the left-hand anterior head segments (data not shown). When the Ep blastomere was ablated and El labeled, we found that the progeny of El occupied the entire left side of the germband, extending into the regions that would normally be comprised of Ep-lineage cells (n = 5) (Figure 2.2C, C'). The compensation by El progeny did not cross the midline, and therefore the posterior ectoderm in Ep-ablated embryos was composed of Er and El progeny on the right and left posterior sides,

respectively. Although in nonablated animals the Ep blastomere generates the posterior ectoderm and the majority of the midline cells (Figure 2.2D, D'), if the Er blastomere (Figure 2.2E, E') or the El blastomere (Figure 2.2F, F') is ablated at the eight-cell stage and Ep is labeled with nuclear localized DsRed, the Ep lineage extends to anterior regions normally occupied by the ablated lineage (n = 8).

To determine more precisely the axial level where compensation appeared restricted, I examined localization of the lineage tracer in fixed specimens using an antibody to DsRed at a later stage of development S19 when the germband is completely segmented and the appendages are becoming well defined and identifiable (Browne et al., 2005) (Figure 2.3). Interestingly, the ability of the El and Er lineages to compensate was limited to the region anterior to maxilla 2 (mx2) (Figure 2.3B, B'), while the extent of Ep compensation was restricted to the region posterior to maxilla 1 (mx1) (Figure 2.3D, D'). In the case of compensation for posterior ectoderm normally made by Ep, the strict adherence to the left/right boundary was maintained, so that El compensated for the left posterior ectoderm (Figure 2.3F, F') and Er compensated for the right posterior ectoderm (data not shown). The cells that make up the midline were composed to varying extents of both the left and right ectoderm lineages in these ablated embryos. These results were intriguing because in the amphipod *Orchestia*, the 16-cell lineage shows that the left and right ectoderms are subdivided into anterior and posterior regions by the first division of the ectoderm blastomeres, El and Er (i.e., transition

from 8 to 16 cells) (Wolff and Scholtz, 2002). In *Parhyale*, I performed lineage studies of the ectoderm blastomeres at the 16-cell stage. These studies revealed that there is a boundary between mx1 and mx2 that segregates the left and right ectoderm into anterior and posterior regions (Figure 2.3G- H'), similar to what is observed in *Orchestia*. In addition, cells from the two progeny blastomeres that result from division of Ep-l and Ep-r—are segregated on the left and right sides of the germband, respectively, with the midline cells arising from either Epl or Epr or both clones (Figure 2.3I, I'). These anterior–posterior and left–right boundaries correspond to the patterns of compensation among El, Er and Ep in ablated embryos. Taken together, these results show that the ectodermal blastomeres, El, Er and Ep, comprise an equivalence group, **E**, at the eight-cell stage. Therefore, in *Parhyale*, two equivalence groups are established at the eight-cell stage, which separates ectoderm and mesoderm cell fates.

Ablation of ectodermal and mesodermal lineages at gastrulation results in compensation within equivalence groups

An advantage of the photoablation technique is that it allows cells to be killed at different developmental stages. Therefore, I next examined the timing of compensation in greater detail by ablating the different ectoderm and mesoderm lineages during gastrulation (S8). Using this technique, I injected specific blastomere combinations at the eight-cell-stage with FITC-dextran or lineage tracer and then performed timed ablation experiments to determine the

degree to which the nonablated ectoderm lineages were able to compensate following ablation.

At gastrulation, each E clone (El, Er, or Ep) consists of approximately 27- 31 cells. By this stage, the ectoderm clones are organizing into a germ disc on the anterior ventral side, and are already spatially organized into left, right, and posterior regions. Ablation at gastrulation results in embryos that were developmentally delayed—particularly on the ablated side—resulting in the asymmetric development of the embryo. I observed the same pattern of compensation in gastrulation-stage ablated embryos as was seen in the eight-cell-stage ablated embryos (Figure 2.4). Ablation of either Er or El descendants are compensated for by the progeny of El or Er, respectively, in the anterior head region, while the progeny of Ep compensates for the loss of cells from the posterior head and trunk region (n = 8)(Figure 2.4A-D”). Ablated Ep progeny are compensated for by the remaining El and Er lineages (n = 4) (Figure 2.4E-F”). Approximately 29% of these embryos survive to hatching, demonstrating that these embryos, although noticeably developmental delayed, retain the ability to respond to the loss of the ablated cells. Although the majority of the gastrulation-ablated embryos do not survive to hatching, in most embryos that died, there was some attempt at compensation for the ablated lineage. My results further confirm that only ectodermal lineages can compensate for loss of ectoderm. Moreover, this compensation is spatially restricted to observe the midline boundary as well as a boundary between mx1 and mx2—similar to the ablations at the eight-cell stage.

I also ablated the mesodermal lineages derived from ml, mr, or Mav, at gastrulation. At this stage, the ml and mr lineages each consist of about six progeny cells. Following photoablation, these cells ceased division and turned into granular, fluorescent debris that was easily identifiable for a full 24 hours afterwards. By 48 hours postablation, the debris had disappeared, and was most likely absorbed by the yolk or degraded by vitellophages. In these ablated embryos, I observed compensation of mesoteloblast development by the progeny of Mav, but not by the remaining m micromere lineage—identical to the situation seen in ablations at the eight-cell stage (n = 10) (data not shown; see Figure 2.1). However, the gastrulation-stage ablated embryos had a significantly decreased survival rate (less than 10% survived to hatching) compared with the embryos ablated at the eight-cell stage. These animals typically reached S26 (180 hours post fertilization) before dying. They underwent germband elongation and appendage and heart formation normally, yet failed either to form or properly extend the bilateral digestive caecae (secretory organs that are formed from the extending midgut) and did not hatch properly. In fact, in all cases where midgut defects were observed, the embryos were unable to hatch from their confining membranes.

At gastrulation, the Mav lineage normally consists of approximately ten cells. Following ablation at gastrulation, the progeny of ml and mr were able to compensate for the ablated lineage—again identical to the situation seen for ablations at the eight-cell stage (n = 9)(see Figure 2.1). Gastrulation-stage ablation of Mav progeny resulted in a completely viable hatchling

approximately 50% of the time. Of the embryos that did not survive, all had midgut or digestive caecae defects similar to those seen in the embryos that had undergone gastrulation-stage ablations of ml and mr (data not shown). Therefore, the majority of these cells are not yet committed to either a segmental mesoderm or visceral mesoderm fate at this point of development. However, the marked decrease in survivorship and the specific midgut defects observed by ablation does suggest that some commitment and perhaps differentiation of the mesodermal lineages has begun by this stage.

Ablation of blastomere lineages at the germband stage S10/11 results in a lack of compensation and the loss of that lineage

Based on previous experiments by Price (2005), ml or mr lineage ablations performed just after formation of the mesoteloblasts, at the germband stage S10/11 (56-60hrs post fertilization), resulted in no compensation for the ablated lineage (Figure 2.1-2; Figure 2.5). The *Parhyale* ortholog of *myocyte enhancing factor 2* (*Ph-mef2*), a marker of differentiated mesoderm, was also completely absent on the ablated side (Figure 2.5C,C'), compared to a nonablated embryo (Figure 2.5D, D'), demonstrating the loss of body musculature. Although these animals were able to develop to S24 (155 hours post fertilization), they never hatched. These animals also fail to form digestive caecae on the ablated side of the embryo.

When I ablated the progeny of Mav at the time of mesoteloblast formation (Figure 2.5E,F), they were not compensated for by the progeny of ml and mr, resulting in a loss of the visceral mesoderm (n = 6). These embryos

often continued to develop to S21-23 (120-144 hours post fertilization). However, the midgut and digestive cecae clearly did not form in ablated embryos (Figure 2.5 G,H) compared to nonablated embryos (Figure 2.5I, J). Based on these observations, I confirm that compensation of ablated mesodermal lineages does not occur following ablation at germband stages. These results suggest that by the germband stage S10/11, cells have lost the capacity to compensate for the ablated cells.

Next, I tested whether the ectodermal lineages were able to compensate for ablation at the germband stage. Ablation of the ectoderm lineages derived from El or Er (Figure 2.6A,B) or Ep (Figure 2.6D,E) at the germband stage S10/11 resulted in a permanent loss of that tissue, suggesting that at this stage, the other ectoderm cells may not be able to compensate. These embryos typically die within three days post ablation. Occasionally, some embryos reach S21-23 (120-144 hours post fertilization) and form appendages but lack the segments and appendages from the ablated region (Figure 2.6C, F) compared to nonablated embryos (Figure 2.6G). The severity of the defects depends on the size of the clone at the time of ablation, which can vary greatly among embryos. Additionally, due to the dilution of FITC at the time of ablation and the great number of ectodermal cells at the germband stage, I cannot confirm that all of the photoablated cells actually died. Based on these findings, the ability of *Parhyale* to regulate ectodermal development appears to be lost at some point after gastrulation; although, it is unclear whether this loss is due to

a change in the state of cell commitment or some other mechanism such as distance from a signal.

Ablation of the mesoderm equivalence group (ml, mr, and Mav) at the eight-cell stage results in a loss of mesoderm

To determine that other lineages cannot compensate for the mesoderm, I ablated all three mesoderm blastomeres, Mav, ml, and mr, at the eight-cell stage. These embryos appeared to have a complete loss of mesodermal derivatives (n = 8) (Figure 2.7 A, B). In nonablated embryos, the mesoteloblasts and mesoblast could be easily identified lying dorsal to the ectoderm in a predictable pattern (Figure 2.7C-C”). In the triple-ablated embryos, the visceral mesoderm appeared completely absent and the mesoteloblasts and their progeny, the mesoblasts, were completely absent from the germband (Figure 2.7D-D”). These results suggest that none of the remaining blastomere derivatives can produce mesoderm. Interestingly, ablation of the three mesoderm-generating blastomeres did not interfere with the embryos ability to make a well-formed ectodermal germband. However, all of these embryos were severely developmentally delayed and died by S13/14 (70 hours post fertilization). This finding suggests that the initial organization of the ectodermal germdisc does not require input from the mesodermal lineages during gastrulation and germband elongation.

Ablation of the en blastomere results in compensation

Based on the fate map, the en blastomere gives rise to the endoderm (Gerberding et al., 2002). When I ablated the en blastomere, a completely viable embryo resulted suggesting compensation from other lineages. However, it has been a technical challenge to determine precisely which lineages may be compensating for these ablations. A few of the challenges of analyzing en ablations include the extensive spatial overlap of the mesodermal or ectodermal lineages with the endodermal lineages normally observed in nonablated embryos, the dilution of cell tracer by the critical developmental timepoint, and changes in cell behavior of the endodermal cells at germband stages. However, based on the experiments I did perform, I was able to draw some conclusions.

First, I tested whether the sister blastomere, Ep, could compensate for loss of the en blastomere. I never observed labeled cells from of the Ep lineage in the region of the embryo consistent with the location of the endodermal lineage suggesting that the posterior ectoderm does not compensate for the endoderm. I also tested the other ectodermal lineages, El and Er. However, to date, these results have been inconclusive. Next, the spatial proximity of the visceral mesoderm lineage (Mav) overlying the en lineage following gastrulation indicated that this lineage might be an obvious candidate for compensation. However, my ablations and cell labeling experiments were unable to answer this question because I was not able to distinguish endoderm from mesoderm based on lineage tracking alone. But I was able to determine

that ablation of the Mav and en blastomeres at the eight-cell stage can also result in a viable embryo (n=3). Taken together, the results suggest that either the left and right ectoderms can compensate for ablation of en, or more likely that the ml and mr lineages can compensate and that a mesendoderm equivalence group may exist at the eight-cell stage.

However, it is unclear whether endoderm is able to compensate for loss of mesoderm. Based on morphology, the triple mesoderm ablations appear to have a complete loss of mesoderm suggesting that the en lineage is not able to compensate for the mesodermal lineages. Although it is clear that the segmental mesoderm (mesoteloblasts and mesoblasts) and visceral mesoderm are absent and that the head morphology is affected, it is formally possible that some head mesoderm exists that may be derived from the en lineage. Further analyses will be required to more precisely determine the compensation of the en blastomere.

DISCUSSION

Ectoderm and mesoderm equivalence groups in *Parhyale* at the eight-cell stage

The findings presented in this dissertation represent one of the most detailed modern analyses examining the commitment of blastomere fates within the Crustacea. I show that the early development of the *Parhyale* embryo is highly regulative and that cell lineage can be separated from cell fate to a limited degree, despite the presence of a stereotypical cleavage pattern and an essentially invariant fate map.

Equivalence groups are groups of cells that will eventually contribute to different derivatives, but at an earlier point in development, all have the same developmental potential. Only after subsequent determination events do they reach their final state of differentiation (Kimble, 1981). Surprisingly, in *Parhyale* regulation of ablated lineages does not occur by “nearest neighbors” or by sister blastomeres of the ablated cells. Rather our labeling and ablation experiments show that ectodermal cells can only compensate for loss of other ectodermal lineages while mesodermal lineages can only compensate for loss of other mesodermal lineages and perhaps endoderm as well. This demonstrates that at the eight-cell stage in *Parhyale*, at least two equivalence groups are established: the ectoderm equivalence group (El, Er, and Ep, or **E**) and the mesoderm equivalence group (Mav, ml, and mr or **M**) (Figure 2.8). The progeny of the two other cells at the eight-cell stage, g and en, are also replaced following ablation. Ablation and regulation of the g blastomere are discussed in Chapter IV. Placement of the en blastomere into an equivalence group is difficult at present. Initial experiments suggest that en may be a member of the **M** equivalence group, however this hypothesis needs to be tested more rigorously.

Germ layer specification by autonomous or non-autonomous mechanisms

The highly asymmetric cell divisions and the establishment of these equivalence groups so early in development is striking and indicates that the earliest cleavages may be highly polarized. It is unclear what mechanisms are involved in this polarized cell division, for example, whether maternal

determinants are placed asymmetrically in the egg as in *Drosophila* (reviewed in Govind and Steward, 1991; Grunert and St Johnston, 1996; Saffman and Lasko, 1999) or if the sperm entry point is responsible for establishing this polarity as in *C.elegans* (reviewed in Labouesse and Mango, 1999; Lyczak et al., 2002). Most likely, it is a combination of mechanisms.

There is some evidence that maternally loaded factors may be important in *Parhyale*. For example, there are visible asymmetries at the one cell stage that are associated with later polarity. The polar bodies, as in other animals, are associated with the first cleavage plane and the establishment of the animal hemisphere and the ectoderm blastomeres. In addition, a subcellular structure or island of cytoplasm of unknown function, is found at the vegetal pole, where micromeres will develop (see Chapter III). Indeed, the cytoplasm of the g micromere of *Parhyale* appears more refringent than other cells, which has led to the suggestion that there is a germ-line determinant localized at these early stages (Extavour, 2005). It therefore seems likely there are additional localized maternal factors that play a role in specifying the mesoderm and ectoderm lineages.

Regulation and specification within germ layers

At the eight-cell stage at least two equivalence groups, **E** and **M**, will contribute to defined germ layers in stereotyped ways. Despite the obvious asymmetry in the cell division pattern between equivalence groups, especially in the M group, our experiments suggest that the blastomeres within each group all have the same developmental potential that diminishes as

development proceeds. However, there are spatial boundaries that clones do not appear to cross; in the ectoderm there is an anterior–posterior boundary at mx1–mx2 and a left–right boundary at the midline; in the mesoderm, the ml and mr lineages do not cross the midline. Furthermore, the cells that give rise to the initial mesoteloblasts are first formed at the level of mx1 and mx2 (Price and Patel, 2007). At this time it is unclear if or how these boundaries play a role in affecting the equipotency of blastomeres as development progresses.

It is not known if this further restriction of cell fate is achieved through asymmetric localization of cytoplasmic determinants or through induction, or both. A nice example of both mechanisms at work comes from ascidians. Macho-1, a cytoplasmic determinant, which is inherited by a specific blastomere lineage, is sufficient to specify muscle fates (Nishida and Sawada, 2001). However, the combination of an anterior–posterior asymmetric cell division and cell signaling from nearby endoderm cells modifies the fate of the responsive cells to a mesenchymal fate rather than the “default” muscle fate (Kobayashi et al., 2003).

From our timed ablations in *Parhyale*, we see intervals where mesoderm and ectoderm equivalence groups appear to lose equipotency. These intervals indicate key developmental times when cells likely become committed to certain fate within a germ layer. In *Parhyale*, ablation of a member of the mesoderm equivalence group or its progeny until gastrulation can result in the regulation for those lost cells and the re-establishment of a complete mesodermal complement. This suggests that progeny within the mesoderm

equivalence group are equipotent until just after gastrulation. However, it is interesting to note that in gastrulation-stage, mesoderm-ablated embryos that did not survive to hatching, but did continue to develop for days following ablation, the major developmental defect associated with death was the lack of digestive caecae formation, a structure derived from both mesoderm and endoderm. This was also the case for germband mr or ml ablations. This suggests that, after the onset of gastrulation, one of the first determination events within the mesoderm germ layer may be of ml/mr derived cells that contribute to digestive caecae formation; only embryos ablated prior to this determination event may be able to compensate and develop a normal digestive caecae. Alternatively, the difference in survivorship may not be a change in cell commitment, but rather attributed to other causes such as the failure of proper intercellular signaling or morphogenetic movements between the endoderm and mesoderm lineages that comprise the digestive caecae. Ablations within the mesoderm equivalence group after the beginning of germband elongation cannot be compensated for. Clearly, much of the irreversible commitment of mesoderm cells to their final fate has occurred by this time. In the case of the ectoderm, it is clear that the blastomeres at the eight-stage are committed to an ectodermal fate and that early ablation results in compensation. However, the inability of the ectoderm to compensate following ablation at the germband stages may be due to the further commitment or differentiation of cells to a particular segmental fate or to other factors that prohibit compensation such as

less cell division in the germband or distance of remaining cells from a signal is too great.

Gene expression patterns also indicate that differentiation of the lineages is not occurring until after gastrulation. The expression of mesoderm determination markers such as *twist* or *mef-2* do not appear until S13 (75 hours post fertilization) (Price and Patel, 2007) consistent with the idea that these cells are not differentiating until germband elongation. Furthermore, expression of a *Parhyale* ortholog of *orthodenticle*, *Photd1*, a head gap gene, at gastrulation (S8), demonstrates that differential gene expression is patterning the developing ectoderm field during the time frame we find critical for determination (Browne et al., 2006).

Presence and significance of the maxillary 2 boundary

The ectoderm of the amphipod germband can be subdivided into two main regions that have different properties: the nonordered cells of the head lobes anterior from the level of mx2 and the highly ordered ectodermal grid posterior to mx 1 that undergoes stereotypical divisions that generate the parasegments (Browne et al., 2005; Scholtz et al., 1994). Fate map studies of the 16-cell stage in two amphipods, *Orchestia* (Wolff and Scholtz, 2002) and in this study, *Parhyale*, show that the mx1–mx2 region as the anterior–posterior boundary for the progeny of the daughter cells of the macromeres that give rise to the right and left ectoderm. In addition, the Ep-lineage cells compensating for the loss of either El or Er do not cross this boundary. Clearly there is a difference in the compensation pattern observed between the ectodermal

lineages in the anterior versus posterior regions. There are two possible explanations for this difference. On the one hand, the rate of cell proliferation in the two regions may limit the spatial arrangement and therefore, the ability or extent that compensating cells can populate the area anterior to mx2 or posterior to mx1. Alternatively, the developmental potential of the anterior and posterior ectoderm daughter cells, at the 16-cell stage, may not be the same. Similar to the anterior–posterior specification system in *C. elegans* (Labouesse and Mango, 1999), induction or the asymmetric distribution of determinants into the daughter cells may be generating different fates at this stage. The fact that gastrulation-staged ablations are compensated for with the same spatially restricted boundaries as observed in the ablations at the eight-cell stage provides evidence for the hypothesis that the blastomeres may no longer be equipotent at the 16-cell stage. As more molecular markers become available, the significance of this boundary may become clear. Examination of the expression pattern of various homeodomain genes known to be involved in body plan patterning may shed light on the possible role this boundary may play in establishing territories or domains in *Parhyale*.

Germ layer specification in amphipods

Cell lineage invariance provides a very useful framework in which to examine evolutionary changes in cell fate specification mechanisms, especially between closely related species. For example, within molluscs, specification of the D quadrant, a conserved precursor cell of the mesodermal lineage, is either accomplished by induction from the micromeres, such as in *Patella vulgata*, or

by the asymmetric division and segregation of factors to one particular blastomere, such as in *Ilyanassa obsoleta* (Freeman and Lundelius, 1992; van den Biggelaar and Guerrier, 1979).

Holoblastic, or total, cleavage is a derived mode that convergently evolved in different crustacean species, although in amphipods, it is a pleiomorphic or ancestral trait (Schmitz, 1992). Conservation of the fate map of three amphipods, *Parhyale*, *Orchestia*, and *Jassa* (Gerberding et al., 2002; Wolff and Scholtz, 2002; and unpublished observations) suggests that mechanisms of blastomere specification may also be conserved. Alternatively, like molluscs, the final outcome may be the same, but the specification mechanism might be different.

How blastomere specification differs between amphipods can shed light on the evolution of germ layer specification. For example, the fate maps of *Parhyale* and *Orchestia* indicate a spatial and temporal difference in the establishment of the endoderm (Gerberding et al., 2002; Wolff and Scholtz, 2002). In *Orchestia*, the endoderm is derived from three different blastomeres from the eight-cell stage in contrast to the one blastomere in *Parhyale*. The three blastomeres in *Orchestia* correspond to the three mesoderm-producing blastomeres in *Parhyale*, therefore making these blastomeres mesendodermal rather than mesoderm or endoderm. In *Orchestia*, the specification of separate endoderm and mesoderm lineages occurs at or after the 16-cell stage, depending on the blastomere (Wolff and Scholtz, 2002). Clearly the mechanism of specification of these germ layers will be different in the two

species, although molecules might be conserved. Hence, although our ablations suggest that cell lineage and cell fate can be separated, this is not to say that it would be the case in other amphipods. Indeed, there may be amphipods that have tightly linked their cell lineages to cell fates. It will be interesting to see if ablation of early blastomeres can be similarly regulated in other amphipods. A greater sampling of amphipods will be required to understand the degree of conservation of blastomere specification in this group.

The link between cell lineage and cell fates has long been of fascination to biologists. In this Chapter, I have described classic embryological experiments testing the developmental potential of cells in an embryo with a stereotyped cell lineage and made some surprising discoveries regarding germ layer commitment. Now with the tools for molecular analyses at hand and the ease of maintaining *Parhyale* in the lab, we are beginning to address the molecular mechanisms underlying asymmetric cell division and cell fate specification in a non-insect arthropod system.

Figure 2.1 Summary of mesoderm ablation and compensation based on Price (2005)

1. Cartoon summarizing ablations of mesoderm-producing blastomeres at the eight-cell stage. Red fill depicts cell labeled with lineage tracer. Black fill with skull and crossbones depicts ablated cell. Unfilled cells outlined in gray represent the other lineages that are present, but not labeled, at those stages. Germband staged schematics are all ventral views. (A) Labeled ml blastomere normally gives rise to the segmental mesoderm on the left side of the germband. (B) Ablation of Mav is compensated for, on the left side, by the ml lineage. (C) Labeled Mav blastomere normally gives rise to visceral mesoderm (D) Ablation of ml is compensated for, on the left side, by the Mav lineage. **2.** Cartoon summarizing ablation of the mr lineage at germband stages (S10). Green fill depicts cell(s) injected with FITC-dextran at the eight-cell stage and the lineage at the time of ablation. In this case, mr has been injected at the eight-cell stage, then ablated at S10, and observed at S14-S18. Unfilled cells outlined in gray represent the other blastomere lineages present at that stage of development. Ablation of the mr lineage at germband results in a loss of the segmental mesoderm on the right side.

Figure 2.2 Regulation of ectoderm following ablation at the eight-cell stage

(A-F) Schematics of ablation at the eight-cell stage and the pattern of compensation observed at the germband stages S12 to S15. Ablated blastomeres are in black; DsRed labeled lineages are in red. (A'-F') Live fluorescent images of DsRed labeled nonablated and ablated embryos at germband stages S12-S15. Ventral views. (A') El labeled nonablated embryo. The left ectoderm lineage does not cross the midline (the larger cells are vitellophages that are also generated from the E blastomeres). (B') Er ablated, El labeled embryo showing the compensation of the right ectoderm in the anterior head region. (C') Ep ablated, El labeled embryo showing compensation of the left posterior ectoderm by the El lineage. (D') Ep labeled nonablated embryo. The Ep lineage gives rise to the posterior ectoderm and midline. (E') Er and (F') El ablated, Ep labeled embryos showing the posterior ectoderm compensation of the ablated lineage on the right and left sides of the posterior germband. Scale bars: 100µm.

Figure 2.3 DsRed expression of ectoderm ablated and nonablated embryos at S19 showing the mx1/2 and midline boundaries of compensation

Ventral views. Anterior is up. (A-F) Brightfield images of S19 embryos stained for DsRed. Embryos are either labeled or ablated and labeled at the eight-cell stage (combination indicated on bottom left corner of picture). (A'-I') False-color overlay of DsRed with DAPI. (A, A') Er lineage. The labeled cells are primarily restricted to the right side of the germband. Notice some mixing in the head region. (B, B') El ablated, Er labeled embryo. The Er lineage compensates for the loss of El in the head region, specifically in the segments anterior to mx1. The posterior most segments are missing due to dissection misfortune. (C, C') Ep lineage. Labeled cells are restricted to the posterior ectoderm and midline cells. (D, D') Er ablated, Ep labeled embryo. The posterior ectoderm compensates for the loss of El in the segments posterior to mx1. (E, E') El lineage. Labeled cells are restricted to the left side of the germband. (F, F') Ep ablated, El labeled embryo. The El lineage compensates for the loss of Ep in the posterior germband on the entire left side. (G, G') Er-anterior (Er-a) labeled embryo. Labeled cells extend to the mx1 segment. (H, H') El-posterior (El-p) labeled embryo. Labeled cells occupy the region posterior to mx1. (I, I') Ep-left (Ep-l) labeled embryo. Labeled cells are restricted to the left side of the midline. The 16-cell stage lineage of the ectoderm blastomeres reflects the boundaries observed at the mx1-mx2 segments and the midline in ablated embryos. Scale bar: 100 μ m.

Figure 2.4 Ablation and compensation of ectodermal lineages at gastrulation (S8)

(A, C, E) Fluorescent live images of S8 embryos at the time of ablation labeled with FITC dextran (green) and DsRed (red). (B, D, F) Brightfield images at S15-S18. (B', D', F') False-color overlay of brightfield images counterstained with DAPI. (A, B, B') El lineage ablated; Er lineage labeled with DsRed. (B, B')

Ablation at gastrulation can also result in compensation in a lineage-restricted manner, such that the lineage of Er compensates for the loss of the El lineage in the head region. Note the severe asymmetric development between the left and right sides. (C, D, D') Er lineage ablated; Ep lineage labeled with DsRed.

Ablation of the right ectoderm lineage at gastrulation is compensated for by the progeny of the posterior ectoderm. (E, F, F') Three embryos with Ep lineage ablated; Er lineage labeled with DsRed. Ablation of the posterior ectoderm at gastrulation is compensated for by the Er lineage. Note the discrepancy between the development of the head segments and the trunk region in these ablated embryos. Scale bars: 100 μ m.

Figure 2.5 Ablation of mesoteloblasts and visceral mesoderm at germband stages

Ventral views unless otherwise noted. (A, B) Live image and schematic of S10 embryo at time of ablation of mr lineage (green cells). The four mesoteloblasts which give rise to the segmental mesoderm have just formed. (C, D) *Ph-mef-2* *in situ* of mr ablated (C) and nonablated (D) embryos at S22. (C, D) Brightfield image with (C', D') corresponding false-color overlay with DAPI. Expression of the muscle determination marker, *Ph-mef2*, is absent only on the ablated side in (C). (E, F) Live image and schematic of S10 embryo at time of ablation of Mav lineage (green cells). (G, H) Lateral and dorsal view (anterior is left), respectively, of Mav lineage ablated embryo at S26. These embryos do not form a midgut or digestive caeca. (I, J) Lateral and dorsal views of a nonablated embryo with the bilateral caeca (*) perfectly formed. Scale bars: 100µm.

Figure 2.6 Ablation of the ectoderm lineages at germband (S11)

Ventral views. (A, D) Live fluorescent images of germband-staged embryos at the time of ablation (green=FITC). (B, E) Schematic of (A) and (D) respectively. (C, F) DAPI images of S21 ablated and (G) Nonablated embryo (C) Er-germband ablated embryo. Ablation of the right ectoderm at germband elongation results in a loss of anterior right segments and limbs. The severity of loss varies between embryos based on the size of the embryo's ectodermal clone. In this case, this embryo has lost A1-T1 on the right side. (F) Ep-germband ablated embryo. Ablation of the posterior ectoderm results in a complete loss of posterior segments on both right and left sides. (G) Nonablated embryo. Scale bars: 100µm.

Figure 2.7 Ablation of the three mesoderm blastomeres at the eight cell stage

(A) Schematic showing ablation of Mav, ml and mr (B) Live image of an eight-cell embryo injected and ablated with FITC dextran (green) in ml, mr, and Mav. (C–D'') DAPI images. Ventral views. (C–C'') Nonablated germband-staged embryo. (C) Ectoderm focal plane (C') the underlying visceral and segmental mesoderm focal plane (C'') confocal image of the area in C' (box) clearly showing the rows of mesoteloblasts (*) and mesoblasts. (D–D'') Triple mesoderm-ablated embryo at germband stage. (D) Ectoderm focal plane (D') the underlying plane where mesoderm is usually found and (D'') confocal image of area in D' (box) showing the loss of mesoteloblasts and mesoblasts in ablated embryos. Scale bars: 100 μm , except in (C'', D''): 20 μm .

Figure 2.8 Model of ectoderm and mesoderm compensation in *Parhyale hawaiiensis*

Two equivalence groups are established at the eight-cell stage. The mesoderm equivalence group, **M**, is comprised of ml, mr and Mav, while the ectoderm equivalence group, **E**, is made up of El, Er, and Ep. Following ablation at the eight-cell stage and at gastrulation, these cells can compensate for each other within the groups, but not between groups.

Chapter III: Germline development in *Parhyale hawaiiensis*

SUMMARY

The specification and development of the germline is one of the most crucial processes in any animal's life, as it ensures the propagation of the species. In *Parhyale hawaiiensis*, lineage studies and cell isolations performed at the eight-cell stage suggests that only one particular blastomere, g, gives rise to germ cells during embryogenesis, suggesting that germ cell fate is restricted by this stage. I determine how germ cell lineage and fate are coupled in this species by characterization of a known germline specific gene as well as a candidate gene for cell fate specification. In this chapter, I describe the expression of the *Parhyale* ortholog of *vasa*, a conserved germline marker, by *in situ* hybridization. *Parhyale vasa* localization in the germ cells suggests a conserved role in germline development. Furthermore, I show the novel localization of the *Parhyale* ortholog of β -*catenin*. Interestingly, at the earliest stages of development, I find maternally provided β -*catenin* is present in what may be analogous to the putative germ plasm that becomes restricted specifically to the g blastomere, and therefore the germline. β -*catenin* is known to be involved in setting up cell fates in a variety of cellular contexts. However, evidence for a direct role in germline development has not been previously observed.

INTRODUCTION

Regardless of whether an organism uses preformation (germline determinants) or epigenesis (induction) to specify their germline, several molecular cues appear to be conserved within metazoans, suggesting there may be elements of an evolutionarily conserved program for germline development. One such marker that is conserved in many metazoans is the DEAD-box RNA helicase *vasa*. Use of *vasa* as a marker for primordial germ cells (PGCs) has been well established in both vertebrates and invertebrates (Extavour and Akam, 2003; Mochizuki et al., 2001).

The DEAD-box family of RNA helicases

RNA helicases comprise a substantial portion of eukaryotic and prokaryotic genomes and are important in many aspects of RNA metabolism including splicing, translation initiation, RNA editing, RNA export and degradation (reviewed in Cordin et al., 2006; Linder, 2006; Linder and Lasko, 2006). The DEAD-box family of RNA helicases is defined by a conserved core of motifs first identified in the 1980s from sequence comparisons of elongation initiation factor-4A (eIF4A) orthologs (Linder and Slonimski, 1989). Using the motifs as a criterion, over 500 proteins have been found to possess conserved DEAD-box elements. At present, the DEAD-box family of proteins has nine conserved motifs that define this family (Figure 3.1). Structural analyses of these motifs reveal the likely interactions and functions of each motif in RNA metabolism. In general, they are classified into three main activities: ATPase, RNA helicase, or RNA binding activities. Although these motifs may be

classified to primarily one activity, many of them interact with other motifs within the protein, therefore may also be involved other activities. The Q-motif, last to be discovered, appears to be involved in regulating the activity of ATPases by sensing the state of bound nucleotides (Cordin et al., 2004; Tanner et al., 2003). Motifs I and II are also required for proper ATPase activity, as mutations in these domains abolish ATPase hydrolysis, while motif III is primarily required for proper helicase activity. Motifs Ia, Ib, IV, and V appear to be involved in RNA binding. Motif VI is at the junction between the DEAD-box and helicase domains and appears to be required for both ATPase and RNA binding activities.

vasa is a member of the DEAD-box family of proteins

vasa was originally discovered in the fruit fly *Drosophila melanogaster* by maternal effect screens looking for mutations that affected anterior–posterior and dorsal–ventral patterning (Schupbach and Wieschaus, 1986). Mutant *Drosophila* females give rise to embryos that have posterior patterning defects and that lack polar granules and pole cells. *vasa* orthologs comprise a subfamily of the DEAD-box proteins. They share the nine conserved motifs but then are further characterized by subfamily specific elements in the amino- and carboxy-terminal sequences (Linder and Lasko, 2006; Tanner and Linder, 2001). Based on sequence analyses, the PL10 subfamily of DEAD box genes is the closest related group to the *vasa* subfamily. Phylogenetic studies suggest that the *vasa* subfamily may have resulted from an ancient duplication of an ancestral *PL10* gene that occurred before sponges appeared (Mochizuki et al.,

2001). However, only the *vasa-related* genes are specifically expressed in the germline, while the expression of *PL10* is more widespread during development, suggesting its activity might not be as specific.

vasa is a widely conserved germline marker in metazoans

vasa mRNA and/or protein localization in the germ cells of many metazoans demonstrates the utility of it as a marker for the germline (reviewed in Extavour and Akam, 2003). Therefore, the temporal and spatial localization of *vasa* is a useful first indicator for when and from what source an embryo's germline is specified.

Among the ecdysozoans, both preformation and epigenesis are observed. In *Drosophila*, *vasa* protein localization is required for the proper posterior segregation of the polar granules into the pole cells. The protein is first localized in the posterior oocyte prior to fertilization and then solely in the pole cells that give rise to the germ cells at blastoderm stages (reviewed in Raz, 2000; Saffman and Lasko, 1999). However, maternal *vasa* mRNA is uniformly present in the early embryos, demonstrating that it is the protein localization that is critical for germ cell segregation. This is in sharp contrast with another insect, the red flour beetle *Tribolium castaneum*, in which *vasa* mRNA is uniformly localized at early cleavages but then becomes restricted to the posterior pole in the presumptive PGCs (Schroder, 2006). In both cases, the early segregation of *vasa* products, either at the RNA or protein level, is indicative of an early mode of germline specification. In the polyembryonic wasp, *Copidosoma floridanum*, which clonally produces many offspring from a

single egg, segregation of Vasa is associated with the determination of reproductive and soldier castes (Donnell et al., 2004). Unlike most insects, early cleavages are total in this wasp. Both *vasa* mRNA and protein are localized to one blastomere at the four-cell stage and then specifically in the reproductive larvae. Ablation of this blastomere results in castes that are primarily composed of soldiers suggesting that PGC fate is not only specified early in this embryo but also that evolution of the soldier caste may be due to the differential partitioning of Vasa (Donnell et al., 2004).

Not all insects segregate their germline early in development; they specify germ cells by induction at a later point. The grasshopper *Schistocerca gregaria* and the silkworm *Bombyx mori* do not appear to have germ plasm, and consistent with that observation, *vasa* mRNA is either not present or not localized in the early embryos (Chang et al., 2002; Nakao, 1999). In both *Schistocera* and *Bombyx*, *vasa* protein is not maternally provided, but is found at later stages in the presumptive PGCs (Chang et al., 2002; Nakao et al., 2006).

In the nematode *C. elegans*, there are four members of the *vasa-related* GLH (germline helicase) family of RNA helicases, GLH-1, 2, 3, and 4 (Gruidl et al., 1996). The mRNAs of these genes are not restricted to the P granules or the germline blastomeres; however, the proteins are specifically localized to the P granules indicating that, similar to *Drosophila*, it is the localization of protein that is crucial (Gruidl et al., 1996; Kuznicki et al., 2000). Interestingly, the localization of some of these proteins appears to be independent of the others

as shown by RNA interference (RNAi) suggesting a divergence in function. In addition, RNAi produces defective gonads and a loss of oocytes resulting in sterility in the offspring of injected adults (Gruidl et al., 1996; Kuznicki et al., 2000).

Among the lophotrochozoans, specification of the germline has not been as well studied at the molecular level, however it appears that epigenetic specification occurs more frequently in this group. *vasa* orthologs have been identified in several groups including the molluscan oyster *Crassostrea gigas* and the polychaete annelid *Platynereis dumerilii* (Fabioux et al., 2004; Rebscher et al., 2007). In *Crassostrea*, *Oy-vg* transcripts are already restricted to one side of an unfertilized oocyte and then to a specific blastomere, CD, at the two-cell stage, followed by successive asymmetric localization to the 4d micromere that gives rise to the mesendoderm of the adult, including the gonads and PGCs (Fabioux et al., 2004). However, it is unclear in these studies when the PGCs are then segregated from the other derivatives of 4d. The early cytoplasmic segregation of transcripts suggests that *vasa* might be a germline determinant in *Crassostrea*. It will be interesting to see if and how the protein localizes in this species. In *Platynereis*, *vasa* is localized uniformly in early cleaving embryos, but then becomes broadly restricted to the mesodermal posterior growth zone (MPGZ) and then to the gonads in juveniles (Rebscher et al., 2007). Initially, these results suggest that the germline is not specified early. However, when Rebscher et al. (2007) looked at Vasa localization, they found that it is localized in a perinuclear ring

in mature oocytes, and then in the yolk free cytoplasm of newly fertilized embryos. The yolk free cytoplasm gives rise primarily to the MPGZ, which subsequently gives rise to the founder PGCs. Therefore, in this annelid, it appears that both mRNA and protein are restricted to regions that give rise to the PGCs, but that neither are localized exclusively in the PGCs.

Unlike in lophotrochozoans, many *vasa* orthologs have been described in deuterostomes. For example, in the sea urchin *Strongylocentrotus purpuratus*, a detailed study examining the RNA localization of known germline specific determinants revealed that many of these mRNAs are uniformly localized during oogenesis and in early cleavages (Juliano et al., 2006). However, in the case of *vasa*, the mRNA does become restricted to the small micromeres at gastrula stages (Juliano et al., 2006). The small micromeres are thought to give rise to the PGCs, among other tissues, in sea urchins (Pehrson and Cohen, 1986). Therefore, it appears that specification of the germline occurs quite late in development, suggestive of inductive specification. Localization of *vasa* protein has not been examined yet; this information will be required to further address the mode of specification in sea urchins.

In the zebrafish *Danio rerio*, *vasa* mRNA is segregated in germ plasm material near the cleavage furrows as early as the two- and four-cell stages and then in the PGC clusters from gastrulation through the end of embryogenesis when they populate the developing gonad (Braat et al., 1999; Knaut et al., 2000; Yoon et al., 1997). Although uniformly distributed in early embryos,

Vasa is not part of the germ plasm at any point during development, but it does become specifically restricted to the PGCs later during gastrulation (Braat et al., 2000; Knaut et al., 2000). Therefore, unlike *Drosophila*, it is the subcellular localization of *vasa* mRNA that first indicates the presence of germ plasm and the beginning of germline segregation in zebrafish.

In mice and humans, the germline is not segregated early in development, but rather is induced by the surrounding somatic tissues during gastrulation (reviewed in Noce et al., 2001; Raz, 2000; Raz, 2002; Saffman and Lasko, 1999). Mammals do not have germ plasm and *vasa* gene products are not expressed until later in development as the PGCs are migrating to the genital ridges (Fujiwara et al., 1994; Noce et al., 2001; Raz, 2000). Indeed, specification of the PGCs in mouse embryos occurs before the appearance of Vasa (reviewed in Matsui and Okamura, 2005; Chapter I), suggesting the germline expression of Vasa is not required for PGC specification, but rather, may be important during the process of gametogenesis.

vasa localization in crustaceans

Experiments looking at the development of PGCs during embryogenesis in crustaceans are limited. *vasa* orthologs have been isolated in five crustacean species, thus far. Expression data is available for only a few of these including *Parhyale*. Vasa localization in *Parhyale* was first shown to be germline specific by Extavour (2005). Using a cross-reactive antibody, she found Vasa in the g blastomere at the eight-cell stage and subsequently in the PGCs that presumably derive from the g blastomere. Studies in the nonmalacostracan

water flea *Daphnia magna* also show an early localization of *vasa* protein, but not mRNA, to one particular blastomere at the eight-cell stage (Sagawa et al., 2005) and then in a restricted subset of cells thought to be the PGCs. These findings support the early specification mode of germline development in both *Parhyale* and *Daphnia*. In the Pacific white shrimp, *Litopenaeus vannamei*, *vasa* transcripts are localized to the oocytes and testes of the adult animals (Aflalo et al., 2007). However, it is unknown where *vasa* is localized during embryogenesis and whether this species has an early specification or late induction of germ cell development. It is unclear based on the evidence what the function of *vasa* may be in these crustaceans. The asymmetric localization of *vasa* protein in both *Parhyale* and *Daphnia* suggests that the protein may be the critical component.

Interestingly, in the organisms that specify their germline early in development, there does not appear to be a general pattern of localization that is observed, even in closely related groups, suggesting that the posttranscriptional and posttranslation modifications that control the exact location and function of *vasa* gene products are not conserved across phyla. Despite these differences, *vasa* has remained a consistent marker of the PGCs in many organisms.

In addition to the highly conserved germline marker, Vasa, I examined the role of *β -catenin*, another conserved gene involved in cell fate specification

and axis determination. In the following section, I review the protein structure and functions of β -catenin in other organisms before describing its expression in *Parhyale*.

Structure and evolution of β -catenin proteins

β -catenin is a bifunctional protein involved in both cell adhesion and as a transcriptional activator of the Wg/Wnt signaling pathway. The *Drosophila* ortholog, *armadillo* (*arm*), was first identified in the early 1980's by a genetic screen looking for segmentation defects (Nusslein-Volhard and Wieschaus, 1980). *arm* mutants are in the "segment polarity" class of mutant phenotypes in which every segment is affected. In this case, the posterior portion of each segment is missing, resulting in a mirror image duplication of the anterior denticle bands (Wieschaus and Riggleman, 1987). Vertebrate β -catenin was first identified in *Xenopus* cell lines for its interaction with the adhesion protein E-cadherin and based on sequence similarity was determined to be the vertebrate ortholog of Arm (McCrea et al., 1991).

β -catenin orthologs are generally composed of 12 Arm repeats that make up the majority of the protein. Each Arm repeat consists of approximately 42 amino acids that define three alpha-helices that form a superhelix (Huber et al., 1997). β -catenin orthologs also have highly conserved motifs in the amino- and carboxyl- terminal regions that function in both cell adhesion and signaling (Aberle et al., 1996; Cox et al., 1999; Hecht et al., 1999; Perego et al., 2000; Schneider et al., 2003; Yost et al., 1996). Within the vertebrate clade, a duplication of an ancestral gene gave rise to what is designated as the

vertebrate *β-catenin* and its related *plakoglobin* genes (Wang and Gu, 2000). The *plakoglobin* genes, while maintaining around 80% identity in the Arm repeat domain, have undergone extensive evolution at conserved residues and in the N and C termini, such that they do not appear to function in the same capacity as *β-catenin*, but rather have acquired a function in desmosomal adhesion in the epithelium (Sacco et al., 1995; Schneider et al., 2003). Interestingly, *C. elegans* has also experienced divergence of its three *β-catenin* genes, *Hmp2*, *Bar1*, and *Wrm1* (Schneider et al., 2003). The amino acid sequence conservation among the *C. elegans* genes, as well as among the *C. elegans* genes and other *β-catenin* orthologs, is only 15% to 30% in the central Arm repeat region (Schneider et al., 2003). Functionally, the *C. elegans* genes have also diverged. *Hmp2* primarily functions in cell adhesion, while *Wrm1* and *Bar1* are involved in cell signaling (Eisenmann et al., 1998; Korswagen et al., 2000; Rocheleau et al., 1997; Thorpe et al., 1997). Zebrafish also have duplicated *β-catenin* genes (Bellipanni et al., 2006). These two paralogs have both redundant and divergent functions during development (Bellipanni et al., 2006; Varga et al., 2007). The zebrafish *β-catenin* proteins are most divergent in the C-terminal transactivation domain suggesting that changes in this region may reflect the functional divergence observed during formation of the organizer, a tissue region and signaling center that induces differential fates within the three germ layers. Gene duplication results in the modification of the dual functions of adhesion and signaling to new roles in different tissues, such as with the *plakoglobins* or zebrafish *β-catenins* or subfunctionalization,

as in *C. elegans*. However, in most organisms, β -catenin is encoded by a single gene, therefore, we expected to find only one copy in *Parhyale*.

Role of β -catenin in cell adhesion

Cell adhesion is critical for tissue integrity, polarization of epithelium, epithelial to mesenchymal transitions (EMT) and morphogenetic movements (reviewed in Nelson and Nusse, 2004). β -catenin serves as the link between E-cadherin, α -catenin and the actin cytoskeleton in the adherens junctions of both invertebrates and vertebrates (Gumbiner, 2000; Jamora and Fuchs, 2002; Kemler, 1993). Coordination of this interaction appears to be regulated, in part, through phosphorylation of key residues (Lilien et al., 2002). This association is highly dynamic and changes in expression of β -catenin at the junctions correspond to major morphogenetic events in development of many organisms (Fagotto and Gumbiner, 1994; Miller and McClay, 1997; Riggleman et al., 1990). Analyses of different *Drosophila arm* mutant alleles reveal that Arm is required for cell adhesion during gastrulation and oogenesis (Cox et al., 1996; Peifer, 1993; Wieschaus and Noell, 1986). In mice, β -catenin loss-of-function mutants cease development at gastrulation due to a loss of cell adhesion within the inner cell mass (Haegel et al., 1995). In addition to its role in cell adhesion, β -catenin is also a key mediator of the Wnt signaling pathway.

Role of β -catenin in the Wingless (wg)/Wnt signaling pathway

In simplified terms, β -catenin acts to transduce the Wnt ligand through the Frizzled receptors, then entering the nucleus where it binds to several

proteins, including the TCF/Lef family of DNA binding proteins to activate transcription of Wnt target genes (reviewed in Wodarz and Nusse, 1998). The cell signaling function of β -catenin has been implicated in cell fate specification and axis formation in many organisms.

In some ecdysozoans, such as crustaceans and insects, Wnt signaling is involved in patterning several tissues including the ectoderm during segmentation, limb outgrowth and branching, and neurogenesis (Duman-Scheel et al., 2002; Giorgianni and Patel, 2004; Miyawaki et al., 2004; Nagy and Carroll, 1994; Nulsen and Nagy, 1999; Wieschaus and Riggelman, 1987). However, Wnt signaling is not involved in the early patterning events that initially set up the axes and germ layers in *Drosophila* (Wieschaus and Noell, 1986). The role of Wnts during early development in other arthropods has either not been examined, or, it has been shown not to be involved in axis determination or germ layer formation.

In another ecdysozoan, *C. elegans*, endoderm specification is mediated by Wrm-1, a β -catenin homolog, although in a noncanonical manner (Rocheleau et al., 1999; Thorpe et al., 1997). In *C. elegans*, the endoderm is derived entirely from the E blastomere following division of the EMS blastomere (Sulston et al., 1983). At the four-cell stage, Wnt signals act to polarize the EMS blastomere and control the fate of the E blastomere by translocating Wrm-1 to the nucleus where it indirectly downregulates the activity of Pop-1, the TCF/LEF ortholog. Mutations in *wrm-1* result in a loss of endoderm and an excess of muscle due to the misspecification of “E”

(Rocheleau et al., 1997). Among ecdysozoans, there is not a conserved role for *β-catenin* that suggests what the ancestral function may have been.

The role of *β-catenin* has been best studied in deuterostomes, such as ascidians, sea urchins and vertebrates. In ascidians, although the animal-vegetal axis is already established in the unfertilized egg, nuclear localization of *β-catenin* is required in the vegetal most blastomeres during early cleavage stage for proper endoderm differentiation. Overexpression of *β-catenin* results in an increase of endoderm markers in those lineages not fated to become endoderm, while downregulation of *β-catenin* disrupted normal endoderm differentiation (Imai et al., 2000).

Likewise in sea urchins, *β-catenin* also patterns the animal-vegetal axis of the early embryo. However, in this case, *β-catenin* is required for the vegetal micromeres to differentiate into skeletal mesenchyme, a mesodermal derivative. In the absence of *β-catenin*, these micromere cells become ectoderm instead; other cell fates, such as endoderm, are also disrupted due to lack of proper inductive signaling by the micromeres (Logan et al., 1999; Wikramanayake et al., 1998).

In *Xenopus* and zebrafish, nuclear localization of *β-catenin* on the presumptive dorsal-anterior side is necessary for proper dorsal–ventral axis formation (Rowning et al., 1997; Schneider et al., 1996). Ectopic expression of *β-catenin* on the presumptive ventral side will induce a secondary axis, while downregulation will result in a ventralized embryo (Kimelman and Schier, 2002; Larabell et al., 1997; Schneider et al., 1996).

Interestingly, in the cnidarian *Nematostella vectensis*, a basal metazoan, β -catenin accumulates differentially at one embryonic pole as well. This pole gives rise to the endodermal germ layer. In this organism, axial polarity along the oral-aboral axis, as well as germ layer formation, may be regulated by the Wnt signaling cascade (Wikramanayake et al., 2003), suggesting the role of β -catenin in axis formation and germ layer specification may be evolutionarily conserved.

In several of these examples, β -catenin functions to specify mesendoderm cell fates in the early embryo suggesting that it may play a conserved role in specification of these specific germ layers. Because of the observed early cell fate restriction in germ layers in *Parhyale*, β -catenin is an ideal candidate gene to examine for its likely role in cell adhesion and possibly in axis or cell fate specification.

In this chapter, I report the isolation and characterization of the *Parhyale* ortholog of *Vasa*. *Parhyale vasa* is localized in all cells during early cleavages, but eventually becomes restricted to the PGCs by the end of gastrulation. In addition, I characterized the maternal localization of the *Parhyale* ortholog of β -catenin. I found that *Parhyale* β -catenin is localized asymmetrically in the early one-cell embryo, becoming restricted to the g blastomere and its progeny, suggesting a role in germline development. Finally, I discuss mechanisms for early germline specification in *Parhyale hawaiiensis*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Cloning of *Parhyale vasa* and β -catenin

A partial clone for *vasa*, AFHB31414, was first obtained from an EST sequencing project (Joint Genome Institute). 5' RACE (Generacer, Invitrogen) was then performed to obtain the complete coding sequence.

Degenerate primers for β -catenin were designed in the conserved central Arm repeat domain and used in a modified RACE protocol using the degenerate primers with the 5 or 3' RACE kit specific primers. Reverse degenerate primers corresponding to the following amino acids were used to amplify a 5' fragment: AGGLQKM and AGGMQAI. Total RNA was isolated from S1-S21 *Parhyale* embryos using Trizol Reagent (Gibco). First strand cDNA synthesis was carried out on the RNA using the Superscript™ III First-Strand kit (Invitrogen) per manufacturers instructions. 5' RACE (Generacer) and 3' RACE (Frohman, 1993) were then performed to obtain the complete cDNA sequence. Samples were sequenced and assembled into Sequencher or MacVector for further analysis.

Phylogenetic analysis

Amino acid sequences of several subfamilies of RNA helicases as well as Armadillo for different organisms were obtained from the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI). Sequence for *Daphnia pulex* β -catenin was generously provided by Francis Poulin, a postdoc in the lab. For the analysis of the RNA helicases, only the DEAD and helicase domains were used in

phylogenetic analysis. For the analysis of β -catenin, the entire central domain containing the Arm repeats was used for generating alignments. Sequences were aligned using CLUSTAL X version 1.62b (Thompson et al., 1997) followed by refinement by eye. Ambiguous alignments and gaps were excluded from the analysis. All the sequences were subjected to maximum parsimony (MP), minimum evolution (ME) and bayesian methods of phylogenetic reconstruction. MP was performed in PAUP* 4.0b10 (Swofford, 2002) using heuristic searches (MulTrees option in effect) with 10 random stepwise additions of taxa. ME analyses (Rzhetsky and Nei, 1992) were carried out in PAUP* using mean character distances. Robustness of the resulting MP and ME trees was evaluated with non-parametric bootstrap proportions (BPs) (Felsenstein, 1985) as implemented in PAUP* with 1,000 pseudoreplicates. BI analyses were performed in MrBayes 3.12 (Huelsenbeck and Ronquist, 2001) by simulating a Metropolis-coupled Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMCMC) with four simultaneous chains, each of 10^6 generations (sampled every 100 generations) under the mtREV model. Trees sampled before the cold chain reached stationarity (as judged by plots of ML scores) were discarded as “burn-in”. Robustness of the resulting BI tree was evaluated using Bayesian posterior probabilities (BPPs).

In situ hybridization

Digoxygenin (DIG) or Fluorescein (FL) labeled antisense and sense riboprobes for *vasa* and *β -catenin* were synthesized using T7 and T3 polymerases (Roche) and then diluted and stored in hybridization buffer.

Probes were then used at a final concentration of 0.5ng/ml to 3 ng/ml. For *vasa*, a 543 bp EcoO109I fragment from the 3'UTR was used as a probe. For *β-catenin*, multiple probes were used spanning the entire transcript. All *β-catenin* probes gave the same patterns.

Embryos were fixed in one of two methods depending on stage:

1. Embryos younger than 48 hours were fixed overnight at 4°C in 3.7% formaldehyde in 90% sterile artificial seawater. These embryos only have one membrane that expands following overnight fixation. The next morning, I rinsed the embryos in 1x PTw (1x PBS and 0.1% Tween-20) for 30 minutes followed by hand dissection of the outer membrane with tungsten wire needles. Embryos were then dehydrated through a methanol series of 30%, 50%, 70%, to 100% methanol, followed by three 100% methanol washes before storage at -20 °C.
2. Embryos older than 48 hours were dissected while in fix, then fixed at room temperature in 3.7% formaldehyde in 90% artificial seawater for 1 hour to overnight at 4°C. Embryos were then washed in 1x Ptw for 30 minutes followed by dehydration through the methanol series and storage at -20 °C.

Embryos were rehydrated through a methanol series into PTw. Following four PTw washes, embryos were post fixed in 3.7% formaldehyde in PTw for 30 minutes, then washed in PTw 4 times for 5 minutes each. To permeabilize the tissue, embryos were incubated in detergent solution (1% SDS; 0.5% Tween-20;

50mM Tris-HCL, pH 7.5; 1mM EDTA, pH 8.0; 150 M NaCl) for 30 minutes followed by 6 washes in PTw for 5 minutes each, and then gradually transitioned into hybridization solution (50% formamide; 5x SSC pH 4.5; 50 µg/ml heparin; 0.25% Tween-20; 1% SDS; 100 µg/ml sonicated salmon sperm DNA; 25µg/ml tRNA). Embryos were prehybridized in hybridization solution for 2-3 hours followed by 17 to 24 hours of incubation with probe. The following day, embryos were washed 6-7 times in hybridization solution for a total of 3 hours, followed by a gradual transition into TBST. Following an hour of TBST washes, embryos were blocked for one hour in TBST with BSA (0.01g/50ml), then incubated in 1:3000 anti-dioxygenin or 1:4000 anti-fluorescein antibody (Roche) overnight at 4°C. Embryos were washed several times in TBST for a total of 3 hours, followed by 3 washes in alkaline phosphatase reaction buffer (5mM MgCl₂; 100mM NaCl; 100mM Tris-HCL pH 9.5; 0.1% Tween-20) or fast red reaction buffer (5mM MgCl₂; 100mM NaCl; 100mM Tris-HCL pH 8.2; 0.1% Tween-20) and then reacted using NBT/BCIP (Promega) or Fast Red (Sigma). For double *in situs*, embryos were rinsed in TBST after the first reaction, followed by a 10 minute rinse in glycine buffer pH 2 to strip away the first antibody, then washed and blocked in TBST prior to adding the second antibody. Embryos were counterstained in 1 µg/ml DAPI in 50% glycerol, then mounted and/or stored in 70% glycerol.

Microscopy

Images were captured and assembled as described in Chapter II.

RESULTS

Cloning and phylogenetic analysis of *Parhyale vasa*

In order to examine the mRNA localization of *vasa*, I obtained a partial EST clone from a sequencing project being conducted by the Joint Genome Institute (DOE, Walnut Creek). Clone AFHB31414 contained 1702 bp of the *vasa* transcript, but was missing the N-terminal coding sequence and the 5' untranslated region. Therefore, I designed 5' RACE primers to obtain the rest of the transcript. Using this method, I obtained the complete coding sequencing and an additional 17 bp upstream of the start ATG. The open reading frame is 2124 bp in length and the protein is 708 amino acids.

Sequence analysis of the amino acids showed that all nine motifs found in DEAD-box proteins are present in *Parhyale vasa* (Figure 3.1). Of the nine motifs, seven are 100% identical with the consensus sequence for the DEAD box family of proteins. The remaining two motifs, V and Q, are 78% and 89% percent identical, respectively, to the consensus sequence. Taken together, there are only a total of three amino acid differences from the consensus sequence. Only one of the differences was at a “wobble” position (a site where multiple amino acids form the consensus). The other two amino acids that differed from consensus are both in motif V and not in “wobble” positions but rather at sites where the consensus is assigned to a particular amino acid. However, mutation analysis of motif V in the yeast gene, Prp28, shows that the critical amino acids are the arginine (A) and the last aspartate (D) (Chang et al., 1997). Neither of these important residues differs in the *Parhyale vasa* motif

V. The glutamine residue (Q) in the Q-motif is the most conserved amino acid present in 99% of sequences while the charged group at the fourth position, where *Parhyale vasa* differs from consensus, is only 67% conserved in sequences (Cordin et al., 2006). Therefore, based on these findings, it seems likely that the changes in *Parhyale vasa* would not affect the proposed function of motifs Q or V in ATPase hydrolysis or RNA binding, respectively.

Multiple alignments of Vasa showed the level of conservation at the DEAD box and helicase domains and, in particular, to the nine conserved motifs (Figure 3.2 A, B). The DEAD domain in *Parhyale* is 53% identical to the DEAD box in *Daphnia magna*, and 55% identical to the *Drosophila melanogaster* domain, while the helicase domains are 60% and 56% identical to *Daphnia* and *Drosophila*, respectively (Figure 3.3). These values are within the range of what is observed for interspecies comparisons across the metazoans. These alignments also showed that *Parhyale* Vasa contains three RGG motifs and six zinc-finger (CCHC) motifs at the N terminus. Variable numbers of RGG have been previously identified in other arthropods and chordates (Noce et al., 2001; Raz, 2000; Sagawa et al., 2005). Zinc-finger motifs in Vasa are also found in chordates and the branchipod crustaceans, but appear to have been lost in the hexapod clade (Sagawa et al., 2005). Both motifs are thought to be involved in RNA binding. However, it is unclear how the difference in number or type of motif influences the function of the protein.

The amino-acid sequences of several subfamilies of RNA helicases from 36 taxa were combined into a single data set that produced an alignment of 321

positions. Of these, 50 were invariant, and 254 were parsimony-informative. The reconstructed Bayesian 50% majority rule consensus tree (-lnL= 68443.87) is shown in Figure 3.4. Maximum parsimony (2362 steps; CI=0.544) and maximum likelihood (score=5.65792) arrived at a congruent topology (not shown). Phylogenetic analyses supported the finding that *Parhyale Vasa* is indeed a Vasa ortholog (Figure 3.4). According to the recovered trees, *Parhyale vasa* unequivocally clustered within the Vasa subfamily and more specifically within the Ecdyzoa clade with the other arthropods (BPP=1; Figure 3.4). However, the relationship between many of the Vasa orthologs could not be resolved with confidence. The PL10 subfamily is more closely related to the Vasa subfamily than to the p68 and EIF4A subfamilies (BPP=1; Figure 3.4), which is consistent with other reports.

Parhyale vasa mRNA is localized to the PGCs during embryogenesis

Based on RT-PCR, *vasa* transcripts are present as early as the one-cell stage and continue to be present throughout embryogenesis (data not shown). This result shows that *vasa* is maternally provided at the earliest stages of development. Using a riboprobe designed against the 3' UTR of *vasa*, I determined the spatial localization of *vasa* transcripts during *Parhyale* embryogenesis (Figure 3.5). *vasa* appeared to be present in all the blastomeres during early cleavages (Figure 3.5A, A'); however, it was only observed in the yolk-free cytoplasm of each cell. *vasa* was then observed in a subset of cells by stage 6 (S6) (12 hrs of development) (Figure 3.5B, B'). Within this subset, there were approximately four intensely stained cells and a variable number of

weakly stained cells. One possible explanation for this pattern is that the strong cells are the presumptive PGCs and the weaker cells are the somatic lineages where the maternally provided transcripts are being degraded. Subsequent expression of *vasa* was restricted to the PGCs and not found in somatic cells after gastrulation is complete (Figure 3.5C, C'). Beginning at germband stages, the expression of *vasa* was observed in a single cluster of cells at the presumptive mandibular segment. This location corresponds to where the g lineage cells have migrated to by this stage (Figure 3.5D, D') (Gerberding et al., 2002). *vasa* mRNA continued to be expressed in the PGCs as the single cluster split into two bilateral clusters on either side of the presumptive gnathal segments (Figure 3.5E, E', F, F'). *In situ* hybridization of late stages (S22-S26) was not performed due to cuticle production and hardening.

To confirm that it was the g lineage that had the highest level of *vasa* transcripts at S6, I first injected the g blastomere with RNA encoding the DsRed protein, then following fixation around S6, I performed a double *in situ* hybridization with *vasa*-DIG and *DsRed*-FL probes (Figure 3.6). The cells with the highest levels of *vasa* mRNA also contained the *DsRed* mRNA (Figure 3.6A). I also injected the mesodermal lineages, ml/mr and Mav. Although the *vasa* signal was weak, it was clear that the Mav lineage was the predominant source of weakly expressing cells closest to the strong cells as would be predicted based on the migration pattern of these two cell populations at gastrulation (Figure 3.6B). In this experiment, I did not observe any weak

vasa-positive cells that were not derived from the Mav lineage suggesting that this lineage may be the exclusive source of the weak *vasa*-positive cells.

However, when I labeled ml or mr, the *DsRed* signal was so strong compared to *vasa* that I could not discern whether these mesoderm lineages also had *vasa* transcript (data not shown). Therefore, while these experiments do not exclude the possibility that the other lineages also contained some transcript as well, it does confirm that the progeny of g has the highest levels of *vasa* transcript at this stage.

vasa is present in the immature oocytes

Parhyale females have a pair of ovaries located on the dorsal side of the body adjacent to the digestive caecae. Oogenesis proceeds from the midline laterally with the progression of immature oocytes to mature oocytes that have undergone vitellogenesis, the process of yolk deposition into the oocytes (Schmitz, 1992; Zerbib, 1980). Ovaries isolated from adult females have *vasa* in the immature oocytes (Figure 3.7A, B). Because of the maternal contribution of *vasa* to the early embryo, the mature oocytes likely have transcript as well, but following vitellogenesis, transcripts are not detectable by current *in situ* hybridization methods. As a control for nonspecific binding, probes to the HOX gene *Ultrabithorax (Ubx)* and the forkhead gene (*FoxB*) were also used on oocytes. No expression was detected with either of these probes, indicating that the localization of *vasa* was specific (data not shown).

Parhyale β -catenin

To investigate the role of β -catenin during *Parhyale* development, I successfully cloned the *Parhyale* ortholog of β -catenin (Figure 3.8) using degenerate PCR and 5' and 3' RACE. I did not obtain any other clones from my degenerate reactions, suggesting that there is only one β -catenin gene in *Parhyale*. *Parhyale* β -catenin contains all 12 Arm repeats as well as conserved motifs in the N and C termini (Figure 3.8; 3.9). The central Arm repeat domain showed the greatest level of conservation sharing 85% identity with both *Drosophila melanogaster* and *Daphnia pulex* compared to the more divergent N and C termini where they are approximately 60% or 40% identical, respectively. However, *Parhyale* β -catenin does contain the other conserved domains found in the N and C termini that are likely important for its function.

The amino acid sequences of β -catenin orthologs from 23 taxa were combined into a single data set that produced an alignment of 601 positions. Of these, 243 were invariant, and 284 were parsimony-informative. The reconstructed Bayesian 50% majority rule consensus tree (-lnL= 7634.96) is shown in figure 3.10. Phylogenetic analyses revealed that *Parhyale* β -catenin does form a monophyletic group with other arthropod β -catenin orthologs (BPP=1; Figure 3.10). However, according to the recovered trees, crustacean β -catenin sequences do not form a monophyletic group and the phylogenetic position of *Parhyale* β -catenin among arthropods cannot be resolved. The lophotrochozoans formed a monophyletic group (BPP=1; Figure 3.10), and were recovered as the sister group of deuterostomes (BPP=0.99; Figure 3.10) in

the Bayesian analysis; thus, this gene tree not mirror the most current metazoan phylogenies.

Parhyale β -catenin is localized to the prospective germ plasm

I performed *in situ* hybridization for β -catenin mRNA and discovered a novel localization pattern during embryogenesis at both the earliest stages of development as well as during segmentation. I discuss the expression during segmentation in Appendix B and only discuss the early localization of β -catenin herein.

Initial experiments showed that, at the one-cell stage, β -catenin transcripts were asymmetrically and subcellularly located near the surface of the cell roughly in the middle of the long axis of the embryo (Figure 3.11-1A). After the embryo divided to the two-cell stage, the localization of β -catenin was asymmetrically located deep within one of the two cells (Figure 3.11-1B). At the four and eight cell stages, the subcellular β -catenin continued to be asymmetrically segregated to only one of the blastomeres following division. At the eight-cell stage, β -catenin was clearly localized to one of the micromeres (Figure 3.11-1C, C'). After the eight-cell stage, β -catenin became symmetrically segregated to the daughter cells of the following two divisions, resulting in a total of four β -catenin positive cells (Figure 3.11-1D, D'). However, at some point between the 128-cell stage and the start of gastrulation, β -catenin transcripts were no longer detected until germband elongation.

This pattern of localization was very intriguing, not only because of the surprising subcellular localization of the transcript, but also because of the

asymmetric segregation of the mRNA. To determine which blastomere contained *β-catenin*, I injected *DsRed* mRNA as a lineage tracer into different blastomeres at the four- and eight-cell stages, and then performed double *in situ* hybridization. I found that *β-catenin* was located in the Mavg blastomere at the four-cell stage and the g blastomere at the eight-cell stage (Figure 3.11-2A, B). Therefore, *β-catenin* is asymmetrically segregated to the prospective germline at the earliest divisions. These observations suggested that *β-catenin* might be segregating in what may be analogous to the germ plasm found in other organisms.

The only evidence of a putative specialized cytoplasm is seen at the one-cell stage. A slightly refringent structure that resembles a spot at the cortex of the embryo can be seen in live embryos (Figure 3.12B). Following division to the two-cell stage, this region was no longer visible in live embryos. This observation raised the question of whether this region was also where *β-catenin* was localized at the one cell stage. To test this idea, I first fixed and stained one-cell embryos with this region clearly visible. In all cases, *β-catenin* was also localized to the surface (n = 21) (data not shown). Next, I fixed one-cell embryos in which the spot could be identified after fixation, cut them roughly in half, and then separated them according to presence or lack of this spot. The pieces that did not have the spot, also did not have *β-catenin* (n = 3) (Figure 3.12C), while the pieces that had the spot were all positive for *β-catenin* (Figure 3.12D). Therefore, the localization of *β-catenin* correlates with the location of the morphological spot.

While doing these experiments, it was clear that the spot was not observed in all one-cell embryos that were collected at a given time (Figure 3.12A). This result suggested that this morphological structure was not present throughout the one-cell stage. The one-cell stage lasts approximately four hours. By observing a newly laid brood for the length of the first cell cycle, I determined that the spot was not visible in an early one-cell embryo, but was only present at approximately two hours post fertilization. My initial thought was that the structure was not visible in the live embryo because it was located deep in the yolk. To see if the localization of β -catenin differed in an early versus late one cell embryo, I isolated a single brood of embryos within 15 minutes of fertilization and then immediately fixed two to three embryos. I then fixed two to three embryos every 30 minutes until the embryos had a visible spot and performed *in situ* hybridization on the different batches. At the earliest time points, I did not observe a deep dot of β -catenin as I initially thought I would, but rather a network of loosely organized “strands” (Figure 3.13A, B). In 11 embryos from a single brood, nine had this localization pattern, while the two embryos from the last fixation condition had the more tightly associated localization pattern (Figure 3.13C, D). Therefore, it seemed that β -catenin transcripts were loosely localized to the cortex for two hours and then in the span of 30 minutes, it coalesced into a tightly associated dot that remained until gastrulation, when it disappeared altogether.

Parhyale β -catenin is localized to the immature oocytes

In the ovary, β -catenin transcripts were found in immature oocytes that had not undergone vitellogenesis, similar to the results observed for *vasa* (Figure 3.14). Interestingly, the mRNA appeared to be located throughout the cytoplasm of the oocyte and not in any subcellular pattern. A dramatic rearrangement in the localization of β -catenin transcripts likely occurs between the end of oogenesis and fertilization. Because *Parhyale* does not have nurse cells, like in *Drosophila*, all the reorganization of transcripts and proteins must be done within the oocyte itself. This process likely involves cytoplasmic and cytoskeletal movements coupled with widespread degradation and selective retention of transcripts.

DISCUSSION

Progressive restriction of *Parhyale vasa* transcripts to the PGCs

Although maternal *vasa* may be distributed to all the blastomeres during the first 12 hours of development, it is not uniformly present in the entire cell. It is unclear whether the unequal distribution of *vasa* to the yolk-free cytoplasm around the nucleus is what really occurs *in vivo* or if it is a technical difficulty of detection. It may be that equal levels of transcript are present throughout the yolk, but that our *in situ* methods cannot detect them. Alternatively, a possible reason to keep transcripts close to the nucleus may be that when cleavages become superficial and the yolk is shunted towards the center of the embryo at S5 (16-128 cells), the transcripts are already

concentrated in the portion of the cell that does not get relocated, but that ultimately makes the embryo proper. The uniform localization of *vasa* shows that it is not asymmetrically segregating prior to or when the g blastomere is established or even subcellularly in the putative germ plasm in the way that β -*catenin* does. Interestingly, between S6 and S8, the localization of *vasa* does become restricted to the PGCs. The loss of *vasa* in the other lineages may be the degradation of maternal transcripts, while the intense staining observed in the PGCs might reflect specific zygotic transcription of *vasa* in the progeny of g. Based on α -amanitin experiments inhibiting RNA polymerase II activity, zygotic transcription begins during gastrulation (S8) in *Parhyale* (unpublished observations). However, in *Drosophila* and *C. elegans*, germ cells are transcriptionally quiescent even when zygotic transcription begins (reviewed in Santos and Lehmann, 2004; Strome and Lehmann, 2007). Future experiments should address when germ cells in *Parhyale* are transcriptionally active to discern if the intense staining is from maternal or zygotic transcripts, which may provide evidence for the role of the early transcripts. Alternatively, it is also possible that maternal transcripts of *vasa* are not necessary for PGC specification or maintenance in *Parhyale*, unless it is somehow involved in initiating or maintaining the expression of zygotic transcripts or protein in the PGCs. The progressive restriction of *vasa* transcripts to the PGCs is also observed in other organisms such as in the cnidarian *Nematostella*, the medaka *Oryzias*, and the polychaete *Platynereis* (Extavour et al., 2005; Herpin et al., 2007; Rebscher et al., 2007; Shinomiya et al., 2000). The mechanism of

restriction may be similar to that observed in *C. elegans*, where there is a class of RNAs that are stabilized and protected in the germline, but degraded in the somatic lineages (Bashirullah et al., 1999; Seydoux and Fire, 1994).

Experiments in zebrafish and medaka demonstrate that the 3' UTR of *vasa* contains elements that are sufficient for RNA stability in the PGCs (Herpin et al., 2007; Wolke et al., 2002). It would be interesting to see if the 3' UTR in *Parhyale* can also direct germline specific stability to *vasa* fusion transcripts, suggesting that posttranscriptional modifications of the mRNA causes the stabilization of transcripts in the PGCs.

vasa protein localization versus mRNA localization

Asymmetric mRNA localization is not required to specify germline in all organisms. In *Drosophila* and *C. elegans*, *vasa* mRNA is uniformly localized at the earliest stages of germline specification, but it is the protein localization that is necessary for proper segregation of the germline (reviewed in Raz, 2000; Saffman and Lasko, 1999). In *Parhyale*, it has been previously shown that Vasa protein is first observed at “barely detectable levels” at the eight-cell stage in the g blastomere and then subsequently only in the PGCs, providing evidence for the early specification of the germline (Extavour, 2005). The lack of Vasa protein at the one-to-four-cell stages suggests that it is not maternally provided, although it is present in mature oocytes (see Chapter IV). If it is not maternally provided, then it must be translated from maternal or zygotic transcripts. If this is the case, then the maternal localization of *vasa* transcripts in the early embryo would play a role in germline specification at the

posttranscriptional level beyond just RNA degradation in the somatic cells. Since *vasa* transcripts are still present in all cells at the eight-cell stage, there would have to be a mechanism to specifically translate the *vasa* mRNA only in the g blastomere or to rapidly degrade the protein in the somatic lineages. Therefore, there could be several different mechanisms working to localize *vasa* protein and transcripts to the PGCs. It is also formally possible that very low levels of Vasa are present at the one-to-four-cell stages that could not be detected by antibody staining. A western blot for Vasa at these early stages may shed light on this issue.

RNA localization in the putative germ plasm in *Parhyale*

RNA localization during oogenesis and embryogenesis is a key mechanism for the cytoplasmic distribution of determinants (Kloc et al., 2001; Mahowald, 2001; Seydoux and Schedl, 2001). I have found a mRNA that is localized subcellularly in what may be the germ plasm in *Parhyale*. Unexpectedly, the mRNA is the *Parhyale* ortholog of β -catenin, a multifunctional protein involved in the transduction of Wnt signaling and in cell adhesion. The localization of β -catenin mRNA to germ plasm or PGCs has not been previously reported, although in the sea urchin *L. variegatus*, β -catenin is observed at higher levels in the cytoplasm and nuclei of the small micromeres (Miller and McClay, 1997). The small micromeres give rise to the majority of the adult tissue and have long been thought to give rise to the PGCs as well (Hyman, 1955; Pehrson and Cohen, 1986).

β-catenin mRNA is first detected as a loose matrix at the cortex in the early one-cell embryo that then aggregates together by the end of the first cell cycle. This aggregate then segregates asymmetrically for three divisions, ending up in the g blastomere, and then segregates symmetrically for two divisions, after which the transcripts are no longer detected. Strikingly, a morphological feature also exists in the one-cell stage embryo that corresponds with *β-catenin* localization. Together, these data suggest the presence of a specialized region within the cytoplasm of early stage *Parhyale* embryo that may be analogous to the germ plasm observed in other organisms that segregate their germline early in development. An interesting, although technically challenging, experiment might be to transplant the putative germ plasm from the g blastomere and put it into another cell at the four- or eight-cell stage to see if that cell is now able to make germ cells.

A similar pattern of aggregation of transcripts is also observed in *Xenopus*, although not for *β-catenin* transcripts, which are thought to be uniformly distributed (DeMarais and Moon, 1992). Following fertilization of *Xenopus* oocytes, the germ plasm aggregates into germ plasm islands at the vegetal cortex (Kloc et al., 2001). It has been shown that microtubules, as well as, an ATP dependent kinesin like protein, Xklp1, are required for this aggregation (Ressom and Dixon, 1988; Robb et al., 1996; Savage and Danilchik, 1993). Based on the cortical localization of *Parhyale β-catenin*, it is worth examining if and how the cytoskeleton may influence the transport or

movement of *β-catenin* transcripts. Experiments using microtubule inhibitors, such as nocodazole and colchicine, would address this question.

Another obvious question is what directs *β-catenin* to localize to the putative germ plasm. In several organisms, the 3'UTRs of different germline mRNAs are important for localization, tethering, or translational repression (reviewed in Kloc et al., 2001; Mahowald, 2001). Elements within the 3'UTR of human *β-catenin* isoforms have been shown to play a role in RNA stability (Thiele et al., 2006), but not in directing localization of the mRNA. *In vivo* functional analysis of the *Parhyale β-catenin* 3'UTR is needed to address this issue. A possible experiment would be to attach the 3'UTR downstream of a reporter gene and see whether that transcript can now localize to the putative germ plasm.

β-catenin transcripts are also present in the immature oocytes. However, it is not detected in the mature oocytes. There are several possibilities for this result. One could be that much of the transcripts are degraded prior to fertilization. Alternatively, there could have been a dramatic rearrangement of transcripts to a subcellular domain located deep within the oocyte. Our *in situ* protocol may not be sensitive enough to distinguish between these two possibilities. So far, only a few mRNAs probes have been tested on oocytes. Based on my own data and those of O'Day (2006), transcripts that are found in the oocytes are only observed in immature oocytes and not mature ones. In the case of *vasa* and *β-catenin*, which are clearly maternally provided, it seems unlikely that there would be complete

degradation of maternal mRNAs prior to fertilization. Therefore, these observations suggest that it may be technical issue detecting transcripts in mature oocytes. A detailed study characterizing the process of oogenesis may shed light on how and when maternal mRNAs are differentially localized in *Parhyale*.

Difference between *vasa* and β -catenin localization

If *Parhyale* does contain a bona fide germ plasm, one might expect to see a highly conserved germline determinant, such as Vasa, localized to that specialized area, either at the mRNA level or protein level. However, neither appears to be localized to anything resembling the germ plasm. *vasa* mRNA is localized in the yolk-free cytoplasm and *vasa* protein appears evenly distributed in the cytoplasm of g during the early cleavages and then perinuclearly thereafter (Extavour, 2005). *In situ* data of another germline determinant, *Parhyale nanos*, suggests that this mRNA is also not subcellularly localized to the putative germ plasm during early cleavage stages although it is localized to the PGCs at later stages (Matthias Gerberding, personal communication).

Yet the subcellular localization of β -catenin specifically to the germline is highly suggestive of a specialized cytoplasm. Germ plasm components are typically retained in the PGCs after specification (Saffman and Lasko, 1999). However, the lack of β -catenin after the 128-cell stage implies either a change in the regulation of the transcript in the putative germ plasm or the absence of germ plasm at these stages. The localization of other RNAs, especially of other

known germline determinants, will further our understanding of the different patterns and mechanisms of RNA localization in *Parhyale*. Furthermore, characterization of the putative germ plasm by electron microscopy and other ultrastructural assays may highlight the similarities and differences between germ plasm in other organisms and in *Parhyale*. The localization patterns of *vasa* and *β -catenin* described in this chapter greatly add new insights into the mechanism of germ cell specification by preformation.

Figure 3.1 Conservation of DEAD box motifs in *Parhyale*

In DEAD box proteins, there are nine conserved motifs: Q-motif, I, Ia, Ib, II, III, IV, V, VI. The consensus sequences listed are greater than 60% homologous between all DEAD box sequences. *Parhyale* sequence motifs are highly conserved compared to the consensus sequences. Differences from consensus are shaded light gray. Color of each box/motif reflects the color of the motifs in Figure 3.2. Symbols for degenerate sites are the same used in Cordin et al., 2006. x: (any amino acid); 1: (I, L); +: (H, K, R); a: (F, W, Y); c: (D, E, H, K, R); h: (A, F, G, I, L, M, P, V, W, Y); u: (A, G); o: (S, T).

MOTIFS	Q-motif	I	Ia	Ib	II	III	IV	V	VI
DEAD-box consensus	GaccPohIQ	AxTGoGKT	PTRELA	TPGR1	DEAD	SAT	1IFhxT+cx	TDV <u>u</u> ARGID	HRIGRTGR
	89%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	78%	100%
P.hawaiensis Vasa	Gyk <u>t</u> PtpiQ	AqTGsGKT	PTRELA	TPGRL	DEAD	SAT	LIFveTkr <u>t</u>	TAVaARGLD	HRIGRTGR

Figure 3.2 Alignment of Vasa DEAD box and Helicase domains

A) Amino acid alignment of the DEAD box domain shows the level of conservation between different species. B) Amino acid alignment of the helicase domain. These two domains contain the nine motifs required for ATPase activity, RNA binding, and RNA helicase activity (shaded colored boxes using the same color scheme from Figure 3.1). Alignments were first made using default parameters of ClustalW and then adjusted by hand. The following protein sequences were obtained from the National Center for Biotechnology Information database (NCBI): *Daphnia magna* (water flea), *Moina macrocopa* (water flea), *Artemia franciscana* (brine shrimp), *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Pacific white shrimp), *Drosophila melanogaster* (fruit fly), *Apis mellifera* (honey bee), *Schistocerca gregaria* (grasshopper), *Tribolium castaneum* (red flour beetle), *Bombyx mori* (silkworm moth), *Copidosoma floridanum* (parasitic wasp), *Crassostrea gigas* (oyster), *Platynereis dumerilli* (polychaete annelid), *Tubifex tubifex* (oligochaete annelid), *Botrylloides violaceus* (colonial ascidian), *Ciona savignii* (sea squirt), *Mus musculus* (mouse), *Xenopus laevis* (frog), *Nematostella vectensis* (sea anemone). Accession numbers are listed in Appendix D.

Figure 3.3 Comparison of select arthropod Vasa orthologs

Comparison of *Parhyale* Vasa domains and motifs with the branchipod crustacean *Daphnia magna* (water flea) and the insect *Drosophila melanogaster* (fruit fly) showing percent identity in the DEAD (orange box) and helicase (blue box) domains. Percent identity was based on comparison of the ClustalW pairwise alignments. The RGG (green ovals) and zinc finger (CCHC) motifs (red rectangles) are important for binding to nucleic acids and vary greatly between species.

Parhyale Vasa

Figure 3.4 Phylogenetic analysis of Vasa orthologs

Phylogenetic relationships among several subfamilies of RNA helicases. The 50%-majority rule consensus of post-burn-in sampled trees from the Bayesian inference analysis based on a data set including the amino acid sequences of Vasa, PL10, p68/62 and eIF4A RNA helicases subfamilies from 36 taxa is shown. Branch lengths are mean estimates. eIF4 amino acid sequences were used as outgroup. Numbers in the nodes are BPP. Nodes below 0.95 were collapsed.

Figure 3.5 *vasa* expression in *Parhyale*

In situ hybridization with an antisense riboprobe showing *vasa* expression during embryogenesis. (A–F) Brightfield images. (A'–F'') False-color overlay counterstained with DAPI to visualize nuclei. (C–F'') Anterior is up; ventral views unless otherwise noted. (A, A') *vasa* transcripts, presumably maternally provided, are localized in the yolk free cytoplasm in all cells at the 16-32 cell stage (S5). (B, B') At soccerball stage, S6, there are four intensely stained cells and a variable number of weakly stained cells. (C, C') During gastrulation (S8), weakly stained cells are not found. Only four to eight strongly stained cells are present. (D, D') At the germband stage S13, *vasa* is expressed in the single germcell cluster at the level of the gnathal segments. Dorsal view. (E, E') By S17, the appendages are beginning to form. The germ cells have split into two bilateral clusters that have migrated laterally towards the midgut. (F, F'') S19 embryo. The germ cell clusters will migrate from this ventral lateral position dorsally to the presumptive somatic gonad.

Figure 3.6 *vasa* and *DsRed* double *in situ* hybridization

(A, B) Brightfield images of *DsRed* mRNA (lineage tracer) in red and *vasa* (germ cell marker) in blue. (A', B') DAPI images. (A, A') S8-S9 embryo injected with *DsRed* into g at the eight-cell stage stained for *DsRed* and *vasa*. The intensely stained *vasa* positive cells are the same as the *DsRed* positive cells (arrow). Weaker *vasa* positive cells are located adjacent to the g cluster. The faint *DsRed* staining at the top of the embryo is not in cells, but in the yolk that is shunted towards the center of the embryo during early cleavages. (B, B') S8-S9 embryo injected with *DsRed* into Mav at the eight-cell stage stained for *DsRed* and *vasa*. *DsRed* labels the cells adjacent to the *vasa* positive cells (arrow), but does not appear to be in the strong *vasa*-positive cells. The weak *vasa* positive cells are no longer visible under the *DsRed* staining, but based on location near the g progeny, the progeny of Mav likely contains low levels of *vasa*. Scale bar: 100 μ m.

Figure 3.7 Localization of *vasa* in oocytes

A) Brightfield image of an ovary from *Parhyale* stained for *vasa*. Stained cells are immature oocytes. Mature oocytes are not stained. In an intact animal, the immature oocytes would be located medially while the mature yolk-filled oocytes are located more laterally. B) False-color overlay counterstained with the nuclear marker, DAPI.

B

A

Figure 3.8 Alignment of the central Arm repeat domain

The central region of the protein contains 12 imperfect Arm repeats.

Comparison of sequences shows the high level of conservation in this region.

Approximate regions of the 12 repeats are alternatively shaded in blue and

green boxes. The following species were analyzed: *Parhyale hawaiiensis*

(amphipod), *Daphnia pulex* (water flea), *Drosophila melanogaster* (fruit fly),

Anopheles gambiae (African malaria mosquito), *Gryllus bimaculatus* (cricket),

Aedes aegypti (yellow fever mosquito), *Achaearanea tepidariorum* (spider),

Aplysia californica (sea hare), *Platynereis dumerilli* (polychaete annelid),

Chaetopterus variopedatus (polychaete annelid), *Strongylocentrolus*

purpuratus (sea urchin), *Ciona intestinalis* (sea squirt), *Xenopus laevis* (frog),

Danio rerio (zebrafish), *Mus musculus* (mouse), *Homo sapiens* (human),

Hydra vulgaris and *Hydra magnipapillata* (cnidarians). Accession numbers

are listed in Appendix D.

Figure 3.9 Comparison of select arthropod β -catenin orthologs

Schematic diagram showing conserved motifs and percent identity between domains. The central Arm domain (green) displays the most conservation with 85% sequence identity with both *Drosophila melanogaster* (fruit fly) and *Daphnia pulex* (water flea) compared to the N-terminal domain (~60%) (pink) and C-terminal domain (~40%) (blue). Motifs are named according to Schneider et al., (2006). In the N-terminus, there are three conserved motifs. Motifs 1 (dark pink) and 3 (orange) are involved in GSK3 β and α -catenin binding, respectively. Motif 2 (gray) has not been functionally described. Motifs A (purple) and B (light blue), in the C-terminus, are important for transactivation and protein-protein interactions. *Parhyale* β -catenin has all five of the conserved motifs.

Parhyale armadillo/β-catenin

Figure 3.10 Phylogenetic analysis of β -catenin orthologs

The 50%-majority rule consensus of post-burn-in sampled trees from the Bayesian inference analysis based on a data set including the amino acid sequences of β -catenin orthologs from 23 taxa is shown. Branch lengths are mean estimates. *Hydra* β -catenin amino acid sequences were used as the outgroup. Numbers in the nodes are BPP. Nodes below 0.95 were collapsed.

Figure 3.11 Asymmetric localization of *Parhyale* β -catenin during early cleavage stages

1. *In situ* hybridization reveals the novel localization of β -catenin (A–D)

Brightfield images. (C', D') False-color overlay counterstained with DAPI in

blue. (A) One-cell embryo with β -catenin aggregate subcellularly localized. (B)

Two-cell embryo. β -catenin has segregated to one of the two blastomeres. (C)

Eight-cell embryo. At this stage, g is located in one specific micromere. (D) 8-

16 cell embryo. β -catenin segregates symmetrically into the daughter cells of

the micromere. **2.** Double *in situ* for β -catenin (blue) and the lineage tracer

DsRed (red). Embryos injected with *DsRed* mRNA into either (A) the Mavg

blastomere at the four-cell stage or (B) the g blastomere at the eight-cell stage

show co-localization of lineage tracer and β -catenin in the same cell. Scale bar:

100 μ m.

1

2

Figure 3.12 *β-catenin* correlates to the morphologically distinct subcellular region (the spot) observed in one-cell embryos that may be the putative germ plasm

(A, B) Live darkfield images (A) An early one-cell embryo with no distinguishing features. (B) A late one-cell embryo with the distinct region (spot) clearly visible on the surface of the cell (arrow). Scale bar: 100 μm. (C, D) Brightfield images of late one-cell embryos cut roughly in halves and stained for *β-catenin*. (C) Halves without the spot are negative for *β-catenin*. (D) *β-catenin* is located in the same pieces as the morphological feature observed in one-cell embryos that may be a specialized cytoplasm called the germ plasm.

Figure 3.13 Aggregation of β -catenin during the one-cell stage

In situ hybridization of one-cell embryos fixed at different times during the first cell cycle and stained for β -catenin. (A) Early one-cell embryo showing the loose matrix of β -catenin at or near the cortex. (B–D) Progressively older one-cell embryos showing the aggregation of β -catenin to a subcellular region.

Scale bar: 100 μ m.

Figure 3.14 *β-catenin* localization in immature oocytes

(A) Bright field image of immature oocytes. *β-catenin* transcripts are predominantly located in the yolk-free cytoplasm surrounding the nuclei. (B) Corresponding DAPI image. The larger diffuse-looking nuclei are the immature oocytes, while the brighter, smaller cells are the follicle cells. (C) False-color overlay of A and B. Scale bar: 100μm.

Chapter IV: Germline ablation and regulation in *Parhyale hawaiiensis*

SUMMARY

Many organisms generate their germline by either one of two specification mechanisms: preformation (segregation of cytoplasmic determinants) or epigenesis (induction). In *Parhyale*, the germline is exclusively derived from a single blastomere, g, at the eight-cell stage. Based on this observation, it appears that the germline in *Parhyale* is segregated by a preformation-based mechanism. To determine the developmental potential of the g blastomere, I ablated this cell or its progeny and examined the subsequent development of the animal. Ablation of g, its precursor blastomere from the four cell stage, Mavg, or, later, its progeny during the germband elongation stage, resulted in a loss of primordial germ cells (PGCs) as defined by the loss of expression of *vasa* gene products, as well as, morphological characteristics. Therefore, ablation of g was not compensated for by any of the other lineages during embryogenesis. Furthermore, these results support the observations that the g blastomere exclusively gives rise to all of the PGCs in the embryo. Remarkably, these g-ablated animals live, mate, and produce normal offspring suggesting that the germ cells were replaced post-embryonically. Based on Vasa localization in the developing gonads, the replacement of the germline occurs between two- and four-weeks post hatching. These results suggest that in the event of germline loss during embryogenesis, *Parhyale* can re-induce germ cell specification

during juvenile stages, thereby availing themselves of both preformation and epigenetic modes of specification.

INTRODUCTION

The unique ability of the germ cells to make the gametes of an animal and hence the next generation makes them one of the most interesting and widely studied cell types in development. The proper specification and maintenance of these cells is a critical step in the process. As reviewed in Chapter I, germ cell specification occurs by two distinct modes: preformation through the early segregation of germline determinants or epigenesis through the later induction of germ cells by the surrounding cells. In organisms that specify their germline by preformation, the germ plasm is an essential component. Experimental manipulations, by genetic means or by manual removal of germ plasm, have shown that loss of specific components of the germ plasm, the entire germ plasm, or the germ cells themselves can have dire consequences for future reproductive success. In many animals, loss of primordial germ cells (PGCs) results in sterility (Eddy, 1975; Geigy, 1931; Sulston et al., 1983; Weidinger et al., 2003).

PGC loss in organisms that specify germline via preformation

Both *Drosophila melanogaster* and *Caenorhabditis elegans* segregate their germline early in development by the asymmetric segregation of germline determinants, i.e., by preformation (see Figure 1.2). In *Drosophila*, proper

assembly and segregation of the germ plasm into the posterior pole cells is required for proper germline development (reviewed in Mahowald, 2001). The first indication that the posterior germ plasm (also called pole plasm) is critical for germline specification came from the UV irradiation of eggs, which results in the loss of PGCs and produce sterile flies (Geigy, 1931). Further experiments show that transplanted germ plasm rescues the UV effect and induces PGCs in ectopic sites (Illmensee and Mahowald, 1974; Okada et al., 1974). Several components of the germ plasm have been identified by maternal effect screens and shown to be essential for germ cell specification, such as *oskar*, *vasa*, and *tudor*. This class of mutations, called “grandchildless,” are mutations in maternal effect genes whereby the mutation causes the loss of a maternally provided product; therefore, its loss does not affect the development of the mother but only of her progeny. In this case, the progeny derived from homozygous mutant mothers do not make germ plasm or pole cells and therefore are sterile, even though the progeny, themselves, are not homozygous mutant (reviewed in Mahowald, 2001). These different mutations can be further classified into groups that affect various aspects of this process. Many of the epistatic relationships and molecular functions of these genes have been elucidated and reveal the complexity of the system (reviewed in Riechmann and Ephrussi, 2001; Santos and Lehmann, 2004; van Eeden and St Johnston, 1999). However, in all these cases, the eventual outcome is sterility demonstrating that these PGCs are the only precursor to functional gametes in the adult.

Segregation of the germline in *C. elegans* begins at fertilization with the asymmetric partitioning of the P granules to more posterior blastomeres until the founder PGC blastomere, P4, segregates P granules symmetrically to its daughter cells, Z2 and Z3 (reviewed in Saffman and Lasko, 1999). Ablation of the P4 blastomere results in a loss of the germline and sterile adults (Sulston et al., 1983). Although P granules are a faithful marker for the germ cells throughout development, they alone are not sufficient to make germ cells, since mutations that affect polarity or asymmetric divisions cause P granule mislocalization but not transformation to germ cell fate (Strome and Wood, 1982). However, specific components of the P granules proteins are required for germline development. Loss-of-function mutations or RNA interference of *pgl* genes, a novel family of proteins with RGG motifs found in RNA binding proteins, or *glh*, the *C. elegans vasa*-related genes, result in sterility (Gruidl et al., 1996; Kawasaki et al., 2004; Kawasaki et al., 1998; Kuznicki et al., 2000). However, in both of these cases, initial germ cell fate does not appear to be affected, but rather later differentiation of the gametes and gonads is affected.

Evidence suggests that both the frog *Xenopus laevis* and the zebrafish *Danio rerio* have germ plasm and specify PGCs by preformation while in mammals, such as mice and humans, no early germ plasm is present and the PGCs are specified by epigenesis (Braat et al., 2000; Knaut et al., 2000; Lawson and Hage, 1994; Tam and Zhou, 1996; Tanabe and Kotani, 1974). In *Xenopus*, assembly of the germ plasm begins during oogenesis in the vegetal region. Physical removal of that germ plasm or UV irradiation of oocytes or

fertilized eggs results in the loss or partial loss of PGCs by tadpole stages providing some of the first clues that the germ plasm is indeed crucial for germ cell development (Bounoure, 1934; Buehr and Blackler, 1970; Holwill et al., 1987; Tanabe and Kotani, 1974). In these experiments, sterility is primarily defined as the loss of PGCs in the genital ridge. It is unclear whether any of these researchers grew these animals to adulthood and assayed their ability to generate offspring.

In zebrafish, genetic analyses gave the first indicators that the germline was specified early (reviewed in Raz, 2003). Estimates based on the frequency of γ -ray-induced mutations in fish irradiated at early cleavage stages and on early transplantations experiments suggest that there are five PGCs by the gastrula stage (Lin et al., 1992; Walker and Streisinger, 1983). The localization of *vasa* in material identified as germ plasm further confirmed that cytoplasmic segregation of germline determinants occurs in zebrafish prior to PGC specification (Knaut et al., 2000; Yoon et al., 1997). However, *vasa* morpholinos do not abolish germ cell specification, likely due to the maternal role of *vasa*, resulting in perfectly viable animals (Braat et al., 2001).

Therefore, to look at the effect of PGC loss on sterility, examination of genes that affect other aspects of PGC maintenance, such as migration and survival, is most informative. One such gene, *dead end (dnd)*, is required for proper migration and survival of the PGCs in both zebrafish and *Xenopus*.

Morpholinos to *dnd* result in the failure of PGCs to migrate to the gonads followed by apoptosis of those cells (Horvay et al., 2006; Weidinger et al.,

2003). Furthermore, when the morpholinos-injected embryos are raised to adulthood (by which time, the *dnd*-morpholinos probably lose effectiveness to dilution), they are still sterile, suggesting that there is no compensation of germline by other cells (Weidinger et al., 2003). *Nanos1* (*nos1*) is another zebrafish gene that is localized to the germ plasm early in development. Injection of morpholinos has shown this gene to be important for PGC migration and survival during embryogenesis, while reverse genetics has shown it is necessary for maintaining oocyte production in the adult females (Draper et al., 2007; Köprunner et al., 2001). In addition, the loss-of-function mutation shows a maternal-effect sterile phenotype whereby the progeny of a homozygous mutant female are sterile, although they themselves are heterozygous for the mutation suggesting that the *nos1* gene products are maternally required in zebrafish, similar to what is observed in *Drosophila nanos* mutant females (Draper et al., 2007; Gavis and Lehmann, 1992).

PGC loss in organisms that specify germline via epigenesis

In mammals, the PGCs are specified by epigenesis (induction) at later stages of development. Because the segregation of the germline involves signaling pathways, such as the Bone Morphogenetic Proteins (BMPs), which are also involved in other processes, mutations in such genes generally result in more widespread defects (reviewed in Matsui and Okamura, 2005). Therefore, the specific analysis of PGC loss on fertility is usually not possible in such mutants. However, mutations in genes that affect PGC function after the cells have already been determined can address how fertility is affected by PGC loss.

In mice, although *vasa* is expressed in the PGCs of both sexes, *vasa* loss-of-function mutants only affect spermatogenesis, resulting in infertile males (Tanaka et al., 2000). Two RNA binding proteins, *tiar* and *nanos3*, are also expressed specifically in the PGCs during migration to the genital ridges. Loss-of-function mutations in either of these genes result in the loss of PGCs by E13.5 and infertility in the adults (Beck et al., 1998; Tsuda et al., 2003). Therefore, in mice, the loss of PGCs during development also results in permanently sterile adults. Unfortunately, this observation is complicated by the use of loss-of-function mutations. Since they are required for PGC development, one would hypothesize that any replacement germ cells would also need these gene products, so could never form in the mutant progeny anyway.

However, irradiation experiments of young mice ovaries by Everett (1943) resulted in a lack of eggs and sterility when these mice were examined 20-180 days later, suggesting that the embryonic PGCs that gave rise to the eggs were the exclusive source (Everett, 1943). This finding is supported by the earlier irradiation of E8-E12-day mice *in utero*, which resulted in the massive decrease of germ cells, although, in this case, not all germ cells were destroyed (Mintz, 1959). Taken together, the irradiation experiments highly suggest that destroying early germ cells would result in irreversible sterility.

Germline specification in *Parhyale*

As mentioned in Chapter I, both modes of germline specification are found among arthropods and specifically among crustaceans. However, there

is a scarcity of information about the mechanism of germ cell specification in this group. In *Parhyale*, lineage studies and cell separations suggest that the founder PGC is segregated from the somatic lineages at the eight-cell stage. Furthermore, early localization of Vasa (Extavour, 2005) and the segregation of β -catenin in the putative germ plasm to the g blastomere and its progeny (Chapter III) support the preformation model of germline specification in *Parhyale*. To assess the effect of PGC loss, we performed timed ablations of the PGCs and examined the subsequent development of the animals. Based on preliminary experiments performed by Price (2005), it appears that photoablation of the g blastomere at the eight-cell stage results in the loss of Vasa-positive cells. To test for sterility, she then allowed some ablated animals to live to adulthood. In these initial experiments, some fertile adults were eventually observed, suggesting that the germline might be replaced in these ablated animals. At this point, I continued to investigate germline development and ablation by confirming and expanding upon these initial observations.

In this chapter, I discuss the regulative ability of the germline in *Parhyale*. Using two different methods of ablating the germline, I found that ablation of the g blastomere resulted in embryos and hatchlings that lack morphological and molecular evidence of germ cells. Most unexpectedly, these ablated animals eventually become fertile and produced normal offspring. I explore the timing of this replacement and the evolutionary implications of germline compensation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Germline Ablation

Embryos were injected at either the four- or eight-cell stage, into Mavg or g blastomeres, respectively, with 100 picoliters of 25-50 mg/ml of fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC) linked to dextran (250,000MW) (Sigma) and then ablated by photo-oxidation (Shankland, 1984). For ablations at the four- or eight-cell stage, embryos were exposed to the fluorescein excitation wavelength ($\lambda = 490\text{nm}$) for twenty minutes under a Zeiss Stemi SV11 Apo fluorescent scope using a GFP filter set and output from a FluoArc mercury lamp. For ablations at germband, a lineage tracer, nuclear localized DsRed, was also injected with the FITC-Dextran at the eight-cell stage. Following development to germband stages, embryos were exposed to $\lambda = 490\text{nm}$ using a Zeiss Axiophot (Zeiss Plan-NeoFLUAR 10x/0.3 objective) as essentially described in Chapter II. However, in these experiments, embryos were exposed for a total of 40 minutes. For RNase/DNase ablations, a 100 picoliters cocktail of 0.1 μg RNase A (Sigma), 0.02 units of RQ1 DNase (Promega) and, as a lineage tracer, 10 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$ TRITC-Dextran (Sigma) was injected into the g blastomere. Following injection, cells ceased to divide and within 24hrs became granular in appearance. This debris was subsequently reabsorbed by the embryo and can be seen as a fluorescent globule in the yolk for days following ablation and then disappearing completely. TRITC-Dextran does not have the same photo-oxidative effects as FITC-Dextran, and therefore can be used as a lineage tracer with no effect on development. Control embryos

injected with up to 100 picoliters of 50 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$ TRITC-Dextran developed normally to hatching. Embryos showing injection trauma were removed and not included in experiments.

Parhyale transformation using the *Minos* transposon system

Approximately 100 picoliters of 500 ng/ μg of the donor plasmid DNA *pMi{3xP3-DsRed; Ph-hsp70-DsRed}* (kindly provided by Anastasios Pavlopoulos), 100 ng/ μg of *Minos* transposase mRNA and 5-10 mg/ml TRITC-dextran were injected into the g blastomere at the eight-cell stage. Embryos were raised to adulthood and intercrossed with other injected Go's. The progeny were scored for the 3xP3 marker under a fluorescent Zeiss Stemi SV11 Apo dissecting scope using a DsRed filter set. Positive progeny (G1) were raised to adulthood and outcrossed with wildtype adults. The G2 progeny were then scored for the 3xP3 marker and for induction of DsRed expression from the heat shock promoter.

Immunohistochemistry

Embryos were dissected away from eggshell membranes and fixed for 15-20 minutes in 4% paraformaldehyde or in 3.7% formaldehyde in PEM (0.1M PIPES; 1mM MgSO_4 ; 2mM EGTA, pH 7.0) at room temperature. Embryos were then washed in 1x PT (1x PBS, pH 7.4 and 0.1% Triton X-100) 2-3 times followed by dehydration through a methanol series and storage at -20°C until further use or embryos were immediately processed through the antibody procedure as described by Patel (1989). Primary antibodies were used at the

following concentrations: rabbit anti-Formosa (for most vasa) (gift from the Akam lab) at 1:40-1:60, rabbit anti-zebrafish Vasa (gift from the Nusslein-Volhard lab) at 1:1000-1:3000, mouse anti-DsRed at 1:500 and rabbit anti-DsRed (Clontech) at 1:1000. Primary antibodies were incubated overnight at 4°C. AlexaFluor and HRP conjugated goat anti-mouse or rabbit (Jackson ImmunoResearch) secondaries was used between 1:300-1:750. Secondary incubations were for 2 hours at room temperature to overnight at 4°C. For the HRP reactions, embryos were reacted in DAB with nickel chloride followed by a counterstain in 1 µg/ml DAPI in either PBS or 50% glycerol and then transferred into 70% glycerol for clearing and mounting. Following DAPI counterstain, fluorescently stained embryos were mounted in *SlowFade* Gold antifade reagent (Invitrogen).

In situ hybridization

Germline ablated embryos were grown to the desired stage and then dissected and fixed in 3.7% formaldehyde in 90% filtered seawater. *In situ* hybridization was then performed as described in Chapter III using *Parhyale vasa* probes.

Timelapse and Microscopy

Embryos were timelapsed as described in (Price and Patel, 2007). Static images were captured and assembled as described in Chapter II.

RESULTS

The g blastomere exclusively gives rise the PGCs during embryogenesis

The fate map of the eight-cell stage in *Parhyale* shows that the g blastomere gives rise to PGCs (Gerberding et al., 2002). However this does not exclude the possibility that other lineages could also give rise to PGCs. Cell separations done at the eight-cell stage show that, when in isolation, only the progeny of g gives rise to Vasa-positive cells, and by extension, germ cells, suggesting that g is cell-autonomously specified to a germline fate, but also that no other lineage can give rise to Vasa-positive cells in the absence of g (Extavour, 2005). The caveat with these experiments is that the aggregates were fixed 24–36 hours following isolation; therefore, it is formally possible that other lineages could give rise to Vasa-positive germ cells at a later time in development. To show that g is the exclusive source of PGCs in intact embryos, I injected g with the RNA encoding nuclear localized DsRed, and then looked at the localization of DsRed compared to the localization of Vasa at a time after the g progeny have stopped dividing (n = 7). In the normal course of development, all of the Vasa-positive PGCs were also all positive for DsRed, demonstrating that the g blastomere gives rise to all the germ cells—and only the germ cells—during normal embryogenesis (Figure 4.1).

The g blastomere gives rise to functional gametes

Genetic transformations have previously been established in *Parhyale* (Pavlopoulos and Averof, 2005). In these cases, the transgenic constructs were

injected at the one- to four-cell stages demonstrating that the germ cells derived from the early embryo can give rise to functional gametes. To specifically test whether the g blastomere, itself, can give rise to functional gametes, I injected the g blastomere with a transgenic construct that drives expression of DsRed from the *Parhyale* heat shock protein-70 (hsp70) promoter. I then raised these embryos (Go) to adulthood and intercrossed the adults. I obtained transgenic progeny from these Go adults, showing that integration of this construct, specifically in the g lineage, can make functional gametes (data not shown). Therefore, all the available evidence convincingly demonstrates that the g blastomere exclusively gives rise to primordial germ cells that populate the gonads and, ultimately, make functional eggs and sperm.

Ablation of the g blastomere results in a viable animal

Because g is the exclusive source of germ cells during embryogenesis, we hypothesized that ablation of the g blastomere would result in a loss of germ cells during embryogenesis. Identification of the g blastomere is relatively easy due to the refringent property of g. Typically, g is also the smallest cell at the eight-cell stage. However, due to the spatial arrangement of blastomeres at the eight-cell stage and the possibility of misidentification, it was critical that I was confident that g had been ablated. Therefore, as a control for my ablations, I also injected Mav, the blastomere adjacent to g, with nuclear localized DsRed or TRITC-dextran (Figure 4.2A). In the event that en was misidentified as g and ablated, I would observe lineage tracer in the posterior ectoderm lineage from Ep, instead of in the visceral mesoderm lineage from Mav. As with the

ablations described in Chapter II, ablated cells ceased to divide following photoablation and died. As a secondary check for a successful ablation, g-ablated embryos can be distinguished from other ablated embryos by the placement of the dead cell near the germ cap 24 hours after ablation, compared to en ablation, after which the dead cell remains in the extraembryonic area. Frequently, these dead cells are entirely excluded from the developing embryo and can be seen as granular debris between the embryo and the outer eggshell membrane until hatching (Figure 4.2B).

Embryos in which the g blastomere was ablated by photoablation survive to hatching greater than 80% of the time (data not shown). This high survival rate suggests that further development of the other lineages is not dependent on signals from the g lineage.

g-ablated embryos lack PGCs

In live embryos, the PGC cluster is refringent, thus, morphologically visible, during germband elongation (Figure 4.3A, B). However, in g-ablated embryos, the cluster of cells is not visible at these stages (Figure 4.3C, D), suggesting that the PGCs are not present at the morphological level.

To confirm the loss of PGCs molecularly, I looked at the expression of the germline marker, *vasa*, in ablated embryos. As detailed in Chapter III, *vasa* is a highly conserved germline marker and can be assayed in *Parhyale* by *in situ* hybridization, as well as, by staining with two cross-reactive Vasa antibodies.

In *Parhyale*, *vasa* transcripts are localized in all cells at the earliest cleavages, but eventually become restricted to the germ cells following gastrulation (see Figure 3.5). *vasa* protein is first observed weakly in the g blastomere at the eight-cell stage and then subsequently only in the progeny of the g blastomere (Extavour, 2005; Figure 4.1).

In nonablated embryos, *vasa* transcripts are clearly present in the PGC clusters during germband elongation (Figure 4.4A, A'). However, *vasa* was not detected in g-ablated (Figure 4.4B, B') or Mavg-ablated embryos (Figure 4.4C, C') by 112 hours of development (S20). In embryos younger than 30 hours post fertilization, the weak *vasa* staining observed in nonablated embryos (see Figure 3.5B) was also still present in g-ablated embryos (data not shown), but clearly it was still degraded in ablated embryos following gastrulation.

Compared to nonablated embryos (Figure 4.5A), g-ablated embryos were absent for *vasa* protein, at S22, as assayed by the cross-reactive anti-formosa antibody (n = 14)(Figure 4.5B) and the anti-zebrafish Vasa antibody (n = 9)(data not shown). Vasa appeared to be completely abolished during embryogenesis in these animals. Therefore, loss of both *vasa* mRNA and protein in g-ablated embryos suggests that the PGCs are completely absent during embryogenesis.

As a control for photoablation and additional confirmation that g-ablated embryos lack PGCs, I used an alternative method for inducing cell death. I injected a toxic cocktail of RNase and DNase into the g blastomere at the eight-cell stage. Cell death was evident by the “spreading” of the cell and

then, usually, the rapid disintegration leaving granular debris, which is subsequently engulfed by the gut (Figure 4.6A–C). Control embryos injected with TRITC-dextran divided normally and showed no phenotype (Figure 4.6D). As in the photoablated embryos, these ablated embryos also lacked the morphologically visible PGC cluster and Vasa was also absent (data not shown), suggesting that ablation via this method also results in the loss of PGCs during embryogenesis.

g-ablated adults are fertile

Although the primordial germ cells are absent in g-ablated embryos, we were surprised to find that these embryos, when raised to adulthood, were actually fertile, implying that they reformed their germline. To test the fertility of g-ablated animals, we placed them in mating tanks and monitored mating activity. The first indication that these animals might be fertile was the presence of mature oocytes in the ovaries of females followed by the standard pre-mating behavior of amplexus.

Approximately 90% of g-ablated adults were fertile, suggesting that the germline is replaced at some time interval following hatching (Table 4.1). Furthermore, these animals were able to reproduce with little to no delay compared to nonablated controls or controls in which another blastomere was ablated, suggesting that the germline is replaced prior to reproductive maturity. In addition, ablation of Mavg at the four-cell resulted in a viable hatchling approximately 8% of the time (11 hatchlings out of 142 injected). Of those hatchlings that survived to reproductive maturity, 88% (7 out of 8) were also

fertile (Table 4.1). In the majority of ablations, the dead g cell is excluded from the embryo proper (Figure 4.2B). As an added control to make sure that the dying g cell could not in any way contribute or influence the later induction of replacement germ cells, I physically removed the dead cell, by S10, following ablation. Of the embryos that survived the ablation and microdissection, both were also fertile (n = 2) suggesting that the ablated cell does not influence germ cell compensation. Control animals that were injected with FITC, but not ablated were 100% fertile (55/55 animals).

In the RNase/DNase ablation experiments, the embryos did not survive as often as did the photoablated embryos. This difference may be due to the rapid disintegration of the cell following injection, which allows the debris and toxic nucleases to surround the other cells, creating an unhealthy extracellular environment. However, in the animals that can surmount this difficulty and survive to adulthood, five out of seven, or 71%, (Table 4.1), were fertile, producing offspring that also appeared normal, consistent with what was observed in photoablated animals. The lower percentage of fertile animals, compared to photoablation, is likely not significant, but rather due to the lower number of total animals assayed in this experiment.

The progeny of these g-ablated matings appeared to be completely normal. However, to test for the possibility of a “grandchildless” phenotype, I first looked to see if the offspring of the g-ablated adults had germ cells during embryogenesis. The offspring had a clearly visible germ cell cluster during germband stages, as well as, Vasa-positive cells in the correct spatial and

temporal pattern consistent with being PGCs (data not shown). When I raised these hatchlings to adulthood, these animals were able to reproduce normally. To date, I have taken this line through four generations, suggesting that animals derived from g-ablated parents are completely normal.

Vasa-positive cells reappear in g-ablated animals

At this point, I knew that the germline must re-form some time between hatching and reproductive age. In order to clarify when this event occurred, I first looked at the localization of Vasa in the ovaries of the fertile g-ablated females. Vasa was localized in both mature and immature oocytes in a perinuclear pattern around the diffuse nucleus (Figure 4.7), in exactly the same pattern observed in nonablated animals (data not shown) (Extavour, unpublished data). Therefore, the gametes that differentiate from the replacement germ cells also localize Vasa. To determine when Vasa-positive cells are first found in g-ablated animals, I fixed and stained juvenile animals at various time points. Normally, in nearly hatched animals, the PGCs express Vasa, migrate medially and dorsally, and then arrange themselves in two bilateral clusters along the medial dorsal side, presumably within the confines of the primordial somatic gonad (Figure 4.8A–C). In g-ablated animals younger than two weeks post hatching, Vasa is absent from the primordial gonad (Figure 4.8D, E, and data not shown), suggesting that replacement does not occur within the first two weeks post hatching. However, by four weeks post hatching, Vasa-positive cells could be distinguished within the gonad, suggesting that the PGCs reform between two- and four-weeks post-hatching

(Figure 4.8F–I). This result is also consistent with my observation that these animals were not reproductively delayed, implying they completely replace their germline before reproductive maturity.

Germband stage ablation (S14) results in the loss of the PGCs by hatching

The evidence thus far supports the hypothesis that if the founder PGC (g blastomere) is ablated at the eight-cell stage, germline replacement is not being induced during embryogenesis, but rather during juvenile stages. However, I cannot exclude the possibility that the initial inductive signaling cascade could be initiated during embryogenesis and that ablation of the germ cells might not be replaceable following ablation later in development. To address this question, I injected FITC-dextran into g at the eight-cell stage and then ablated the PGCs at the germband stage S14 when the PGCs are located as a single cluster underlying the ectoderm (Figure 4.9A). In these experiments, I also co-injected DsRed as a lineage tracer, so that following photoablation, cell death could be more easily assessed. Cell death was evident by the granular appearance of the cluster, which never segregated into two clusters (Figure 4.9B) as nonablated embryos would, at this stage (Figure 4.9D), and by the loss of all of the FITC- and DsRed-positive cells (data not shown). Vasa was also absent in these ablated animals (Figure 4.9C) compared to nonablated animals (Figure 4.9E). These results show that ablation at the germband stage also results in a loss of PGCs during embryogenesis.

Ablation of PGCs at the germband stage results in fertile adults

The germband-ablated animals are also fertile. One hundred percent of the animals were able to mate and produce viable offspring with no significant delay (Table 4.1). This high fertility rate implies that even if a germ cell or a couple of germ cells survived the ablation process in a few of the ablated embryos, it could not account for the observed fertility in the remaining ablated animals. Furthermore, these results demonstrate that germ cell replacement can still occur when the PGCs are ablated later during embryogenesis. This finding suggests that the inductive signal for germline compensation is not required prior to germband stages. Although Vasa localization was not examined in four-week-old juveniles in these experiments, the lack of a delay in reproduction suggests that compensation likely occurs at approximately the same time as in the ablations performed at the eight-cell stage.

DISCUSSION

Parhyale uses both preformation and epigenesis

Ablation of the Mavg blastomere at the four-cell stage, the g blastomere at the eight-cell stage, or of the PGCs at the germband stage, in *Parhyale*, all result in the loss of Vasa-positive PGCs during embryogenesis, yet these germline-ablated adults are fertile. In *Parhyale*, several lines of evidence demonstrate that PGC specification relies on preformation by the segregation of germline determinants early in development (Extavour, 2005; Gerberding et

al., 2002; Chapter III), yet this ability to compensate for the loss of those cells suggests that an inductive mechanism must also exist. This unexpected result indicates that although the preferred mode of germline specification is preformation, *Parhyale*, if required, can induce another lineage to produce functional germ cells, ensuring the propagation of the next generation.

The ancestral mode of specification in the lineage leading to arthropods remains unclear. However, the higher frequency of epigenesis within this group suggests that epigenesis may be ancestral and that preformation is derived. Extavour et al. (2005 and 2007a) hypothesizes that the evolution of preformation from an ancestral epigenetic mode could have occurred by the misexpression of genes required for gametogenesis, such as *vasa* and *nanos*, which were then mislocalized in the cytoplasm of oocytes as germline determinants, thus evolving a preformation mechanism. If this were the case, it seems plausible, if not likely, that there would be some animals that can use both preformation and epigenetic mechanisms of germ cell specification. In such animals, they would retain the ability to induce germ cells, although they evolved and primarily use preformation to specify germline and that in other animals, such as *Drosophila*, *C. elegans*, and zebrafish, this ability has been lost in preference for strictly preformation. For example, a re-examination of some animals, such as sea urchins or ascidians, may reveal the dual existence of preformation and epigenesis in the same organism.

In sea urchins, it has long been thought that the small micromeres may also generate the germ cells during embryonic development (Pehrson and

Cohen, 1986). The accumulation of germline determinants, such as *vasa*, *seawi*, and *nanos*, in the small micromeres further suggest that this may be the case (Juliano et al., 2006), although a definitive PGC population has yet to be described in these animals. However, ablation of the small micromeres during embryonic development results in fertile adults, raising the possibility that the germline arises *de novo* from a postembryonic lineage (Ransick et al., 1996). Based on this result, Ransick et al. (1996) conclude that the small micromeres are not the “exclusive or obligatory source of the germline” and further predict that an embryonic germline lineage would not exist in maximally indirect developers, such as the sea urchin. Perhaps an alternative explanation is that the germline is segregated during embryonic and larval development from the small micromeres, but that other lineages compensate for the loss of these germ cells when the small micromeres are ablated, similar to what is observed in *Parhyale*. A clearer analysis of the lineage of the small micromeres regarding the development of the germline is required to fully address this hypothesis.

Another case in which germline compensation may also be observed is in the sea squirt *Ciona intestinalis*. The dynamic localization of *vasa* products in specific posterior blastomeres during early cleavages and gastrula stage strongly suggests that the progeny of the B.12 cells specifies the germline (Fujimura and Takamura, 2000; Shirae-Kurabayashi et al., 2006; Takamura et al., 2002). Experiments where the tail containing the *Vasa*-positive cells was cut off during larval stages and the remaining larvae followed through

metamorphosis showed that the resulting juveniles did not have Vasa-positive cells during early juvenile stages, but that some 15-day-old animals did contain Vasa-positive cells. These animals subsequently also had sperm, although their functionality, in terms of fertility, was assumed and not directly tested (Takamura et al., 2002). There are several caveats to these experiments. In *Ciona*, while the germ cells are Vasa positive, other lineages also contain Vasa, some of which were not removed in the tail removal experiment, suggesting that perhaps these lineages may also normally contribute to the germline at later stages of development. Alternatively, these other cells could have been induced in the absence of the B.12 cells to become germ cells. Ablation of the B.12 cells followed by lineage tracing of other lineages may resolve this issue. Therefore, it is intriguing to speculate that both sea urchins and *Ciona* may be organisms like *Parhyale*, that specify their germline early, but can, if forced, induce germ cells later in development. Examination, or in some cases, a re-examination of PGC development in diverse organisms will be required to determine how widespread the phenomenon of having both epigenetic and preformanistic mechanisms is within the metazoans.

Sex specific differentiation in germline-ablated animals

In zebrafish, removal of the PGCs, either by a morpholino to *deadend*, a gene required for PGC migration and differentiation, or by induction of a bacterial toxin, results in sterile adults (Slanchev et al., 2005; Weidinger et al., 2003). Interestingly, all these adults are phenotypically male and display typical male mating behavior. In this case, sex determination can be

modulated by the presence/absence of PGCs. It appears that the PGCs are not required for the initial formation of the somatic gonad, but are required later, when the gonad is differentiating into sex-specific ovaries or testes.

In *Parhyale*, the presence of Vasa-positive germ cells in germline-ablated animals roughly coincides with the first appearance of sexually dimorphic characteristics in juveniles, such as the size difference in the T3 claw. Up until this point, juveniles are indistinguishable. However, germline ablation results phenotypically in both sexes with no significant bias towards one sex versus the other, suggesting that the phenotypic sex characteristics of the animal is determined independent of germ cell replacement. Preliminary data suggests this may be the case. In one of the four-week-old juveniles assayed for Vasa-positive cells, I had classified the animal as phenotypically male, but the structure surrounding the Vasa-positive cells did not appear differentiated as testes, but looked more like an immature ovary.

One hypothesis is that the sexual identity of the gonad and/or the germ cells had not yet been established and that the observed structure simply resembled an ovary, but had none of the molecular characteristics of an ovary, prior to morphological differentiation of the gonad into ovaries or testes. Alternatively, it could be that the somatic gonad does indeed have an ovary-like structure as a “default” state, and that further differentiation into testes requires the PGCs. If the PGCs were similarly required for further gonadal maturation in *Parhyale* as in zebrafish, in which male gonadal differentiation begins with oocyte degradation followed by testes formation (Uchida et al.,

2002), then my findings would be consistent with germ cell replacement occurring prior to sexual differentiation of the gonads. However, it is unclear whether this observation is specific to germline-ablated animals or whether nonablated animals also have a similar state during the normal course of gonadal maturation.

To address these types of questions, we need a clearer understanding of the normal developmental process of gonad maturation in nonablated animals. In addition, we would need to develop a method for permanently removing the germ cells at later stages to characterize subsequent gonadal development in these animals.

Replacement of the germline from a somatic source

The obvious outstanding question is from whence these replacement germ cells arise. In mice, embryonic stem (ES) cells derived from chimeras or *in vitro* can generate both germline and somatic lineages (Geijsen et al., 2004; Hubner et al., 2003; Nayernia et al., 2006; Toyooka et al., 2003), while in adults, there are distinct stem cells devoted to either the germline or soma. In organisms such as *Drosophila*, *C. elegans* and mice, the gametes are produced via germline stem cells (GSC) that are generated from the PGCs. Based on the small number of PGCs that populate the presumptive gonads at the time of hatching, it seems likely that GSCs might also exist in *Parhyale* as well. Direct evidence for this will be needed to determine the role of GSCs in *Parhyale*.

If *Parhyale* has GSCs that are derived from the earlier specified PGCs only, then following ablation of those PGCs, compensation of the germline

must be derived from a somatic cell lineage. At this point, the distinction between soma and germline become muddled. Clearly, in many animals the germline is normally segregated from somatic lineages regardless of which mode of PGC specification is employed. However, once those cells are fated to a somatic or germline existence, they are not thought to be interchangeable. Even in animals capable of regeneration, such as the annelid *Enchytraeus japonensis* and the planarian *Dugesia japonica*, development of regenerated gonads appear to be specifically derived from germline stem cells; however, these germline stem cells are themselves thought to be derived from a multipotent stem cell population (Sato et al., 2006; Tadokoro et al., 2006). In a recent study in mice, researchers claim that the bone marrow may contain a supply of putative germ-like cells that can give rise to oocytes implying that an alternative somatic source for germ cells are present in this animal (Johnson et al., 2005). However, it is unclear if these oocytes can even make functional gametes and be fertilized to make functional offspring. Subsequent studies dispute this finding completely (Eggan et al., 2006; Liu et al., 2007), and heated debate continues around these claims.

In *Parhyale*, it will be interesting to see which of the lineages are able to compensate for the loss of the PGCs, as well as what is the state of differentiation or pluripotency of the compensating cells. Because of the intimate relationship between the somatic gonad and follicle cells surrounding the PGCs, it is plausible that the cells of the mesodermally derived somatic gonad are able to “sense” the loss of the PGCs and initiate the compensatory

response. This response could arise from a pluripotent adult stem cell niche that resides within or near the somatic gonad. Niches are microenvironments that control the process of renewal, proliferation and differentiation of stem cells. In the gonadal niche of *Drosophila*, both germline stem cells (GSC) and somatic stem cells exist in close proximity to one another suggesting they interact to properly maintain the niche (reviewed in Fuller and Spradling, 2007). It will be critical to develop techniques that allow the tracking of PGCs through gonadal maturation and gametogenesis in *Parhyale*. Furthermore, the characterization of stem cells, both somatic and germline, may further our understanding of the molecular underpinnings of epigenesis in *Parhyale*.

Table 4.1 Summary of germline ablation and fertility

(A) Ablation of Mavg or g blastomeres at the four- or eight-cell stage either by photoablation or RNase/DNase ablation (*). (B) Ablation of the progeny of the g blastomere at germband by photoablation. n refers to the number of adults that were fertile compared to the total number of adults present in each trial.

A

ABLATION AT THE FOUR OR EIGHT CELL STAGE

Experimental Trials	Blastomere ablated	% Fertility
1	g	86% (n=6/7)
2	g	67% (n=4/6)
3	g	100% (n=3/3)
4	g	100% (n=14/14)
5	Mavg	88% (n=7/8)
6*	g	86% (n=6/7)
TOTALS		89% (n=40/45)

B

ABLATION AT THE GERMBAND STAGE

Experimental Trials	% Fertility	
1	100% (n=11/11)	
2	100% (n=3/3)	
3	100% (n=3/3)	
TOTALS		100% (n=17/17)

* g ablated by RNAse/DNAse toxicity as an alternative method to photoablation

Figure 4.1 DsRed co-localization with Vasa in the progeny of the g blastomere

(A–D) S19/20 embryo injected with DsRed in g at the eight-cell stage. Stained with anti-formosa (Vasa) antibody. (A) Anti-formosa staining (green). This antibody labels the PGCs. (B) Same individual shown in panel A. DsRed fluorescence (red) is only found in the progeny of g blastomere. (C) Merge of panels A and B showing colocalization of Vasa (green) and DsRed (red). (D) Merge of panel C and DAPI. Arrowhead indicates a dividing cell that has lost the perinuclear Vasa and nuclear DsRed. Scale bar: 20 μm .

Figure 4.2 Exclusion of the ablated cell from the embryo proper

1. (a) Schematic of Mav-DsRed labeled, g FITC-ablated embryo at the eight-cell stage. Skull and crossbones depicts cell being ablated, in these cases, the g-blastomere. Red needle and fill depicts cell labeled with lineage tracer. (b) Live image of S8 embryo with ablated g blastomere and Mav lineage labeled as a control. **2.** (a) Schematic of g-ablation and result. (b) Live fluorescent image with darkfield overlay of dead FITC cell following ablation and (c) at gastrulation. (d) Live darkfield image of granular debris exclusion (arrows) from the embryo at S11 and at (e) S20. Scale bars: 100 μm .

Figure 4.3 Live embryos with loss of morphologically visible PGCs

Schematic and live darkfield images of a (A, B) nonablated embryo with visible germ cell cluster (arrow) and a (C, D) g-ablated embryo at germband stages.

Scale bars: 100 μm .

Figure 4.4 Loss of *vasa* expression in *Mavg* and *g* ablated embryos

vasa expression in nonablated versus ablated S19-21 embryos. Ventral views.

(A–C) Brightfield images. (A'–C') DAPI images. In (A), *vasa* is false-colored

pink. (A, A') Nonablated embryo. *vasa* transcripts are present in the bilateral

germ cell clusters. (B, B') *g*-ablated embryo. (C, C') *Mavg*-ablated embryo. *vasa*

is not present in ablated embryos. Scale bar: 100 μm .

Figure 4.5 Loss of *vasa* protein expression in g-ablated embryos

(A) Lateral and ventral views of nonablated embryo at S20 stained for the anti-formosa (*Vasa*) antibody (black) with corresponding DAPI images. *Vasa* is false colored pink and labels the PGC clusters. (B) Lateral and ventral views a g-ablated embryo at S20 stained for anti-formosa antibody with corresponding DAPI images. Ablated embryos lack *Vasa*-positive cells. Scale bars: 100 μm .

A

B

Figure 4.6 g-blastomere ablations with RNase plus DNase

(A–C) Live fluorescent images with darkfield overlay of RNase+DNase+TRITC g-injected embryos or (D) nonablated TRITC g-injected embryo. (A) Eight-cell stage embryo (S4) following injection. The injected cell begins to lose cellular integrity. (B) Gastrulation stage embryo (S8) and (C) germband stage (S10) embryo injected at the eight-cell stage with RNase+DNase+TRITC. The progression of death in ablated embryos is evident compared to a (D) TRITC g-injected control embryo, which shows the normal pattern for the g lineage at germband stages. Scale bars: 100 μm .

Figure 4.7 Vasa localization in oocytes derived from g-ablated females

Ovaries, from g-ablated embryos raised to adulthood, stained for the anti-formosa (Vasa) antibody (black). (A, B) Brightfield images (A', B') DAPI images with Vasa false colored in pink. (A, A') Ovary from a g-ablated fertile female stained for Vasa in the mature and immature oocytes, similar to what is observed in control, nonablated ovaries (not shown). Scale bar: 100 μm . (B, B') Magnification of box in panels A and A'. Vasa accumulation in oocytes is concentrated around the nucleus. Scale bar: 50 μm .

Figure 4.8 Vasa expression in the gonads of g-ablated animals at S26 and four-weeks post hatching

(A–E, F, H) Brightfield images of juveniles stained for anti-formosa (Vasa) in black (G, I) DAPI images. (A, B) Lateral and dorsal views, respectively, of nonablated S26 embryo stained for Vasa (C) Magnification of Vasa-positive clusters in B. (D, E) Lateral and dorsal views, respectively, of g-ablated S26 embryo lacking Vasa-positive cells. (F) Paired gonads (arrows) removed from a four-week-old juvenile stained for Vasa. (G) Corresponding DAPI image. (H) magnified view of Vasa-positive cells in the gonad. The gonad was dissected away from the surrounding tissue. (I) Corresponding DAPI image. Arrowheads indicate some of the more intensely stained Vasa-positive cells. Scale bars for A, B, D, E: 100 μm . Scale bar for C: 20 μm . Scale bars for F-I: 50 μm .

Figure 4.9 PGC ablation at the germband stage (S14)

(A) Schematic of experimental design and results. The g blastomere is co-injected with FITC dextran (green) and the RNA encoding nuclear DsRed protein (red) at the eight-cell stage, photoablated at germband stage (S14), fixed and stained for anti-formosa at S28. (B) Darkfield image of an ablated embryo at S20. The germ cell cluster (arrow) fails to migrate following ablation. (C) Brightfield image of S28 hatchling stained for Vasa. Vasa is not present in these ablated animals (the head and abdomen were dissected away). (D) Darkfield image of nonablated embryo at S20. The germ cell clusters (arrows) have properly migrated to the lateral sides of the embryo. (E) Brightfield image of S28 nonablated hatchling showing Vasa in the bilateral germ cell clusters. Scale bars: 100 μm .

Conclusions and future directions

In this dissertation, I have described experiments addressing the developmental potential of the early blastomeres in *Parhyale hawaiiensis*. Based on the fate map, one hypothesis is that the blastomeres, at the eight-cell stage, are committed to their fate and that ablation of the blastomere would result in a loss of that lineage. However, I find, using timed ablations, that cell lineage can be uncoupled from cell fate in a restricted manner. While some of the early blastomeres appear to be committed to a particular germ layer at the eight-cell stage, equivalence groups containing three mesoderm- or three ectoderm-generating blastomeres indicate that much regulation occurs within germ layers following ablation. Therefore, ablation does not result in the loss of the fated lineage, but rather is compensated for by cells from their equivalence groups. These results suggest that the early blastomeres are not committed until a later time in development, after gastrulation, when ablated lineages can no longer be compensated.

Within the ectoderm equivalence group, E, the pattern of compensation is predictable, as it is for the mesoderm as well. For example, the ablation of the El blastomere is compensated for by the Ep lineage in the left posterior ectoderm up to the level of maxillae 1 and the Er lineage in the left anterior ectoderm to the level of maxillae 2. These findings suggest that a boundary exists at this level. The 16-cell lineage also shows a similar division between the anterior and posterior daughter blastomeres of El and Er. However, it is

unclear whether this restriction reflects a spatial restriction, or a functional restriction, or both. Using the example ablation above, it is possible that at the 16-cell stage, the anterior daughter of Er (Er-a) compensates for El ablation because it is closest to the ablated cell and can passively occupy that space. This might suggest that Er-a and Er-p are still equivalent. Alternatively, similar to the A–P specification pathway in *C.elegans* (Labouesse and Mango, 1999), Er-a and Er-p could have different potentials at this stage that prevents Er-p from being able to compensate. Then signals from surrounding cells further restrict the compensating cells to the maxillary 1–2 boundary. To address these types of questions, ablations and cell labeling experiments would have to be done, in combination, at the eight and 16-cell stages.

In addition to more experimental manipulations, the addition of molecular markers at the early cleavage and gastrulation stages would greatly advance our understanding of blastomere specification at the molecular level. Due to the high conservation of developmental pathways, one approach is to clone the ortholog of genes known to be involved in a particular process. This approach has already yielded insights to *Parhyale* development. Genes known to be involved in gastrulation and mesodermal patterning in other species, such as *snail* and *twist*, appear to be expressed after gastrulation when the mesoderm is differentiating suggesting a conserved role in mesodermal patterning but not in gastrulation (Price, 2005; Price and Patel, 2007). The fact that they are not expressed at earlier cleavage stages, as one might expect

given the fate map, is consistent with our ablation experiments suggesting that the early blastomeres do not acquire a mesoderm specific fate until after gastrulation. However, they are specified towards a particular blastomere identity at the eight-cell stage, as different developmental potentials exist by this stage. Thus, the characterization of genes involved in germ layer patterning, particularly of the endoderm and ectoderm, will be most informative. For example, the GATA family of transcription factors and the FoxA class of Forkhead genes play key roles in the gene regulatory network leading to the specification of mesendoderm and endoderm in both protostomes and deuterostomes (reviewed in Grapin-Botton and Condamine, 2007; Technau and Scholz, 2003). Based on the fate map in *Parhyale*, the endoderm is derived from one blastomere. Therefore, it will be interesting to see what the spatial and temporal expression of such genes are in this embryo, as well as, if the functions are suggestive of a conserved role in endodermal fates.

Given their roles in multiple processes, another approach is to examine the role of signaling pathways, such as the FGFs, Wnts and TGF- β superfamily members, in *Parhyale*. O'Day (2006) has characterized the role of Notch-Delta signaling in *Parhyale*, yet their expression profiles do not indicate an involvement in the early segregation of blastomere fates (O'Day, 2006). Towards that end, I have cloned β -catenin, a downstream mediator of the Wnt signaling pathway and important cell adhesion protein (Brembeck et al., 2006; Cadigan and Nusse, 1997; Nelson and Nusse, 2004; Wodarz and Nusse, 1998),

and found a novel expression pattern in the putative germ plasm that becomes asymmetrically inherited into the g blastomere and its progeny. Although it is unclear if or what role *β-catenin* plays in germline development, my description of this subcellularly localized RNA suggests that other RNAs will also be similarly localized. A more comprehensive analysis of other putative germline markers would indicate how widespread this phenomenon is. Much work remains to be done to fully characterize the expression and role of *β-catenin*, not only in germ cell development, but also in other developmental contexts such as during gastrulation and segmentation. In Appendix B, I show that *β-catenin* is expressed strongly in the head segments and not the trunk. This finding was unexpected and suggests a divergent role of *β-catenin* during segmentation in *Parhyale*, even more so considering, to date, no Wnts have been found to be expressed during segmentation (Ron Parchem, personal communication). Using a cross-reactive antibody to *β-catenin*, my preliminary experiments show localization at the cell membranes, as expected for a role in cell adhesion, but nuclear localization was not observed. Possible reasons for this may be that the antibody cannot detect nuclear *β-catenin* or there is no nuclear *β-catenin* at this stage. A careful protein expression series with this antibody and a *Parhyale* specific antibody may reveal the different roles of *β-catenin* and direct future functional experiments.

One of the most surprising findings to arise from this work is that the germline can be replaced following ablation of the embryonic primordial germ

cells (PGC). In *Parhyale*, the germline is specified early in embryogenesis by preformation. Ablation of the PGCs results in the loss of germline based on morphology and molecular evidence. Yet, these animals are fertile. This is the first report of germline replacement in an animal that does not regenerate. This finding suggests that in *Parhyale* both preformation and epigenesis mechanisms exist to ensure germline development and the propagation of the species. Future experiments should be aimed towards understanding the mechanism underlying replacement. Some questions to address are which cell type gives rise to the replacement germ cells, which tissues or molecules are important for that interaction, and if or how somatic stem cells might be involved in the process. An in-depth characterization of germline development in nonablated and ablated animals at juvenile to adult stages may reveal the source the replacement germ cells. These types of experiments will require additional molecular markers for germ cells in *Parhyale*. In addition to understanding the epigenetic mechanism of germline replacement, the early specification event requires further attention. Although the protein and RNA expression profiles of *vasa* have been described, previously and in this dissertation, the functional role of *vasa* is unclear. *vasa* morpholinos appear to disrupt or prohibit germ cell development at the morphological level; molecular analyses and fertility tests of the knockdowns remain to be done (Matthias Gerberding, personal communication). Analysis of other genes required for germ cell development will greatly add to our understanding of germ cell specification.

Another question is how widespread the phenomenon of germline replacement is in other amphipod species as well as in other phyla. Based on cleavage patterns and fate maps of a few amphipods, a high degree of similarity may exist within the Amphipoda suggesting that mechanisms of blastomere specification may also be conserved. For example, in *Orchestia*, the germline is also derived from one blastomere from the eight-cell stage (Wolff and Scholtz, 2002). Furthermore, the division to 16-cells, in both *Orchestia* (Wolff and Scholtz, 2002) and *Parhyale* (Extavour, personal communication), segregates the germline into left and right halves, implying another level of specification occurs at the 16-cell stage. In both species, germline specification appears to be cell autonomous. It will be interesting to see if the molecular mechanisms are also conserved in germline specification. One of the first experiments would be to see if the localization of β -catenin to a putative germ plasm is also observed in *Orchestia* and other amphipods. Another experiment is whether ablation of the germline in *Orchestia* also results in fertile adults. If this were the case, it would suggest that the ability to compensate is retained in the lineage leading to the amphipods and that the underlying mechanisms of germline replacement might also be similar. Future studies of blastomere specification and germline specification in *Parhyale* hold much promise for deepening our understanding of these processes.

Appendix B: Expression of β -catenin during segmentation

In Chapter III, I reviewed the role of β -catenin in cell adhesion and in the Wnt signaling pathway. Here, I show the cDNA sequence and translation of the gene (Appendix B.1) and the expression of the mRNA and protein at later stages of development (Appendix B.2, B.3). In addition to the novel early localization of maternal β -catenin to the founder primordial germ cells, zygotic expression of β -catenin is observed during segmentation and appendage formation (Appendix B.2). During segmentation in other arthropods, β -catenin orthologs act as segment polarity genes; it is expressed in the anterior domain of every segment (Dhawan and Gopinathan, 2004; Miyawaki et al., 2004; Riggleman et al., 1989).

In *Parhyale*, I observed a segmental expression pattern of β -catenin during the germband stages suggesting a role in segmentation. However, in sharp contrast to other arthropods, *Parhyale* β -catenin was strongly expressed in the ectoderm of the three anterior most segments, antennal segments 1 and 2, and the mandible; it was not in every segment at germband stages as would be expected if the role of β -catenin were conserved in *Parhyale* (Appendix B.2 A–B'). However, as the appendages began to grow and elaborate, β -catenin was expressed in an anterior stripe of cells within all of the appendages (Appendix B.2 C–E'). It also may be expressed in a subset of neural cells near the midline (data not shown). The expression pattern suggests that the role of β -catenin in segmentation has diverged in *Parhyale*. In an attempt to perturb the function

of β -catenin, I injected the mRNA encoding a dominant-negative version of *Xenopus* β -catenin ($\Delta\beta$ -catenin GFP) in *Parhyale* embryos. This construct lacks a GSK3 binding site required for the degradation of β -catenin. I also injected the *Xenopus* β -catenin-GFP mRNA in an attempt to overexpress the protein. In my experiments, protein was never expressed from either construct in *Parhyale* embryos, although they were functional in *Xenopus* embryos (data not shown). It remains a mystery as to why protein was never made in *Parhyale*. However, since I now have a complete full-length β -catenin clone from *Parhyale*, species-specific overexpression constructs can be generated.

I also examined the localization of β -catenin protein using a commercially available antibody. This antibody detected the cell membrane localization of β -catenin, however, no nuclear staining was detected (Appendix B.3). In *Drosophila*, nuclear localization of β -catenin is also not observed, although, it presumably enters the nucleus to elicit its effect (Riggleman et al., 1990). This pattern does not correlate with the *in situ* pattern described above. One might expect to see a higher level of expression of the protein in the three anterior segments. The presence of protein in all cell membranes further suggests that at least a low level of transcript should also be present in all cells. This may be the case; and uniform low level of transcripts may not be as apparent in my *in situs*, especially in light of the more intense specific staining in the segments and limbs. A more in-depth characterization with this antibody is required to fully address whether this discrepancy is due to technical or biological causes.

Materials and Methods

In situ hybridization and Immunohistochemistry

In situ hybridization was performed as described in Chapter III.

Immunohistochemistry was performed as described in Chapter II. Primary concentration of rabbit-anti- β -catenin antibody (Sigma C2206) was used at 1:250. Secondary goat-anti-rabbit AlexaFluor-488 was used at 1:600.

Constructs

The *Xenopus* β -catenin-GFP (XE69) and dominant-negative β -catenin-GFP ($\Delta\beta$ -catenin GFP) (XE85) constructs were kindly provided by the Harland lab.

The Ambion SP6 mMessageMachine kit was used to synthesize the capped mRNA for injection.

Figure B.2 *β-catenin* expression at the germband and appendage stages

(A–E) Brightfield images of *β-catenin in situ* hybridizations. (A'–E')

Corresponding DAPI images with false-color overlay or fluorescent overlay. In all panels except (B, B') *β-catenin* is in purple; in (B, B') *β-catenin* is in red. (A, A') S14/15 embryo showing transcripts in a single row of cells in the three anterior-most segments, A1, A2, and mandible. (B, B') S17/18 embryo stained with *β-catenin*. *β-catenin* is expressed only in the anterior portion of the three anterior segments, although segmentation is nearly complete. (C, C') S21 embryo. *β-catenin* is now in the anterior portion in all of developing appendages. (D, D') S22 embryo. Note: although the expression looks posterior, the antennal segments will flip in the opposite (dorsal) direction once the head has developed. (E, E') close up of anterior expression of *β-catenin* in the appendages. Scale bar: 100 μm.

Figure B.3 Localization of β -catenin in the cell membranes

Confocal stack of S14 embryo stained for β -catenin (green) and DAPI (blue).

(A) β -catenin (green) labels the cell membranes, but does not appear to accumulate in the nuclei. (B) Corresponding DAPI (blue). (C) Merge of A and B.

Appendix C: Cloning and Antibody production of the *Parhyale* ortholog of PAR-6

Cell polarity is a key aspect of generating cellular diversity, in part by localizing cytoplasmic determinants that affect cell fates, as well as being crucial for processes involving cell migration and morphogenesis. The Partitioning defective (PAR) genes appear to be involved in a conserved mechanism for establishing cell polarity in a variety of cellular contexts in both protostomes and deuterostomes (reviewed in Doe, 2001; Ohno, 2001). The PAR proteins are used for establishing early embryonic polarity in *Caenorhabditis elegans*, *Drosophila melanogaster*, and perhaps *Xenopus laevis*, as well as cell polarity in other cellular contexts among metazoans. For example, in *C. elegans*, several of the PAR proteins are asymmetrically expressed in distinct anterior–posterior domains at the one-cell stage. In particular, PAR-6 is asymmetrically expressed in the cortex of the anterior portion of the one-cell zygote and expression continues in the cell periphery of particular cell lineages (Hung and Kemphues, 1999). PAR-6 is a PDZ domain containing protein primarily involved in protein-protein interactions with a conserved cassette of proteins. As a starting point for understanding how embryonic polarity and cellular asymmetries are established in *Parhyale*, I attempted to characterize the expression of PAR-6. I successfully amplified the full-length cDNA from degenerate PCR and standard RACE protocols (Figure C.1). I made several antisense riboprobes to PAR-6 and performed *in situ*

hybridizations. However, I never observed any staining with these probes—ubiquitous or specific.

For antibody production, I cloned the full-length coding sequence into three different expression constructs: pGEX-4T-1 (GST tag), pQE32 (HIS tag) and Path10 (TrpE tag). Of these constructs only the PAR-6-GST and PAR-6-TrpE fusions expressed protein in sufficient quantities to send to Covance, where the antibodies were being produced. For each protein, three rats were injected. The anti-sera from of all three rats for both fusion constructs were able to detect protein by western blot analysis. I then began testing the different anti-serum batches for reactivity on *Parhyale* embryos. Initial testing of all three anti-sera from PAR-6-TrpE test bleed two yielded promising results in early cleavage through late gastrulation-staged embryos. In these embryos, it appeared that PAR-6 was staining the cell membrane of a subset of cells (data not shown). Unfortunately, I was not able to obtain repeatable results with this batch or subsequent batches of anti-sera. To reduce background, I affinity purified the PAR6-TrpE sera against bacterial lysates. The resulting anti-sera did not work on *Parhyale* embryos. To follow up on this project, retesting the test bleed by western blot on bacterial and *Parhyale* extracts should first be done. Depending on the outcome of those experiments, a systematic antibody screen of the different anti-sera should be performed on embryos of all stages, in particular during gastrulation and neurogenesis, as localization of PAR-6 has been reported in other systems at these stages.

Materials and Methods

Cloning of *Parhyale* PAR-6

The following degenerate primers were used to amplify a fragment of *Parhyale* PAR-6: F1 GTSAARWSSAARTTYGRBG; F2 TGCCVMTYAMCAAYGAYG; R1 CKCTCRTTGGCVGGYYTGAC; R2 TTSGCVAYCATCATRTRCVG. Total RNA was isolated from S1-S21 *Parhyale* embryos using Trizol Reagent (Gibco). First strand cDNA synthesis was carried out on the RNA using the Superscript™ III First-Strand kit (Invitrogen) per manufacturers instructions. 5' and 3' RACE (Generacer) (Frohman, 1993) were then performed to obtain the complete cDNA sequence. Sequences were assembled in Sequencher (Genecodes) or MacVector 7.2 (Accelrys Inc.) for further analysis.

Bacterial expression of PAR-6-fusion constructs

For the path (TrpE) expression system (Koerner et al., 1991), bacterial expression and purification were performed according to Patel et al. (1992). For the GST gene fusion system, protein was isolated following standard manufacturer protocols (Amersham Biosciences). Affinity purification of *Parhyale* PAR-6-TrpE was performed using bacterial lysates to reduce background (Patel et al., 1992).

Antibody production

Approximately 0.8 mg/ml of protein was sent to Covance Research Products (Denver, PA) for the initial injection (3 rats), and 0.4 mg/ml for five and seven boosts. Rats 2590, 2591, and 2592 were injected with PAR-6-TrpE. Rats 2621, 2622, and 2623 were injected with PAR-6-GST. All bleeds are currently stored at -80°C.

Immunohistochemistry

Antibody staining was performed as described in Chapter II with the following exceptions: embryos were dissected for 5 minutes in 3.7% formaldehyde in seawater, then transferred and fixed in 3.7% formaldehyde in PEM for 15 minutes. Embryos were then dehydrated in 100% methanol for one-two hours prior to rehydration and continuation of the standard protocol. Primary concentrations used were 1:250-1:300.

Appendix D: Accession Numbers

Table D.1 NCBI accession numbers for Vasa and β -catenin amino acid sequences used for alignments and phylogenetic analyses

Vasa

SPECIES	ACCESSION NUMBER
<i>Daphnia magna</i> (water flea)	BAD99522
<i>Moina macrocopa</i> (water flea),	BAD99524
<i>Artemia franciscana</i> (brine shrimp)	BAD99523
<i>Litopenaeus vannamei</i> (Pacific white shrimp)	AAV89069
<i>Drosophila melanogaster</i> (fruit fly)	P09052
<i>Apis mellifera</i> (honey bee)	NP001035345
<i>Schistocerca gregaria</i> (grasshopper)	AAO15914
<i>Tribolium castaneum</i> (red flour beetle)	NP001034520
<i>Bombyx mori</i> (silkworm moth)	BAA19572
<i>Copidosoma floridanum</i> (parasitic wasp)	AAT12450
<i>Crassostrea gigas</i> (oyster)	AAR34337
<i>Platynereis dumerilli</i> (annelid)	CAJ15139
<i>Tubifex tubifex</i> (oligochaete annelid)	BAE93269
<i>Botrylloides violaceus</i> (colonial ascidian)	ABM74410
<i>Ciona savignii</i> (sea squirt)	BAB12216
<i>Mus musculus</i> (mouse)	Q61496
<i>Xenopus laevis</i> (frog)	AAC03114
<i>Nematostella vectensis</i> (sea anemone) Vasa1	AAW29703
<i>Nematostella vectensis</i> (sea anemone) Vasa2	AAW29074

PL10

<i>Platynereis dumerilli</i> PL10a (annelid)	CAJ15140
<i>Crepidula fornicata</i> (mollusc)	ABD59346
<i>Xenopus laevis</i> (frog)	NP001080283
<i>Mus musculus</i> (mouse)	NP149068
<i>Nematostella vectensis</i> (sea anemone)	AAW29072
<i>Ephydatia fluviatilis</i> (sponge)	BAB13309
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> (yeast)	NP015206

p68 , p62, and elf-1alpha

<i>Tubifex tubifex</i> (annelid) p68	BAD90013
<i>Molgula oculata</i> (ascidian) p68	AAD38874
<i>Drosophila melanogaster</i> (fruit fly) p62	P19109
<i>Xenopus laevis</i> (frog) p68	NP001084230
<i>Mus musculus</i> (mouse) p68	CAA46581
<i>Homo sapiens</i> (human) p68	AAB84094
<i>Schizosaccharomyces pombe</i> (yeast)	AAA35319
<i>Drosophila melanogaster</i> (fruit fly) elF-4A	Q02748
<i>Mus musculus</i> (mouse) elF-4A	P60843
<i>Schizosaccharomyces pombe</i> (yeast) elF-4A	CAA56772

β -catenin

<i>Drosophila melanogaster</i> (fruit fly)	P18824
<i>Schistocerca americana</i> (grasshopper)	AAL49501
<i>Anopheles gambiae</i> (African malaria mosquito)	Q7QHW5
<i>Aedes aegypti</i> (yellow fever mosquito)	EAT45858
<i>Gryllus bimaculatus</i> (cricket)	BAD00045
<i>Achaearanea tepidariorum</i> (spider)	BAC87840
<i>Chaetopterus variopedatus</i> (annelid)	AAL49497
<i>Platynereis dumerilii</i> (annelid)	ABQ85061
<i>Aplysia californica</i> (mollusc)	AAZ29569
<i>Amphioxus floridae</i> (lancelet)	AAZ34439
<i>Strongylocentrotus purpuratus</i> (sea urchin)	XP_001175634
<i>Ciona intestinalis</i> (ascidian)	BAE06330
<i>Xenopus laevis</i> (frog)	NP_001084045
<i>Danio rerio</i> (zebrafish)	AAC59732
<i>Mus musculus</i> (mouse)	AAA37280
<i>Homo sapiens</i> (human)	CAA61107
<i>Hydra vulgaris</i> (cnidarian)	AAQ02885
<i>Hydra magnipapillata</i> (cnidarian)	AAC47137

Plakoglobins

<i>Xenopus laevis</i> (frog)	M95593
<i>Danio rerio</i> (zebrafish)	AF099738
<i>Mus musculus</i> (mouse)	M90365
<i>Homo sapiens</i> (human)	Z68228

Bibliography

Aberle, H., Schwartz, H., Hoschuetzky, H. and Kemler, R. (1996).

Single amino acid substitutions in proteins of the armadillo gene family abolish their binding to α -catenin. *J Biol Chem* **271**, 1520-6.

Aflalo, E. D., Bakhrat, A., Raviv, S., Harari, D., Sagi, A. and Abdu, U.

(2007). Characterization of a *vasa-like* gene from the pacific white shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* and its expression during oogenesis. *Mol Reprod Dev* **74**, 172-7.

Aguinaldo, A. M., Turbeville, J. M., Linford, L. S., Rivera, M. C.,

Garey, J. R., Raff, R. A. and Lake, J. A. (1997). Evidence for a clade of nematodes, arthropods and other moulting animals. *Nature* **387**, 489-93.

Angerer, L. M. and Angerer, R. C. (2000). Animal-vegetal axis patterning mechanisms in the early sea urchin embryo. *Dev Biol* **218**, 1-12.

Astrow, S., Holton, B. and Weisblat, D. (1987). Centrifugation

redistributes factors determining cleavage patterns in leech embryos. *Dev Biol* **120**, 270-83.

Barnard, J. L. (1965). Marine Amphipoda of atolls in Micronesia.

Proceedings of the United States National Museum **117**, 459-551.

Bashirullah, A., Halsell, S. R., Cooperstock, R. L., Kloc, M.,

Karaiskakis, A., Fisher, W. W., Fu, W., Hamilton, J. K., Etkin, L. D.

and Lipshitz, H. D. (1999). Joint action of two RNA degradation pathways

controls the timing of maternal transcript elimination at the midblastula transition in *Drosophila melanogaster*. *Embo J* **18**, 2610-20.

Beck, A. R., Miller, I. J., Anderson, P. and Streuli, M. (1998). RNA-binding protein TIAR is essential for primordial germ cell development. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **95**, 2331-6.

Bellipanni, G., Varga, M., Maegawa, S., Imai, Y., Kelly, C., Myers, A. P., Chu, F., Talbot, W. S. and Weinberg, E. S. (2006). Essential and opposing roles of zebrafish β -catenins in the formation of dorsal axial structures and neurectoderm. *Development* **133**, 1299-309.

Boterenbrood, E. C. and Nieuwkoop, P. D. (1973). The formation of the mesoderm in urodelian amphibians. V. Its regional induction by the endoderm. *Wilhem Roux' Arch.* **173**, 319-332.

Bounoure, L. (1934). Recherches sur la lignée germinale chez la grenouille rousée aux premiers stades du développement. *Annls Sci. Nat. (Ser 10) A* **17**, 67-248.

Braat, A. K., van de Water, S., Goos, H., Bogerd, J. and Zivkovic, D. (2000). Vasa protein expression and localization in the zebrafish. *Mech Dev* **95**, 271-4.

Braat, A. K., van de Water, S., Korving, J. and Zivkovic, D. (2001). A zebrafish *vasa* morphant abolishes *vasa* protein but does not affect the establishment of the germline. *Genesis* **30**, 183-5.

- Braat, A. K., Zandbergen, T., van de Water, S., Goos, H. J. and Zivkovic, D.** (1999). Characterization of zebrafish primordial germ cells: morphology and early distribution of *vasa* RNA. *Dev Dyn* **216**, 153-67.
- Brembeck, F. H., Rosario, M. and Birchmeier, W.** (2006). Balancing cell adhesion and Wnt signaling, the key role of β -catenin. *Curr Opin Genet Dev* **16**, 51-9.
- Browne, W. E., Price, A. L., Gerberding, M. and Patel, N. H.** (2005). Stages of embryonic development in the amphipod crustacean, *Parhyale hawaiiensis*. *Genesis* **42**, 124-49.
- Browne, W. E., Schmid, B. G., Wimmer, E. A. and Martindale, M. Q.** (2006). Expression of otd orthologs in the amphipod crustacean, *Parhyale hawaiiensis*. *Dev Genes Evol* **216**, 581-95.
- Brusca, R. C. and Brusca, G. J.** (2003). Invertebrates. Sunderland: Sinauer Associates, Inc., Publishers.
- Buehr, M. L. and Blackler, A. W.** (1970). Sterility and partial sterility in the South African clawed toad following the pricking of the egg. *J Embryol Exp Morphol* **23**, 375-84.
- Cadigan, K. M. and Nusse, R.** (1997). Wnt signaling: a common theme in animal development. *Genes Dev* **11**, 3286-305.
- Chang, C. C., Dearden, P. and Akam, M.** (2002). Germ line development in the grasshopper *Schistocerca gregaria*: *vasa* as a marker. *Dev Biol* **252**, 100-18.

- Chang, T. H., Latus, L. J., Liu, Z. and Abbott, J. M.** (1997). Genetic interactions of conserved regions in the DEAD-box protein Prp28p. *Nucleic Acids Res* **25**, 5033-40.
- Chiquoine, A. D.** (1954). The identification, origin, and migration of the primordial germ cells in the mouse embryo. *Anat. Rec.* **2**, 135-146.
- Conklin, E. G.** (1905). The organization and cell lineage of the ascidian egg. *J. Acad. Nat. Sci. (Philadelphia)* **13**, 1-119.
- Cordin, O., Banroques, J., Tanner, N. K. and Linder, P.** (2006). The DEAD-box protein family of RNA helicases. *Gene* **367**, 17-37.
- Cordin, O., Tanner, N. K., Doere, M., Linder, P. and Banroques, J.** (2004). The newly discovered Q motif of DEAD-box RNA helicases regulates RNA-binding and helicase activity. *Embo J* **23**, 2478-87.
- Cox, R. T., Kirkpatrick, C. and Peifer, M.** (1996). Armadillo is required for adherens junction assembly, cell polarity, and morphogenesis during *Drosophila* embryogenesis. *J Cell Biol* **134**, 133-48.
- Cox, R. T., Pai, L. M., Kirkpatrick, C., Stein, J. and Peifer, M.** (1999). Roles of the C terminus of Armadillo in *Wingless* signaling in *Drosophila*. *Genetics* **153**, 319-32.
- Davidson, E. H.** (1991). Spatial mechanisms of gene regulation in metazoan embryos. *Development* **113**, 1-26.
- Davidson, E. H., Cameron, R. A. and Ransick, A.** (1998). Specification of cell fate in the sea urchin embryo: summary and some proposed mechanisms. *Development* **125**, 3269-90.

- DeMarais, A. A. and Moon, R. T.** (1992). The *armadillo* homologs β -catenin and plakoglobin are differentially expressed during early development of *Xenopus laevis*. *Dev Biol* **153**, 337-46.
- Dhawan, S. and Gopinathan, K. P.** (2004). Molecular cloning and expression pattern of an *armadillo* homologue from the mulberry silkworm *Bombyx mori*. *Gene Expr Patterns* **4**, 15-23.
- Dictus, W. J. and Damen, P.** (1997). Cell-lineage and clonal-contribution map of the trochophore larva of *Patella vulgata* (mollusca). *Mech Dev* **62**, 213-26.
- Doe, C. Q.** (2001). Cell polarity: the PARty expands. *Nat Cell Biol* **3**, E7-9.
- Donnell, D. M., Corley, L. S., Chen, G. and Strand, M. R.** (2004). Caste determination in a polyembryonic wasp involves inheritance of germ cells. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **101**, 10095-100.
- Draper, B. W., McCallum, C. M. and Moens, C. B.** (2007). *nanos1* is required to maintain oocyte production in adult zebrafish. *Dev Biol* **305**, 589-98.
- Duman-Scheel, M., Pirkl, N. and Patel, N. H.** (2002). Analysis of the expression pattern of *Mysidium columbiae wingless* provides evidence for conserved mesodermal and retinal patterning processes among insects and crustaceans. *Dev Genes Evol* **212**, 114-23.
- Eddy, E. M.** (1975). Germ plasm and the differentiation of the germ cell line. *Int Rev Cytol* **43**, 229-80.

- Eggan, K., Jurga, S., Gosden, R., Min, I. M. and Wagers, A. J.** (2006). Ovulated oocytes in adult mice derive from non-circulating germ cells. *Nature* **441**, 1109-14.
- Eisenmann, D. M., Maloof, J. N., Simske, J. S., Kenyon, C. and Kim, S. K.** (1998). The β -catenin homolog BAR-1 and LET-60 Ras coordinately regulate the Hox gene *lin-39* during *Caenorhabditis elegans* vulval development. *Development* **125**, 3667-80.
- Everett, N. B.** (1943). Observational and experimental evidences relating to the origin and differentiation of the definitive germ cells in mice. *J Exp Zool* **92**, 49-91.
- Extavour, C. G.** (2005). The fate of isolated blastomeres with respect to germ cell formation in the amphipod crustacean *Parhyale hawaiiensis*. *Dev Biol* **277**, 387-402.
- Extavour, C. G. and Akam, M.** (2003). Mechanisms of germ cell specification across the metazoans: epigenesis and preformation. *Development* **130**, 5869-84.
- Extavour, C. G., Pang, K., Matus, D. Q. and Martindale, M. Q.** (2005). *vasa* and *nanos* expression patterns in a sea anemone and the evolution of bilaterian germ cell specification mechanisms. *Evol Dev* **7**, 201-15.
- Fabioux, C., Huvet, A., Lelong, C., Robert, R., Pouvreau, S., Daniel, J. Y., Minguant, C. and Le Pennec, M.** (2004). Oyster *vasa-like* gene as a marker of the germline cell development in *Crassostrea gigas*. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun* **320**, 592-8.

- Fagotto, F. and Gumbiner, B. M.** (1994). β -catenin localization during *Xenopus* embryogenesis: accumulation at tissue and somite boundaries. *Development* **120**, 3667-79.
- Felix, M. A. and Barriere, A.** (2005). Evolvability of cell specification mechanisms. *J Exp Zool B Mol Dev Evol* **304**, 536-47.
- Felsenstein, J.** (1985). Confidence limits on phylogenies—an approach using the bootstrap. *Evolution* **39**, 783-791.
- Freeman, G. and Lundelius, J.** (1992). Evolutionary implications of the mode of D quadrant specification in coelomates with spiral cleavage. *J Evol Biol* **5**, 205-247.
- Frohman, M. A.** (1993). Rapid amplification of complementary DNA ends for generation of full-length complementary DNAs: thermal RACE. *Methods Enzymol* **218**, 340-56.
- Fujimura, M. and Takamura, K.** (2000). Characterization of an ascidian DEAD-box gene, *Ci-DEAD1*: specific expression in the germ cells and its mRNA localization in the posterior-most blastomeres in early embryos. *Dev Genes Evol* **210**, 64-72.
- Fujiwara, Y., Komiya, T., Kawabata, H., Sato, M., Fujimoto, H., Furusawa, M. and Noce, T.** (1994). Isolation of a DEAD-family protein gene that encodes a murine homolog of *Drosophila vasa* and its specific expression in germ cell lineage. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **91**, 12258-62.
- Fuller, M. T. and Spradling, A. C.** (2007). Male and female *Drosophila* germline stem cells: two versions of immortality. *Science* **316**, 402-4.

- Gavis, E. R. and Lehmann, R.** (1992). Localization of *nanos* RNA controls embryonic polarity. *Cell* **71**, 301-13.
- Geigy, R.** (1931). Action de l'ultra-violet sur le pole germinale dans l'oeuf de *Drosophila melanogaster*. *Rév. Suisse Zool.* **32**, 187-288.
- Geijsen, N., Horoschak, M., Kim, K., Gribnau, J., Eggan, K. and Daley, G. Q.** (2004). Derivation of embryonic germ cells and male gametes from embryonic stem cells. *Nature* **427**, 148-54.
- Gerberding, M., Browne, W. E. and Patel, N. H.** (2002). Cell lineage analysis of the amphipod crustacean *Parhyale hawaiensis* reveals an early restriction of cell fates. *Development* **129**, 5789-801.
- Gilbert, S.** (1997). *Developmental biology*. Sunderland, Mass.: Sinauer Associates.
- Giorgianni, M. W. and Patel, N. H.** (2004). Patterning of the branched head appendages in *Schistocerca americana* and *Tribolium castaneum*. *Evol Dev* **6**, 402-10.
- Goldstein, B.** (1992). Induction of gut in *Caenorhabditis elegans* embryos. *Nature* **357**, 255-7.
- Goldstein, B.** (1995). An analysis of the response to gut induction in the *C. elegans* embryo. *Development* **121**, 1227-36.
- Goldstein, B., Frisse, L. M. and Thomas, W. K.** (1998). Embryonic axis specification in nematodes: evolution of the first step in development. *Curr Biol* **8**, 157-60.

- Govind, S. and Steward, R.** (1991). Dorsoventral pattern formation in *Drosophila*: signal transduction and nuclear targeting. *Trends Genet* **7**, 119-25.
- Grapin-Botton, A. and Constam, D.** (2007). Evolution of the mechanisms and molecular control of endoderm formation. *Mech Dev* **124**, 253-78.
- Green, J.** (1971). Crustaceans. In *Experimental embryology of marine and freshwater invertebrates*, (ed. G. Reverberi), pp. 312-362. Amsterdam: North-Holland Publishing Co.
- Grill, S. W., Gonczy, P., Stelzer, E. H. and Hyman, A. A.** (2001). Polarity controls forces governing asymmetric spindle positioning in the *Caenorhabditis elegans* embryo. *Nature* **409**, 630-3.
- Gruidl, M. E., Smith, P. A., Kuznicki, K. A., McCrone, J. S., Kirchner, J., Roussell, D. L., Strome, S. and Bennett, K. L.** (1996). Multiple potential germ-line helicases are components of the germ-line-specific P granules of *Caenorhabditis elegans*. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **93**, 13837-42.
- Grunert, S. and St Johnston, D.** (1996). RNA localization and the development of asymmetry during *Drosophila* oogenesis. *Curr Opin Genet Dev* **6**, 395-402.
- Gumbiner, B. M.** (2000). Regulation of cadherin adhesive activity. *J Cell Biol* **148**, 399-404.
- Haegel, H., Larue, L., Ohsugi, M., Fedorov, L., Herrenknecht, K. and Kemler, R.** (1995). Lack of β -catenin affects mouse development at gastrulation. *Development* **121**, 3529-37.

- Harrison, R. G.** (1933). Some difficulties of the determination problem. *American Naturalist*, 306-321.
- Hayashi, K., de Sousa Lopes, S. M. and Surani, M. A.** (2007). Germ cell specification in mice. *Science* **316**, 394-6.
- Hecht, A., Litterst, C. M., Huber, O. and Kemler, R.** (1999). Functional characterization of multiple transactivating elements in β -catenin, some of which interact with the TATA-binding protein in vitro. *J Biol Chem* **274**, 18017-25.
- Henry, J.** (2002). Conserved mechanism of dorsoventral axis determination in equal-cleaving spiralian. *Dev Biol* **248**, 343-55.
- Herpin, A., Rohr, S., Riedel, D., Kluever, N., Raz, E. and Schartl, M.** (2007). Specification of primordial germ cells in medaka (*Oryzias latipes*). *BMC Dev Biol* **7**, 3.
- Hertzler, P. and Clark, W.** (1992). Cleavage and gastrulation in the shrimp *Sicyonia ingentis*: invagination is accompanied by oriented cell division. *Development* **116**, 127-40.
- Hertzler, P. L., Wang, S. W. and Clark, W. H., Jr.** (1994). Mesendoderm cell and archenteron formation in isolated blastomeres from the shrimp *Sicyonia ingentis*. *Dev Biol* **164**, 333-44.
- Hibino, T., Nishikata, T. and Nishida, H.** (1998). Centrosome-attracting body: a novel structure closely related to unequal cleavages in the ascidian embryo. *Dev Growth Differ* **40**, 85-95.

- Holwill, S., Heasman, J., Crawley, C. R. and Wylie, C.** (1987). Axis and germ line deficiencies caused by u.v. irradiation of *Xenopus* oocytes cultured *in vitro*. *Development* **100**, 735-743.
- Horvay, K., Claussen, M., Katzer, M., Landgrebe, J. and Pieler, T.** (2006). *Xenopus Dead end* mRNA is a localized maternal determinant that serves a conserved function in germ cell development. *Dev Biol* **291**, 1-11.
- Horvitz, H. R. and Herskowitz, I.** (1992). Mechanisms of asymmetric cell division: two Bs or not two Bs, that is the question. *Cell* **68**, 237-55.
- Huber, A. H., Nelson, W. J. and Weis, W. I.** (1997). Three-dimensional structure of the armadillo repeat region of β -catenin. *Cell* **90**, 871-82.
- Hubner, K., Fuhrmann, G., Christenson, L. K., Kehler, J., Reinbold, R., De La Fuente, R., Wood, J., Strauss, J. F., 3rd, Boiani, M. and Scholer, H. R.** (2003). Derivation of oocytes from mouse embryonic stem cells. *Science* **300**, 1251-6.
- Huelsenbeck, J. P. and Ronquist, F.** (2001). MRBAYES: Bayesian inference of phylogenetic trees. *Bioinformatics* **17**, 754-755.
- Humphrey, R. R.** (1929). The early position of the primordial germ cells in urodeles: evidence from experimental studies. *Anat. Rec.* **42**, 301-314.
- Hung, T. J. and Kemphues, K. J.** (1999). PAR-6 is a conserved PDZ domain-containing protein that colocalizes with PAR-3 in *Caenorhabditis elegans* embryos. *Development* **126**, 127-35.
- Hyman, L.** (1955). *The Invertebrates: Echinodermata*. New York: McGraw-Hill.

- Ikenishi, K. and Nieuwkoop, P. D.** (1978). Location and ultrastructure of primordial germ cells (PGCs) in *Ambystoma mexicanum*. *Dev Growth Differ.* **20**, 1-9.
- Illmensee, K. and Mahowald, A. P.** (1974). Transplantation of posterior polar plasm in *Drosophila*. Induction of germ cells at the anterior pole of the egg. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **71**, 1016-20.
- Imai, K., Takada, N., Satoh, N. and Satou, Y.** (2000). β -catenin mediates the specification of endoderm cells in ascidian embryos. *Development* **127**, 3009-20.
- Iseto, T. and Nishida, H.** (1999). Ultrastructural studies on the centrosome-attracting body: electron-dense matrix and its role in unequal cleavages in ascidian embryos. *Dev Growth Differ* **41**, 601-9.
- Jamora, C. and Fuchs, E.** (2002). Intercellular adhesion, signalling and the cytoskeleton. *Nat Cell Biol* **4**, E101-8.
- Johnson, A. D., Bachvarova, R. F., Drum, M. and Masi, T.** (2001). Expression of axolotl *DAZL* RNA, a marker of germ plasm: widespread maternal RNA and onset of expression in germ cells approaching the gonad. *Dev Biol* **234**, 402-415.
- Johnson, A. D., Crother, B., White, M. E., Patient, R., Bachvarova, R. F., Drum, M. and Masi, T.** (2003). Regulative germ cell specification in axolotl embryos: a primitive trait conserved in the mammalian lineage. *Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci* **358**, 1371-9.

Johnson, J., Bagley, J., Skaznik-Wikiel, M., Lee, H. J., Adams, G. B., Niikura, Y., Tschudy, K. S., Tilly, J. C., Cortes, M. L., Forkert, R. et al. (2005). Oocyte generation in adult mammalian ovaries by putative germ cells in bone marrow and peripheral blood. *Cell* **122**, 303-15.

Juliano, C. E., Voronina, E., Stack, C., Aldrich, M., Cameron, A. R. and Wessel, G. M. (2006). Germ line determinants are not localized early in sea urchin development, but do accumulate in the small micromere lineage. *Dev Biol* **300**, 406-15.

Kawasaki, I., Amiri, A., Fan, Y., Meyer, N., Dunkelbarger, S., Motohashi, T., Karashima, T., Bossinger, O. and Strome, S. (2004). The PGL family proteins associate with germ granules and function redundantly in *Caenorhabditis elegans* germline development. *Genetics* **167**, 645-61.

Kawasaki, I., Shim, Y. H., Kirchner, J., Kaminker, J., Wood, W. B. and Strome, S. (1998). PGL-1, a predicted RNA-binding component of germ granules, is essential for fertility in *C. elegans*. *Cell* **94**, 635-45.

Kemler, R. (1993). From cadherins to catenins: cytoplasmic protein interactions and regulation of cell adhesion. *Trends Genet* **9**, 317-21.

Kimble, J. E. (1981). Strategies for control of pattern formation in *Caenorhabditis elegans*. *Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci* **295**, 539-51.

Kimelman, D. and Schier, A. F. (2002). Mesoderm induction and patterning. *Results Probl Cell Differ* **40**, 15-27.

- Kingsley, E. P., Chan, X. Y., Duan, Y. and Lambert, J. D.** (2007). Widespread RNA segregation in a spiralian embryo. *Evol Dev* **9**, 527-39.
- Kloc, M., Bilinski, S., Chan, A. P., Allen, L. H., Zearfoss, N. R. and Etkin, L. D.** (2001). RNA localization and germ cell determination in *Xenopus*. *Int Rev Cytol* **203**, 63-91.
- Knaut, H., Pelegri, F., Bohmann, K., Schwarz, H. and Nusslein-Volhard, C.** (2000). Zebrafish *vasa* RNA but not its protein is a component of the germ plasm and segregates asymmetrically before germline specification. *J Cell Biol* **149**, 875-88.
- Kobayashi, K., Sawada, K., Yamamoto, H., Wada, S., Saiga, H. and Nishida, H.** (2003). Maternal *macho-1* is an intrinsic factor that makes cell response to the same FGF signal differ between mesenchyme and notochord induction in ascidian embryos. *Development* **130**, 5179-90.
- Koerner, T. J., Hill, J. E., Myers, A. M. and Tzagoloff, A.** (1991). High-expression vectors with multiple cloning sites for construction of trpE fusion genes: pATH vectors. *Methods Enzymol* **194**, 477-90.
- Köprunner, M., Thisse, C., Thisse, B. and Raz, E.** (2001). A zebrafish *nanos-related* gene is essential for the development of primordial germ cells. *Genes Dev* **15**, 2877-85.
- Korswagen, H. C., Herman, M. A. and Clevers, H. C.** (2000). Distinct β -catenins mediate adhesion and signalling functions in *C. elegans*. *Nature* **406**, 527-32.

Kourakis, M. J. and Smith, W. C. (2005). Did the first chordates organize without the organizer? *Trends Genet* **21**, 506-10.

Kuznicki, K. A., Smith, P. A., Leung-Chiu, W. M., Estevez, A. O., Scott, H. C. and Bennett, K. L. (2000). Combinatorial RNA interference indicates GLH-4 can compensate for GLH-1; these two P granule components are critical for fertility in *C. elegans*. *Development* **127**, 2907-16.

Labbe, J. C., McCarthy, E. K. and Goldstein, B. (2004). The forces that position a mitotic spindle asymmetrically are tethered until after the time of spindle assembly. *J Cell Biol* **167**, 245-56.

Labouesse, M. and Mango, S. E. (1999). Patterning the *C. elegans* embryo: moving beyond the cell lineage. *Trends Genet* **15**, 307-13.

Lambert, J. D. (2007). Mesoderm in spiralian: the organizer and the 4d cell. *J Exp Zool B Mol Dev Evol.* **310(1)**, 15-23.

Lambert, J. D. and Nagy, L. M. (2002). Asymmetric inheritance of centrosomally localized mRNAs during embryonic cleavages. *Nature* **420**, 682-6.

Larabell, C. A., Torres, M., Rowning, B. A., Yost, C., Miller, J. R., Wu, M., Kimelman, D. and Moon, R. T. (1997). Establishment of the dorso-ventral axis in *Xenopus* embryos is presaged by early asymmetries in β -catenin that are modulated by the Wnt signaling pathway. *J Cell Biol* **136**, 1123-36.

Lawrence, P. A. and Levine, M. (2006). Mosaic and regulative development: two faces of one coin. *Curr Biol* **16**, R236-9.

- Lawson, K. A. and Hage, W. J.** (1994). Clonal analysis of the origin of primordial germ cells in the mouse. *Ciba Found Symp* **182**, 68-84; discussion 84-91.
- Lilien, J., Balsamo, J., Arregui, C. and Xu, G.** (2002). Turn-off, drop-out: functional state switching of cadherins. *Dev Dyn* **224**, 18-29.
- Lin, S., Long, W., Chen, J. and Hopkins, N.** (1992). Production of germline chimeras in zebrafish by cell transplants from genetically pigmented to albino embryos. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **89**, 4519-23.
- Linder, P.** (2006). Dead-box proteins: a family affair--active and passive players in RNP-remodeling. *Nucleic Acids Res* **34**, 4168-80.
- Linder, P. and Lasko, P.** (2006). Bent out of shape: RNA unwinding by the DEAD-box helicase Vasa. *Cell* **125**, 219-21.
- Linder, P. and Slonimski, P. P.** (1989). An essential yeast protein, encoded by duplicated genes TIF1 and TIF2 and homologous to the mammalian translation initiation factor eIF-4A, can suppress a mitochondrial missense mutation. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **86**, 2286-90.
- Liu, Y., Wu, C., Lyu, Q., Yang, D., Albertini, D. F., Keefe, D. L. and Liu, L.** (2007). Germline stem cells and neo-oogenesis in the adult human ovary. *Dev Biol* **306**, 112-20.
- Logan, C. Y., Miller, J. R., Ferkowicz, M. J. and McClay, D. R.** (1999). Nuclear β -catenin is required to specify vegetal cell fates in the sea urchin embryo. *Development* **126**, 345-57.

- Lyczak, R., Gomes, J. E. and Bowerman, B.** (2002). Heads or tails: cell polarity and axis formation in the early *Caenorhabditis elegans* embryo. *Dev Cell* **3**, 157-66.
- Mahowald, A. P.** (2001). Assembly of the *Drosophila* germ plasm. *Int Rev Cytol* **203**, 187-213.
- Mango, S. E., Thorpe, C. J., Martin, P. R., Chamberlain, S. H. and Bowerman, B.** (1994). Two maternal genes, *apx-1* and *pie-1*, are required to distinguish the fates of equivalent blastomeres in the early *Caenorhabditis elegans* embryo. *Development* **120**, 2305-15.
- Martindale, M. Q.** (1986). The ontogeny and maintenance of adult symmetry properties in the ctenophore, *Mnemiopsis mccradyi*. *Dev Biol* **118**, 556-76.
- Matsui, Y. and Okamura, D.** (2005). Mechanisms of germ-cell specification in mouse embryos. *Bioessays* **27**, 136-43.
- McCrea, P. D., Turck, C. W. and Gumbiner, B.** (1991). A homolog of the *armadillo* protein in *Drosophila* (plakoglobin) associated with E-cadherin. *Science* **254**, 1359-61.
- McLaren, A.** (2003). Primordial germ cells in the mouse. *Dev Biol* **262**, 1-15.
- Miller, J. R. and McClay, D. R.** (1997). Changes in the pattern of adherens junction-associated β -catenin accompany morphogenesis in the sea urchin embryo. *Dev Biol* **192**, 310-22.
- Mintz, B.** (1959). Continuity of the female germ cell line from embryo to adult. *Arch Anat Microsc Morphol Exp (Suppl)* **48**, 155-172.

- Miyawaki, K., Mito, T., Sarashina, I., Zhang, H., Shinmyo, Y., Ohuchi, H. and Noji, S.** (2004). Involvement of Wingless/Armadillo signaling in the posterior sequential segmentation in the cricket, *Gryllus bimaculatus* (Orthoptera), as revealed by RNAi analysis. *Mech Dev* **121**, 119-30.
- Mochizuki, K., Nishimiya-Fujisawa, C. and Fujisawa, T.** (2001). Universal occurrence of the *vasa-related* genes among metazoans and their germline expression in *Hydra*. *Dev Genes Evol* **211**, 299-308.
- Moody, S. A.** (1999). Cell Lineage and Fate Determination. San Diego: Academic Press.
- Myers, A. A.** (1985). Shallow-water, coral reef and mangrove Amphipoda (Gammaridea) of Fiji. *Records of the Australian Museum Supplement* **5**, 1-143.
- Nagy, L. M. and Carroll, S.** (1994). Conservation of wingless patterning functions in the short-germ embryos of *Tribolium castaneum*. *Nature* **367**, 460-3.
- Nakao, H.** (1999). Isolation and characterization of a *Bombyx vasa-like* gene. *Dev Genes Evol* **209**, 312-6.
- Nakao, H., Hatakeyama, M., Lee, J. M., Shimoda, M. and Kanda, T.** (2006). Expression pattern of *Bombyx vasa-like* (BmVLG) protein and its implications in germ cell development. *Dev Genes Evol* **216**, 94-9.
- Nardi, F., Spinsanti, G., Boore, J. L., Carapelli, A., Dallai, R. and Frati, F.** (2003). Hexapod origins: monophyletic or paraphyletic? *Science* **299**, 1887-9.

- Nayernia, K., Nolte, J., Michelmann, H. W., Lee, J. H., Rathsack, K., Drusenheimer, N., Dev, A., Wulf, G., Ehrmann, I. E., Elliott, D. J. et al.** (2006). In vitro-differentiated embryonic stem cells give rise to male gametes that can generate offspring mice. *Dev Cell* **11**, 125-32.
- Nelson, W. J. and Nusse, R.** (2004). Convergence of Wnt, β -catenin, and cadherin pathways. *Science* **303**, 1483-7.
- Nieuwkoop, P. D. and Sutasurya, L. A.** (1979). Primordial Germ Cells in the chordates. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Nishida, H.** (1987). Cell lineage analysis in ascidian embryos by intracellular injection of a tracer enzyme. III. Up to the tissue restricted stage. *Dev Biol* **121**, 526-41.
- Nishida, H.** (1992). Regionality of egg cytoplasm that promotes muscle differentiation in the embryo of the ascidian, *Halocynthia roretzi*. *Development* **116**, 521-529.
- Nishida, H.** (2005). Specification of embryonic axis and mosaic development in ascidians. *Dev Dyn* **233**, 1177-93.
- Nishida, H. and Sawada, K.** (2001). *macho-1* encodes a localized mRNA in ascidian eggs that specifies muscle fate during embryogenesis. *Nature* **409**, 724-9.
- Nishikata, T., Hibino, T. and Nishida, H.** (1999). The centrosome-attracting body, microtubule system, and posterior egg cytoplasm are involved in positioning of cleavage planes in the ascidian embryo. *Dev Biol* **209**, 72-85.

- Noce, T., Okamoto-Ito, S. and Tsunekawa, N.** (2001). *Vasa* homolog genes in mammalian germ cell development. *Cell Struct Funct* **26**, 131-6.
- Nulsen, C. and Nagy, L. M.** (1999). The role of *wingless* in the development of multibranching crustacean limbs. *Dev Genes Evol* **209**, 340-8.
- Nusslein-Volhard, C. and Wieschaus, E.** (1980). Mutations affecting segment number and polarity in *Drosophila*. *Nature* **287**, 795-801.
- O'Day, K. E.** (2006). Notch signaling and segmentation in *Parhyale hawaiiensis*. In *Department of Molecular and Cell Biology*, (ed., pp. 1-195. Berkeley: University of California, Berkeley.
- Ohno, S.** (2001). Intercellular junctions and cellular polarity: the PAR-aPKC complex, a conserved core cassette playing fundamental roles in cell polarity. *Curr Opin Cell Biol* **13**, 641-8.
- Okada, M., Kleinman, I. A. and Schneiderman, H. A.** (1974). Restoration of fertility in sterilized *Drosophila* eggs by transplantation of polar cytoplasm. *Dev Biol* **37**, 43-54.
- Patel, N. H., Ball, E. E. and Goodman, C. S.** (1992). Changing role of even-skipped during the evolution of insect pattern formation. *Nature* **357**, 339-42.
- Pavlopoulos, A. and Averof, M.** (2005). Establishing genetic transformation for comparative developmental studies in the crustacean *Parhyale hawaiiensis*. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **102**, 7888-93.
- Pehrson, J. R. and Cohen, L. H.** (1986). The fate of the small micromeres in sea urchin development. *Dev Biol* **113**, 522-6.

- Peifer, M.** (1993). The product of the *Drosophila* segment polarity gene *armadillo* is part of a multi-protein complex resembling the vertebrate adherens junction. *J Cell Sci* **105 (Pt 4)**, 993-1000.
- Perego, C., Vanoni, C., Massari, S., Longhi, R. and Pietrini, G.** (2000). Mammalian LIN-7 PDZ proteins associate with β -catenin at the cell-cell junctions of epithelia and neurons. *Embo J* **19**, 3978-89.
- Pilon, M. and Weisblat, D. A.** (1997). Early events leading to fate decisions during leech embryogenesis. *Semin Cell Dev Biol* **8**, 351-8.
- Price, A. L.** (2005). Gastrulation and mesoderm development in *Parhyale hawaiiensis*. In *Committee on Developmental Biology*, pp. 211. Chicago: University of Chicago.
- Price, A. L. and Patel, N. H.** (2007). Investigating divergent mechanisms of mesoderm development in arthropods: the expression of *Ph-twist* and *Ph-mef2* in *Parhyale hawaiiensis*. *J Exp Zool B Mol Dev Evol* **0**, 0.
- Priess, J. R. and Thomson, J. N.** (1987). Cellular interactions in early *C. elegans* embryos. *Cell* **48**, 241-50.
- Ransick, A., Cameron, R. A. and Davidson, E. H.** (1996). Postembryonic segregation of the germ line in sea urchins in relation to indirect development. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **93**, 6759-63.
- Raz, E.** (2000). The function and regulation of *vasa-like* genes in germ-cell development. *Genome Biol* **1**, REVIEWS1017.
- Raz, E.** (2002). Primordial germ cell development in zebrafish. *Semin Cell Dev Biol* **13**, 489-95.

- Raz, E.** (2003). Primordial germ-cell development: the zebrafish perspective. *Nat Rev Genet* **4**, 690-700.
- Rebscher, N., Zelada-Gonzalez, F., Banisch, T. U., Raible, F. and Arendt, D.** (2007). Vasa unveils a common origin of germ cells and of somatic stem cells from the posterior growth zone in the polychaete *Platynereis dumerilii*. *Dev Biol* **306**, 599-611.
- Ren, X.** (2005). Isolation and characterization of PAR-1 and PAR-6 homologs in *Helobdella robusta*. In *Dept of Molecular and Cellular Biology*. Berkeley: University of California, Berkeley.
- Ren, X. and Weisblat, D. A.** (2006). Asymmetrization of first cleavage by transient disassembly of one spindle pole aster in the leech *Helobdella robusta*. *Dev Biol* **292**, 103-15.
- Ressom, R. E. and Dixon, K. E.** (1988). Relocation and reorganization of germ plasm in *Xenopus* embryos after fertilization. *Development* **103**, 507-18.
- Reverberi, G. and Minganti, A.** (1946). Fenomeni di evocazione nello sviluppo dell'uovo di ascidie. *Pubbl. Stn. Zool. Napoli* **20**, 199-252.
- Riechmann, V. and Ephrussi, A.** (2001). Axis formation during *Drosophila* oogenesis. *Curr Opin Genet Dev* **11**, 374-83.
- Riggleman, B., Schedl, P. and Wieschaus, E.** (1990). Spatial expression of the *Drosophila* segment polarity gene *armadillo* is posttranscriptionally regulated by *wingless*. *Cell* **63**, 549-60.
- Riggleman, B., Wieschaus, E. and Schedl, P.** (1989). Molecular analysis of the *armadillo* locus: uniformly distributed transcripts and a protein with

novel internal repeats are associated with a *Drosophila* segment polarity gene. *Genes Dev* **3**, 96-113.

Robb, D. L., Heasman, J., Raats, J. and Wylie, C. (1996). A kinesin-like protein is required for germ plasm aggregation in *Xenopus*. *Cell* **87**, 823-31.

Rocheleau, C. E., Downs, W. D., Lin, R., Wittmann, C., Bei, Y., Cha, Y. H., Ali, M., Priess, J. R. and Mello, C. C. (1997). Wnt signaling and an APC-related gene specify endoderm in early *C. elegans* embryos. *Cell* **90**, 707-16.

Rocheleau, C. E., Yasuda, J., Shin, T. H., Lin, R., Sawa, H., Okano, H., Priess, J. R., Davis, R. J. and Mello, C. C. (1999). WRM-1 activates the LIT-1 protein kinase to transduce anterior/posterior polarity signals in *C. elegans*. *Cell* **97**, 717-26.

Rose, L. S. and Kemphues, K. J. (1998). Early patterning of the *C. elegans* embryo. *Annu Rev Genet* **32**, 521-45.

Rowning, B. A., Wells, J., Wu, M., Gerhart, J. C., Moon, R. T. and Larabell, C. A. (1997). Microtubule-mediated transport of organelles and localization of β -catenin to the future dorsal side of *Xenopus* eggs. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **94**, 1224-9.

Ruiz-Trillo, I., Riutort, M., Littlewood, D. T., Herniou, E. A. and Baguna, J. (1999). Acoel flatworms: earliest extant bilaterian Metazoans, not members of Platyhelminthes. *Science* **283**, 1919-23.

- Rzhetsky, A. and Nei, M.** (1992). A Simple Method for Estimating and Testing Minimum-Evolution Trees. *Molecular Biology and Evolution* **9**, 945-967.
- Sacco, P. A., McGranahan, T. M., Wheelock, M. J. and Johnson, K. R.** (1995). Identification of plakoglobin domains required for association with N-cadherin and α -catenin. *J Biol Chem* **270**, 20201-6.
- Saffman, E. E. and Lasko, P.** (1999). Germline development in vertebrates and invertebrates. *Cell Mol Life Sci* **55**, 1141-63.
- Sagawa, K., Yamagata, H. and Shiga, Y.** (2005). Exploring embryonic germ line development in the water flea, *Daphnia magna*, by zinc-finger-containing VASA as a marker. *Gene Expr Patterns* **5**, 669-78.
- Santos, A. C. and Lehmann, R.** (2004). Germ cell specification and migration in *Drosophila* and beyond. *Curr Biol* **14**, R578-89.
- Sasakura, Y., Ogasawara, M. and Makabe, K. W.** (2000). Two pathways of maternal RNA localization at the posterior-vegetal cytoplasm in early ascidian embryos. *Dev Biol* **220**, 365-78.
- Sato, K., Shibata, N., Orii, H., Amikura, R., Sakurai, T., Agata, K., Kobayashi, S. and Watanabe, K.** (2006). Identification and origin of the germline stem cells as revealed by the expression of *nanos-related* gene in planarians. *Dev Growth Differ* **48**, 615-28.
- Savage, R. M. and Danilchik, M. V.** (1993). Dynamics of germ plasm localization and its inhibition by ultraviolet irradiation in early cleavage *Xenopus* embryos. *Dev Biol* **157**, 371-82.

- Schmitz, E. H.** (1992). Amphipoda. In *Microscopic Anatomy of Invertebrates: Crustacea*, vol. 9 (ed. F. W. H. Harrison, F. G.), pp. 443-528. New York: Wiley-Liss.
- Schnabel, R.** (1995). Duels without obvious sense: counteracting inductions involved in body wall muscle development in the *Caenorhabditis elegans* embryo. *Development* **121**, 2219-32.
- Schnabel, R.** (1997). Why does a nematode have an invariant cell lineage? *Semin Cell Dev Biol* **8**, 341-9.
- Schneider, S., Steinbeisser, H., Warga, R. M. and Hausen, P.** (1996). β -catenin translocation into nuclei demarcates the dorsalizing centers in frog and fish embryos. *Mech Dev* **57**, 191-8.
- Schneider, S. Q., Finnerty, J. R. and Martindale, M. Q.** (2003). Protein evolution: structure-function relationships of the oncogene β -catenin in the evolution of multicellular animals. *J Exp Zool B Mol Dev Evol* **295**, 25-44.
- Scholtz, G., Patel, N. H. and Dohle, W.** (1994). Serially homologous engrailed stripes are generated via different cell lineages in the germ band of amphipod crustaceans (Malacostraca, Peracarida). *Int J Dev Biol* **38**, 471-8.
- Schram, F. R. a. K., S.** (2004). Are the crustaceans monophyletic? In *Assembling the Tree of Life*, (ed. J. a. D. Cracraft, M. J.), pp. 319-329. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Schroder, R.** (2006). *vasa* mRNA accumulates at the posterior pole during blastoderm formation in the flour beetle *Tribolium castaneum*. *Dev Genes Evol* **216**, 277-83.

- Schupbach, T. and Wieschaus, E.** (1986). Germline autonomy of maternal-effect mutations altering the embryonic body pattern of *Drosophila*. *Dev Biol* **113**, 443-8.
- Seydoux, G. and Fire, A.** (1994). Soma-germline asymmetry in the distributions of embryonic RNAs in *Caenorhabditis elegans*. *Development* **120**, 2823-34.
- Seydoux, G. and Schedl, T.** (2001). The germline in *C. elegans*: origins, proliferation, and silencing. *Int Rev Cytol* **203**, 139-85.
- Shankland, M.** (1984). Positional determination of supernumerary blast cell death in the leech embryo. *Nature* **307**, 541-3.
- Shinomiya, A., Tanaka, M., Kobayashi, T., Nagahama, Y. and Hamaguchi, S.** (2000). The *vasa-like* gene, *olvas*, identifies the migration path of primordial germ cells during embryonic body formation stage in the medaka, *Oryzias latipes*. *Dev Growth Differ* **42**, 317-26.
- Shirae-Kurabayashi, M., Nishikata, T., Takamura, K., Tanaka, K. J., Nakamoto, C. and Nakamura, A.** (2006). Dynamic redistribution of *vasa* homolog and exclusion of somatic cell determinants during germ cell specification in *Ciona intestinalis*. *Development* **133**, 2683-93.
- Shoemaker, C. R.** (1956). Observations on the amphipod genus *Parhyale*. *Proceedings of the United States National Museum* **106**, 345-358.
- Slack, J. M. W.** (1991). From Egg to Embryo: Regional Specification in Early Development. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

- Slanchev, K., Stebler, J., de la Cueva-Mendez, G. and Raz, E.** (2005). Development without germ cells: the role of the germ line in zebrafish sex differentiation. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **102**, 4074-9.
- Strome, S. and Lehmann, R.** (2007). Germ versus soma decisions: lessons from flies and worms. *Science* **316**, 392-3.
- Strome, S. and Wood, W. B.** (1982). Immunofluorescence visualization of germ-line-specific cytoplasmic granules in embryos, larvae, and adults of *Caenorhabditis elegans*. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **79**, 1558-62.
- Sulston, J. E., Schierenberg, E., White, J. G. and Thomson, J. N.** (1983). The embryonic cell lineage of the nematode *Caenorhabditis elegans*. *Dev Biol* **100**, 64-119.
- Sulston, J. E. and White, J. G.** (1980). Regulation and cell autonomy during postembryonic development of *Caenorhabditis elegans*. *Dev Biol* **78**, 577-97.
- Sutasurya, L. A. and Nieuwkoop, P. D.** (1974). The induction of the primordial germ cells in the urodeles. *Wilhem Roux' Arch.* **175**, 199-220.
- Swofford, D. L.** (2002). PAUP*: phylogenetic analysis using parsimony (*and other methods). Sunderland, MA: Sinauer Associates.
- Tadokoro, R., Sugio, M., Kutsuna, J., Tochinai, S. and Takahashi, Y.** (2006). Early segregation of germ and somatic lineages during gonadal regeneration in the annelid *Enchytraeus japonensis*. *Curr Biol* **16**, 1012-7.

- Takamura, K., Fujimura, M. and Yamaguchi, Y.** (2002). Primordial germ cells originate from the endodermal strand cells in the ascidian *Ciona intestinalis*. *Dev Genes Evol* **212**, 11-8.
- Tam, P. P. and Zhou, S. X.** (1996). The allocation of epiblast cells to ectodermal and germ-line lineages is influenced by the position of the cells in the gastrulating mouse embryo. *Dev Biol* **178**, 124-32.
- Tanabe, K. and Kotani, M.** (1974). Relationship between the amount of the 'germinal plasm' and the number of primordial germ cells in *Xenopus laevis*. *J Embryol Exp Morphol* **31**, 89-98.
- Tanaka, S. S., Toyooka, Y., Akasu, R., Katoh-Fukui, Y., Nakahara, Y., Suzuki, R., Yokoyama, M. and Noce, T.** (2000). The mouse homolog of *Drosophila Vasa* is required for the development of male germ cells. *Genes Dev* **14**, 841-53.
- Tanner, N. K., Cordin, O., Banroques, J., Doere, M. and Linder, P.** (2003). The Q motif: a newly identified motif in DEAD box helicases may regulate ATP binding and hydrolysis. *Mol Cell* **11**, 127-38.
- Tanner, N. K. and Linder, P.** (2001). DExD/H box RNA helicases: from generic motors to specific dissociation functions. *Mol Cell* **8**, 251-62.
- Technau, U. and Scholz, C. B.** (2003). Origin and evolution of endoderm and mesoderm. *Int J Dev Biol* **47**, 531-9.
- Thiele, A., Nagamine, Y., Hauschildt, S. and Clevers, H.** (2006). AU-rich elements and alternative splicing in the β -catenin 3'UTR can influence the human β -catenin mRNA stability. *Exp Cell Res* **312**, 2367-78.

- Thompson, J. D., Gibson, T. J., Plewniak, F., Jeanmougin, F. and Higgins, D. G.** (1997). The CLUSTAL X windows interface: Flexible strategies for multiple sequence alignment aided by quality analysis tools. *Nucleic Acids Res* **25**, 4876-4882.
- Thorpe, C. J., Schlesinger, A., Carter, J. C. and Bowerman, B.** (1997). Wnt signaling polarizes an early *C. elegans* blastomere to distinguish endoderm from mesoderm. *Cell* **90**, 695-705.
- Toyooka, Y., Tsunekawa, N., Akasu, R. and Noce, T.** (2003). Embryonic stem cells can form germ cells *in vitro*. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **100**, 11457-62.
- Tsuda, M., Sasaoka, Y., Kiso, M., Abe, K., Haraguchi, S., Kobayashi, S. and Saga, Y.** (2003). Conserved role of *nanos* proteins in germ cell development. *Science* **301**, 1239-41.
- Uchida, D., Yamashita, M., Kitano, T. and Iguchi, T.** (2002). Oocyte apoptosis during the transition from ovary-like tissue to testes during sex differentiation of juvenile zebrafish. *J Exp Biol* **205**, 711-8.
- van den Biggelaar, J. A. and Guerrier, P.** (1979). Dorsoventral polarity and mesentoblast determination as concomitant results of cellular interactions in the mollusk *Patella vulgata*. *Dev Biol* **68**, 462-71.
- van Eeden, F. and St Johnston, D.** (1999). The polarisation of the anterior-posterior and dorsal-ventral axes during *Drosophila* oogenesis. *Curr Opin Genet Dev* **9**, 396-404.

- Varga, M., Maegawa, S., Bellipanni, G. and Weinberg, E. S.** (2007). Chordin expression, mediated by Nodal and FGF signaling, is restricted by redundant function of two beta-catenins in the zebrafish embryo. *Mech Dev.* **124**, 775-91.
- Walker, C. and Streisinger, G.** (1983). Induction of mutations by γ -rays in pregonial germ cells of zebrafish embryos. *Genetics* **103**, 125-136.
- Wang, Y. and Gu, X.** (2000). Evolutionary patterns of gene families generated in the early stage of vertebrates. *J Mol Evol* **51**, 88-96.
- Weidinger, G., Stebler, J., Slanchev, K., Dumstrei, K., Wise, C., Lovell-Badge, R., Thisse, C., Thisse, B. and Raz, E.** (2003). *dead end*, a novel vertebrate germ plasm component, is required for zebrafish primordial germ cell migration and survival. *Curr Biol* **13**, 1429-34.
- Wieschaus, E. and Noell, E.** (1986). Specificity of embryonic lethal mutations in *Drosophila* analyzed in germline clones. *Roux's Arch. Dev. Biol.*, 63-73.
- Wieschaus, E. and Riggleman, R.** (1987). Autonomous requirements for the segment polarity gene armadillo during *Drosophila* embryogenesis. *Cell* **49**, 177-84.
- Wikramanayake, A. H., Hong, M., Lee, P. N., Pang, K., Byrum, C. A., Bince, J. M., Xu, R. and Martindale, M. Q.** (2003). An ancient role for nuclear β -catenin in the evolution of axial polarity and germ layer segregation. *Nature* **426**, 446-50.

- Wikramanayake, A. H., Huang, L. and Klein, W. H.** (1998). β -catenin is essential for patterning the maternally specified animal-vegetal axis in the sea urchin embryo. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **95**, 9343-8.
- Wodarz, A. and Nusse, R.** (1998). Mechanisms of Wnt signaling in development. *Annu Rev Cell Dev Biol* **14**, 59-88.
- Wolf, N., Priess, J. and Hirsh, D.** (1983). Segregation of germline granules in early embryos of *Caenorhabditis elegans*: an electron microscopic analysis. *J Embryol Exp Morphol* **73**, 297-306.
- Wolff, C. and Scholtz, G.** (2002). Cell lineage, axis formation, and the origin of germ layers in the amphipod crustacean *Orchestia cavimana*. *Dev Biol* **250**, 44-58.
- Wolke, U., Weidinger, G., Köprunner, M. and Raz, E.** (2002). Multiple levels of posttranscriptional control lead to germ line-specific gene expression in the zebrafish. *Curr Biol* **12**, 289-94.
- Wolpert, L.** (2007). Principles of Development. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Yoon, C., Kawakami, K. and Hopkins, N.** (1997). Zebrafish *vasa* homologue RNA is localized to the cleavage planes of 2- and 4-cell-stage embryos and is expressed in the primordial germ cells. *Development* **124**, 3157-65.
- Yost, C., Torres, M., Miller, J. R., Huang, E., Kimelman, D. and Moon, R. T.** (1996). The axis-inducing activity, stability, and subcellular

distribution of β -catenin is regulated in *Xenopus* embryos by glycogen synthase kinase 3. *Genes Dev* **10**, 1443-54.

Zerbib, C. (1980). Ultrastructural observation of oogenesis in the crustacean amphipoda *Orchestia gammarellus* (Pallas). *Tissue Cell* **12**, 47-62.